

D1.3

Potential effects of remote working arrangements on the working and living conditions

Koç University (KU)

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BERTopic	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
CATI	Computer-Assisted Telephone Interviewing
CAWI	Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing
COR	Conservation of Resources
Covid-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CVD	Cardiovascular Diseases
EMCC	European Mentoring and Coaching Council
ESENER	European Survey of Enterprises on New and Emerging Risks
EU OSHA	European Agency for Safety and Health at Work
EU	European Union
EUROFOUND	European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions
EWCS	European Working Conditions Survey
EWCTS	European Working Conditions Tele Survey
GHG	Green House Gas
GIS	Gastro Intestinal System
HDBSCAN	Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
HTWC	Home-to-Work Conflict
ICT	Information and Communications Technology

ILO	International Labour Organization
JD-R	Job Demands-Resources
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
MSD	Musculoskeletal
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NWW	New Ways of Working
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OSH	Occupational Safety and Health
RO	Research Objective
RQ	Research Question
RWAs	Remote Working Arrangements
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIP	Social Information Processing
SSRN	Social Science Research Network
UN	United Nations
WFH	Work-From Home
WHO	World Health Organization
WHO-IRIS	World Health Organization- Institutional Repository for Information Sharing

WTC	Work Time Control
WTHC	Work-to-Home Conflict

Executive Summary

This report, titled '**Deliverable 1.3 for Work Package 1 - Setting the Scene,**' seeks to **deepen our understanding of the potential effects of remote working arrangements (RWAs) on working and living conditions.** It also highlights key findings related to work-life balance, health and well-being, and gender-specific aspects associated with these conditions with the objectives explored as follows:

Setting the literature scene: Key trends and topics RWAs over the past decade

Working Conditions: Impact of RWAs on organisational and individual conditions

Living Conditions: Influence of RWAs on living conditions.

Work-Life Balance: Influence of RWAs on balancing professional and personal life the balance between professional and personal life

Health and Well-Being: Impact of RWAs on health, behaviours, well-being

Gender-Associated Factors: Gender-specific challenges and their influence on work-life dynamics

To achieve these objectives a **mixed exploratory research approach** was employed, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods. Topic Modelling Analyses were used to identify key themes from existing interdisciplinary literature. Data Re-analysis utilised the 2021 European Working Conditions Telephone Survey to offer observational insights. Finally, an Exploratory Narrative Review was carried out to integrate findings from both scientific and grey literature.

The findings reveal that remote work has significantly transformed **working conditions**, impacting both physical and digital environments, organisational dynamics and individual roles. This shift present challenges in terms of accessibility, adaptability, and reliance on digital services and skills. Issues such as taxation, labour laws, and unionisation are critical in preventing inequalities and vulnerabilities.

While remote work offers **increased job satisfaction and autonomy**, it **risks fostering a detached work culture** and widening gaps between remote and on-site workers. The findings highlight the **importance of organisational factors** in sustaining engagement, satisfaction, and workplace culture, all of which are closely linked to mental health outcomes. Maintaining these elements requires careful monitoring and a tailored Occupational Health and Safety (OSH) framework to address the specific challenges of remote work.

Remote work also affects **living conditions** by altering the relationship between environmental factors and access to services. **Household dynamics**, particularly caregiving responsibilities, significantly influence the remote work experience. Flexible work policies that accommodate diverse family structures is crucial. **Gender-specific challenges** show that men and women experience remote work differently, with gender norms heavily influencing their experiences. Women may struggle more with balancing work and caregiving, highlighting the need for inclusive policies to address disparities. Remote work can improve work-life balance by reducing fatigue and stress through increased flexibility. However, concerns remain about extended working hours offsetting the benefits of reduced commuting time.

The results indicate that **remote work** environments have a **complex association with well-being, affecting health, behaviour, and mental health**. While well-organised remote work can lead to positive outcomes, such as improved mental health and healthier behaviours, risks such as loneliness, social isolation, and unstructured environments persist. Key health behaviours—such as physical activity, diet, and sleep—are particularly vulnerable due to the blurred boundaries potentially leading to harmful habits (Mustafa and Gold, 2012; Spieler et al, 2017). Targeted interventions to foster social connections, promote positive health behaviours are crucial for enhancing mental well-being in remote work environments (Rothbard and Ollier, 2016).

Comprehensive support systems, including **OSH services addressing the bio-psycho-social aspects** of health, are necessary to mitigate these risks. Mental health challenges associated with remote work, particularly those related to **loneliness and isolation**, can adversely affect job satisfaction and motivation, highlighting the need for targeted interventions.

A critical insight is the **variability in access and availability** to (RWAs). Enhancing remote work infrastructure is essential to **ensure equitable access** to necessary tools and services. These disparities extend beyond technology, affecting access to employee services, career development opportunities, and living conditions. Workers in less developed regions may be disadvantaged not only in accessing remote work tools but also in participating in organisational activities, benefiting, and progressing in their careers. Addressing these disparities is crucial to ensure equal opportunities for all workers in remote work settings.

Remote work also introduces **new ethical considerations**, potential disparities. Ethical implications must be carefully evaluated to ensure fairness and equity. Developing ethical guidelines and policies, alongside research and theoretical frameworks, is crucial to addressing the challenges and inequalities associated with

remote work. Additionally, remote work can lead to **presenteeism where employees overwork due to** blurred boundaries between work and personal life, resulting in burn-out, and reduced long-term productivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

This report is produced as part of the R-Map project under the Grant Agreement (GA) No.101132497 and funded by the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon Europe. This document is prepared for Work Package 1 - ‘**Setting the Scene**’ and Task 1.3 - ‘**Understanding the potential effects of remote working arrangements on the working and living conditions**’, which seeks to advance our understanding of potential effects of remote working arrangements (RWAs) on working and living conditions of remote workers.

1.1 Background

As the ‘world of work’ is rapidly changing, work and living conditions are becoming increasingly important and presenting new opportunities and challenges, especially due to the significant rise in remote working after the Covid-19. Remote working - also known as teleworking - involves working from home or other locations under flexible working conditions, often using information and communication technologies, outside of traditional office environments (WHO/ILO, 2021; ILO, 2024; Beckel and Fisher, 2022). Additionally, RWAs which are often used interchangeably with ‘telework’ arrangements in some literature, are changing and challenging traditional expectations regarding the use of terminology RWAs embody such as working and living environments, including employment relations, working conditions such as income, job opportunities, commuting time, infrastructure, and employee services including occupational health services (Huras-Darkowska, 2021; Martinez, 2021; Waters, 2015). **This report will use the term ‘Remote working arrangements (RWAs)’ for the purposes of the study to address broader aspects, including remote and hybrid models.**

1.1.1 Transition to New Modes of Employment

The world is transitioning from traditional work arrangements to new types and paradigms of employment. Current practices to maintain the benefits of RWAs based on technological developments vary widely in different contexts. There is heterogeneity across countries, enterprises, and sectors depending on the work location infrastructure and preferences at multiple (micro, mezzo, and macro) levels. Based on the rapid uptake of remote work during and after the Covid-19 pandemic, the transition of employment types and

demands that require clear procedures in all respects, are supported by scientific evidence, with future iterations. Ozimek (2020) analysed how the ovidCovid-19 pandemic has dramatically accelerated the shift to remote work, affecting the current and future workforce trends. As part of a survey, they collected data in two episodes, the first one in 2019 and the second in 2020, after the onset of pandemic, with more than 1500 hiring managers, including executives, vice presidents and others. During this period, the percentage of hiring managers with fully remote teams rose from 2.3% in 2019 to 20% in 2020, and the proportion of the labour force working entirely remote increased from around 13.2% in 2019 to between 56% and 74% in the post-pandemic era (Ozimek, 2020). According to the findings, 56% of hiring managers reported that the remote work period went better than expected, with only 10% reporting worse than expected. The main benefits identified were (i) no commute (49%), (ii) fewer non-essential meetings (46.3%), and (iii) fewer office distractions (41.2%). Roughly a third of managers reported an increase in productivity (32.3%), while 22.5% reported a decrease. Hiring managers expect their workforce to be more in a remote setting (61.9%). Furthermore, research by Dingel and Neiman (2020) reveals that 37% of the jobs can be performed fully remotely, and these jobs tend to offer a higher pay compared to those that cannot be done remotely (Dingel and Neiman, 2020).

Advancements in technology, particularly in jobs related to the knowledge economy, have led to a shift towards home-offices and hybrid spaces in work life that combine the workplace with social and private spheres in the world of work. This type of flexible working arrangement requires specific and increasing attention using technological advancements, instituting societal changes, and considering economic factors (Berkery, 2024; Yaroshenko, 2024) and it can potentially lead to permanent changes in employment patterns previously accepted as 'remote working practices' widely in information technologies (IT) sectors, banking, and some other sectors (Xia, 2024; Aleem, 2023). As this phenomenon has been spread to other sectors and diversified under the flexible working arrangements, it has become necessary to explore future directions. However, the Covid-19 pandemic and the subsequent expansion of work types and practices from office to home and collaborative offices and platforms have left a considerable gap. This gap needs to be viewed holistically as an essential component for the continued evolution of the world of work by pushing related challenges and bringing alternative work environments and work-related terminology structure practices into the mainstream.

These studies reflect that the pandemic has accelerated the shift towards remote working, with more companies recognising the benefits and planning for a more remote future. The shift is expected to bring long-term changes in the workforce, potentially leading to increased productivity and a broader geographic reach for recruiting new talent. Discussed benefits of RWAs include improved work-life balance, job satisfaction, and organisational flexibility (Wöhner, 2023). However, remote work also brings along its challenges identified as follows (Oppong Peprah, 2024): isolation, time management issues, blurred work-life boundaries (Beckel and Fisher, 2022; Joseph et. al., 2023; de Macêdo et. al., 2020; Elshaiekh et. al., 2018), ergonomics and the complexity of health, well-being, performance, and individual, organisational or macro-level factor dynamics. These evolutions need further considerations to devise effective implementation strategies to evaluate long-term effects (de Macêdo et. al., 2020).

In this context, **the following factors contribute to a healthy life** and are essential for sustainability in working life (Gupta et. al., 2024):

- Prevention of psycho-social risks in work life
- Bio-psycho-social well-being developed through healthy lifestyles
- Quality of working life and employee services (e.g. occupational health and safety, emergency planning, communication, infrastructure related to virtual work and leisure needs)

1.1.2 Emergence of hybrid models and impacts on planning

The concept of remote work previously considered atypical, non-standard practice, is now being widely adopted by examining both the advantages and disadvantages of integrating it into the 'world of work'. The challenges encompass environmental, urban, rural, and infrastructural elements, creating a ripple effect that extends beyond working conditions and ultimately impacts them as well.

Remote work has the capacity to involve large numbers of people in labour relations and employment (Ludanik and Reshetova, 2021). The shift to remote working has the potential to reduce historical inequalities resulting from the demands of the modern workplace (Lord, 2020).

Companies are developing their policies and practices in collaboration with employees and employers to find better ways to sustain the workforce and the economy while transforming the world of work from traditional office-based employment into a new paradigm that offer flexibility and convenience to both employees and

employers. This collaborative approach ensures that all stakeholders' needs and concerns are considered, fostering a sense of inclusion and shared responsibility. However, the transition to remote working has brought various challenges to the working environment, living environment, organisations, and individuals' work-life interface, health and well-being. These challenges manifest differently in rural and urban settings and may vary across gender perspectives.

It is anticipated that new hybrid working models will emerge with the developments of digital technologies. These offer individual autonomy and organisational flexibility, potentially transforming the way of work. However, they also present uncertain challenges to work-life balance, health and well-being (EU-OSHA 2023a; EU-OSHA, 2023b). These challenges often address the associations between work arrangements and individual health and well-being, vary and depend on the characteristics of work, relationships and skills. Experiences, particularly in relation to work-life balance, health and well-being of workers, job characteristics and the social context of work are the main variables discussed in the literature (Beckel and Fisher, 2022). Employees who work remotely for around 40% of their working hours experience the most favourable outcomes in the study by Beckel and Fisher (2022). Another study explored the use of technology in the home office modality, including its benefits, challenges, and the need for the adequacy of this modality and the digital inclusion of employees, based on research and data collection from professionals who have worked from home (De Carvalho et. al., 2022). According to their findings, the main advantages of the home office modality were reduced travel, freedom in dress code, flexible schedules, cost reduction, less distraction, and increased productivity. On the other hand, the main disadvantages were:

- Social isolation
- Increased working hours
- Lack of support
- Difficulty in career progression
- Inability to take time off
- Increased costs to employees

Integrating the business world into the digital environment and the adaptability of organisations is essential to creating better, more effective arrangements as well as monitoring and improving these challenges.

The transition to new forms of employment, particularly remote and hybrid working models, presents both significant opportunities and challenges. It is vital that stakeholders, including employers, policy-makers and community organisations, devise clear and evidence-based practices that support the evolving nature of work.

This could be achieved through harnessing improved common perspectives towards further directions in RWAs related research literature. There is need to employ a set of standardised minimum core variables for the future and a minimum definition approach to track RWAs as well as related individual, professional and societal impacts over time.

1.1.3 Definitions and terminology

In the evolving employment landscape, the need for standardised and accurate terminology has become increasingly important for mutual understanding. With the proliferation of remote and hybrid working models, the diversity of employment arrangements has increased, including different modalities in different sectors, job and contract types. This diversity requires clear and consistent terminology to ensure effective communication, accurate research and policy development. Having a nuanced understanding of employment related terms in different resources is essential for researchers, policymakers, employers and workers to decipher and navigate the information. Standardised definitions allow more reliable comparisons across studies, facilitate assessment of job quality and conditions, and contribute to the creation of evidence-informed practices that can underpin the changing nature of work.

This chapter provides insights into the various components of the working environment, focusing on the terminology used to describe each component in different circumstances and models. This report makes use of the terms as defined in Table 1. There are certain differences across the variables and concepts relating to teleworking and remote work, which they are often being used interchangeably, sometimes both being referred to as 'flexible working' (Huras-Darkowska, 2021).

Due to the rapid developments, the focus of research on the multifactorial aspects of different disciplines and the need to provide evidence, the literature includes some overlapping and intertwined terms in an effort to quickly identify the effect and prevent adverse outcomes in separate but related antecedents in their complexity. This suggests the need for mutually specific definitions of each terminology for interdisciplinary research or the extension of specific mutual definitions for policy areas based on the interdisciplinary and multidimensional characteristics of remote working conditions. This is because some conceptual definitions and approaches in the literature play an important role in developing specifically defined forms of remote work, actions and policies. Considering the challenges with respect to coordinating efforts within the EU and beyond, through agreements on technological developments and improvements, there is a need to

standardise the terminological definitions used specifically related to the formulation and implementation of future shared objectives.

Different forms of remote work partially overlap, and by convention, this report used the following definitions (ILO, 2020; Sostero, 2020; EU-OSHA, 2022d; (EU-OSHA, 2023a; Eurofound, 2022b; Eurofound, 2023a).

- **Remote work** refers to any type of work arrangement where workers work remotely, away from the employer’s premises (or a fixed location), using information and communications technologies (ICT) (e.g. networks, laptops, mobile phones and the Internet).
 - Telework is a sub-category of remote work when remote work involving ICTs is performed from home (or more rarely in out-of-the-home-based office spaces dedicated to teleworking). It includes, by definition, only work that entails a formal relationship between an employer and an employee.
- **Hybrid work** is a combination of telework and work at the employer’s premises. In this **mode** of work, an employee may work both from the office and from home (or from an out-of-the-homebased office space dedicated to remote working or another location such as a café, means of transport, etc.) (Eurofound, 2022b). In practice, hybrid work is mainly performed both from home (including telework) and at the employer’s premises. The weekly distribution of the teleworking and on-site work periods varies widely, e.g. one, two or more days of telework per week (Eurofound, 2023b). As teleworkers, hybrid workers use digital technologies and an Internet connection for work ‘always’ or ‘almost all of the time,’ whichever the location of work.
- **Workplace / on-site work** refers to ‘Work at the employers’ premises’ full-time work on site that may involve occasional telework (of a duration of less than 10% of the working time).

Table 1: Definition of different forms of remote working arrangements

The establishment of common definitions and standardisation of research terminology is crucial to promote a mutual understanding and to increase reliability of findings across studies. Diverse forms of non-standard

employment, such as temporary, part-time and home-based work on digital platforms, require clear and consistent definitions to ensure accurate analysis and comparability. Similarly, key employment concepts such as sustainable work, undeclared work and impact of an ageing workforce require standardised definitions to facilitate coherent discussions and effective policymaking.

As research continues to explore the evolving landscape of employment, maintaining a commitment to common definitions and further standardisation will be essential. This approach not only enhances the clarity and applicability of research findings, but also strengthens collaborative efforts and promotes meaningful progress in the field of employment research.

By clarifying the terminology used in the context of this report, we aim to improve the clarity and applicability of research findings, to support the formulation of policies and practices that meet diverse needs encompassed by these terminologies. Appendix 1 seeks to give an overview the key employment-related terms that are critical to understanding existing knowledge.

1.2 Objectives

This report comprises Deliverable 1.3 in the context of T1.3, investigating the ‘Potential effects of remote working arrangements on working and living conditions.’ More specifically, **the report places special emphasis on potential long-term changes in (i) working conditions (e.g. working hours, work autonomy, work fatigue), (ii) form and nature of employment, (iii) occupational health and safety, (iv) costs for employer / employee (v) work-life balance and well-being (e.g. mental health, depression, loneliness, feeling of social exclusion) and (vi) overall working life quality, through a gender-specific lens.**

This report investigates the potential effects of Remote Working Arrangements (RWAs) on various aspects of work and life, utilising a structured analysis based on six key research questions. The analysis draws on information extracted from both scientific and grey literature, exploring different dimensions of RWAs and their implications. It also includes data analysis to offer insights summarised from the collected data. The findings are aligned with the specific objectives outlined in the narrative review and seek to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of RWAs.

The methodology used in this report explores the research objectives (ROs) listed below, guiding the topics of investigation:

RO1: Explore the key topic trends and distributions related to RWAs in scientific publications over the past ten years (e.g. distribution of publications, topic distribution, and trends over the years).

RO2: Investigate how RWAs might influence organisational and individual working conditions (e.g. the form and nature of employment, costs for employees and employers, organisational services, psychosocial factors, job quality indicators, occupational health and safety services, and employee services).

RO3: Examine how RWAs could shape living conditions (e.g. working from home, location, and household dynamics).

RO4: Explore how RWAs could impact the balance between professional and personal life (e.g. the conceptual transition effects of RWAs in supporting the work-life interface, aiming to promote well-being).

RO5: Assess the potential effects of RWAs on health outcomes and well-being (e.g. behaviours and overall well-being).

RO6: Identify gender-specific challenges that could arise from RWAs, and how they might influence work-life dynamics (e.g. flexible working practices, work intensity, health outcomes, monitoring and support, working models, and reducing inequalities through a gender-specific lens).

1.3 Document Structure

The report includes six chapters, structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1 - INTRODUCTION:** Introduction provides a brief background, an overview of new employment types of transition and some remote working arrangements related terminology used in the literature.
- **Chapter 2 – METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW:** The methodological overview provides a detailed explanation of the research methodology, including research questions, sources of information, and the selection process. It also outlines the approach for re-analysing and evaluating data, incorporating flow diagrams that illustrate the review process.

Methodology and related research objectives are as follows:

- Data re-analysis of EWCTS 21 (Setting the scene in real data example)
- Topic modelling and BERTopic (Setting the scene in the interdisciplinary scientific literature)

- Systematic literature search (Explore research questions related scene in the literature)
- **Chapter 3 – RESULTS OF DATA RE-ANALYSIS: (RO2-6)** This chapter provides summary of key working and living conditions findings relating to work location (remote/hybrid and on-site work) focused evaluation and re-analysis of **data EWCTS 21**.
 - Demographics, location and household dynamics (RO1,3)
 - Work Life Characteristics (RO2,3,4)
 - WHO-5 Well-being (RO5)
 - Health related outcomes with a gender lens (RO5-6)
 - Summary of the key results from the univariate and multivariate analysis
- **Chapter 4 – RESULTS OF LITERATURE REVIEW**
 - **Topic modelling and BERTopic (RO1)** related findings
 - **Working conditions related findings (RO2)** enable us to explore of potential impact of RWAs on various forms and nature of employment, working conditions, quality of work/job indicators, psycho-social factors at work, occupational health and safety, and organisational outcomes.
 - **The results on living conditions (RQ3)** offer an exploratory perspective on aspects related to remote working arrangements, including both the living and working environments
 - The chapter on **work-life balance (RQ4)** summarises the two key aspects of the concept, which can either reconciliation or conflict between working and living conditions in remote work. It explores the 'work-to-home' and 'home-to-work' interfaces, examining how these dynamics affect overall work and life environments.
 - Findings related to **health and well-being (RQ5)** summarise relevant literature on how different working arrangements can affect bio-psycho-social well-being and mental health, including potential consequences, such as loneliness.
 - **Gender perspective (RQ6)** summarises the findings specifically through a gender lens.
- **Chapter 5- POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS:** In addition to recommendations based on the findings, it offers:
 - a new conceptual framework and overview of
 - possible alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals.

- **Chapter 6 – CONCLUSIONS**
- **Appendices**

2. METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW

2.1 Research Design

This report is based on a mixed exploratory design (Figure 1). It encompasses three main approaches, with detailed information on the sources for each section provided in Section 2.3 and 2.4:

- 1- Analysis of data from the 2021 European Working Conditions Telephone Survey (for setting scene in the real data example).
- 2- Topic Modelling and BERTopic modelling (for setting the scene of the literature)
- 3- An exploratory narrative review (to provide comprehensive understanding on research questions related associations)

Figure 1: Conceptual structure of the report

The first part includes a descriptive and comparative analysis of the European Working Conditions Survey-2021 (EWCS) microdata includes both the existing calculated variables and a recoded analysis of the 'work location variable'. Based on the new category related analysis approach, this section involves recoding work locations into three categories: remote, hybrid, and on-site(workplace). The recoding process introduces a new definition of remote work based on the objectives outlined in D1.3., ensuring that the classification aligns with the specific criteria and goals set forth in the report. This section provides a snapshot of the existing data in relation to the RMAP D1.3 objectives.

The second section presents research clusters and distributions to provide insights into future directions. This is achieved by combining Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic modelling, with expert-guided hierarchical clustering and BERTopic modelling, all drawn from a vast interdisciplinary literature. In the hybrid model combining LDA and BERTopic, content experts refine and enhance the initial topic clusters generated by LDA by applying the more contextually aware clustering capabilities of BERTopic. The process is detailed below:

- Initial clustering with LDA: LDA is first used to identify broad topics across the document set by grouping words that co-occur frequently into topics. The authors first renamed the broad topics identified by LDA for clarity, and then transferred these selected and renamed topics to BERTopic for further refinement and precise clustering based on contextual embeddings.
- Expert clustering with BERTopic: These broad LDA-generated topics are then passed through BERTopic, which uses advanced transformer-based embeddings (like BERT) to understand the deeper, contextual relationships between words. BERTopic further refines these topics by breaking down the broad clusters into more precise, semantically rich subtopics.

The third part consists of a systematic search of the scientific published and grey literature based narrative review of the targeted topics. In this approach, the methodology outlines the data sources and search strategy for each stage, detailed under specific sub-headings along with the corresponding search results. It is important to note that the findings of a review included in this section contributes conceptually to the body of knowledge on Remote Working Arrangements (RWAs). The concept and theoretical papers based on topic modelling were included in the review to explore their contributions, especially where other data sources were lacking, with a focus on evaluating the effects of Remote Working Arrangements (RWAs).

Adopting and combining LDA and BERTopic modelling purpose:

While LDA provides a broad overview by categorising the literature into distinct topics for topic discovery and topic distribution, BERTopic can dynamically adjust to variations in topic definitions across different segments of the corpus to capture evolving trends in the literature over time, identify shifts in research focus or emerging areas of interest. Together they provide for both a macro and micro understanding of the literature.

LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation): LDA is a generative statistical model used in natural language processing for topic modelling. It discovers the underlying topics within a collection of documents by assuming that each document is a mixture of a small number of topics and that each word within the document is assigned to one of these topics. LDA works by identifying groups of words that frequently occur in different documents and classifying them into topics.

BERTopic: BERTopic is a topic modelling technique that uses transformer-based embeddings such as BERT combined with clustering algorithms such as HDBSCAN. It generates dense vector representations of documents, clusters them based on similarity, and then extracts the most representative words for each cluster to form topics. BERTopic provides a more semantically rich and context-aware approach to topic modelling than traditional methods such as LDA (Grootendorst, 2022).

Hybrid modelling with LDA and BERTopic:

This approach integrates Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and BERTopic to improve topic discovery within a corpus of documents. LDA, a generative probabilistic model, is used to identify general topic distributions by assuming that documents are a mixture of latent topics, where each topic is characterised by a distribution over words. BERTopic, on the other hand, uses transformer-based embeddings (such as BERT) to capture contextual word representations and clusters these embeddings to form more nuanced and semantically meaningful topics.

In a hybrid workflow, LDA can be used initially to generate broad topic distributions, which can then be refined by BERTopic to capture deeper, context-aware topics. This combination allows the extraction of both broad thematic content and more fine-grained, contextually rich topics, providing a comprehensive understanding of the document set.

Expert clustering in this hybrid model involves taking the broad themes identified by LDA and using BERTopic to drill down into those themes, revealing more specific and meaningful clusters within the broader themes. The result is a more detailed and accurate topic structure that combines the strengths of both methods.

2.2 Research Questions related to the objectives

As stated in section 1.2 the objective of the research to evaluate the potential effects of remote working arrangements (RWAs) on working and living conditions, with a focus on work-life balance, health and well-being, and gender-specific aspects by using a mixed exploratory research approach.

The methodology used in this report explores the research questions in relation to the research objectives:

RQ1: What are the key trends and topic distributions in Remote Working Arrangements (RWAs) as identified in scientific publications over the past ten years (e.g. distribution of publications, topic distribution, and trends over the years)?

RQ2: How do RWAs influence organisational and individual working conditions (e.g. the form and nature of employment, costs for employees and employers, organisational services, psycho-social factors, job quality indicators, occupational health and safety services, and employee services)?

RQ3: In what ways could RWAs shape living conditions, considering factors such as location and household dynamics (e.g. working from home, work location, and household dynamics)?

RQ4: How could RWAs impact the balance between professional and personal life (e.g. the conceptual transition effects of RWAs in supporting the work-life interface, aiming to promote well-being)?

RQ5: What are the potential effects of RWAs on health outcomes, behaviours, and overall well-being (e.g. behaviours and overall well-being)?

RQ6: What gender-specific challenges could arise from RWAs, and how do they influence work-life dynamics (e.g. flexible working practices, work intensity, health outcomes, monitoring and support, working models, and reducing inequalities through a gender-specific lens)?

2.3 Data Re-analysis approach

2.3.1 EWCTS 2021 Micro-data source:

The researchers reached out to various institutes and business cases to request microdata for analysis and reporting on RWAs. Access to the European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS) 2021 data was provided as an independent file on 11 June 2024, during the period of D1.3 (Eurofound, 2022a), for analysis. [the 2021 European Working Conditions Telephone Survey \(EWCTS\)](#)² methodology for our report is based on microdata provided by Eurofound, accessed through the [U.K. Data Service](#)³. This data was collected in 2021 through a cross-sectional survey conducted by Eurofound. The questionnaire⁴ and detailed information on the methodology can be found at the Eurofound website (Eurofound, 2022b). The [Data](#) used in the Eurofound EWCTS 2021 reports include calculated categorical variables related to working conditions⁵. Data related process is sustained in compliance with Eurofound and national copyright provision on reproduction. Methodological documents provided by EUROFOUND with the metadata are used to prepare consequent analyses and evaluate the results. The details are presented under the secondary analysis results sub-chapter.

It should be noted that the term ‘remote work’ is defined exclusively within the context of the variable’s information and recoding sections.

Information about the ‘European Working Conditions Telephone Survey (EWCTS) 2021’: Eurofound provided valuable reports from collected data during a period of significant change in working life and recovery, EWCTS is one of them (Eurofound, 2022a). The data collection was carried out using various interviewing modes in time, including face-to-face and telephone surveys. Due to changes in these modes over time, direct comparisons with previous survey editions are not possible.

²<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/european-working-conditions-telephone-survey-2021>

³<https://beta.ukdataservice.ac.uk/datacatalogue/studies/study?id=9026>

⁴<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/surveys/european-working-conditions-surveys/ewcts-2021/ewcts-2021-questionnaire>

⁵<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/surveys/european-working-conditions-surveys/ewcts-2021/ewcts-2021-methodology>

2.3.2 Variables information

In this section, data from [the 2021 European Working Conditions Telephone Survey \(EWCTS\)](#) is used to evaluate D1.3-related information by analysing microdata based on the newly defined work location variables.

To align with our objectives, data are summarised based on a population that includes only three categories (remote, hybrid, and workplace), derived from the original dataset. Other variables are utilised as calculated versions within the data. Sociodemographic variables are presented in Table 2 and working life related variables are summarised in Table 3.

Descriptive univariate comparative statistics are given in summary tables of each section and as a summary finding at the end, along with comparisons between groups of Remote (hybrid included) workplace comparisons and remote-hybrid comparisons. The chi-square test was used to analyse the differences in between categories according to the work location (Confidence Interval 95%, alpha: 0.05).

Variable	Measure	From data of EWCTS questionnaire	Variable categories used from the data received. No recalculation was performed. Recoding based on existing versions
Overall Distribution	Work location	QM35	Recoded
Country origin	Country origin	EU 27	Not recoded
Urbanity	Living place	Urban/rural	Not recoded
Gender	Gender (calculated variable used)	QN4F, Q2	Yes/ 2 category; only limited numbers of respondent in the other respondents' group
Education	Education level	Q106	Yes/3 category calculated version used
Age Group (16-24)	Working age groups	Q92b	Yes/4 category
Housework	Distribution of housework responsibilities	Q45B, Q45D, Q95D	Yes, calculated v.
Childcare	Distribution of childcare responsibilities	Q95C	Yes, calculated v.

Table 2: Summary of the sociodemographic variables in visuals and statistics section of this report (labels and categories based on the data EWCTS 2021)

Working life characteristics	Information: Variable categories were used from the data received. No recalculation was performed. Recoding based on exist versions; (recoded for logistic regression)
Sector type	Private/ public/joint/ NGO/ other
Employment type	Employee, Self-employed
Working time	Part-time/full-time
Working during free time	Very easy- fairly easy, fairly difficult, very difficult
Ability to take time off	Very easy- fairly easy, fairly difficult, very difficult
Seniority	Less than a year/1-4,5-9, 10 or more
Working Hours	Working hours, Q2d, Q26, Q24; categorical 48 hours more or less per week
Computer Usage	Computer usage, Q30J
Work-Life Balance	Work-life balance by gender, Q44, (calculated variable used)
Boss gender	Women/man
Engagement Level	Engagement Level (low to high)
Occupational Health Risk	Occupational Health Risk, Q73
Insecure work	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Work Intensity	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Physical Demand	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Social Demands (discrimination)	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Unsocial Working Tim	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Autonomy	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Flexible Working Time	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Social Support	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Self-Realization	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)
Learning and Development	Job quality calculated variable used from data (0-1)

Table 3: Summary of the variables used from data working life characteristics

2.3.3 Creation of 'loc-work adjusted' variable

To analyse collected data according to the 'work location' to understand and explore RWAs related variables in the collected data new 'work location variable' was created. Data summarised in this report focuses on this

'work location' variable, by using 'existing calculated' variables (Table 4) from the 2021 European Working Conditions Telephone Survey (EWCTS).

In the original data report is a summary on 'loc_work' variable to look over distributions related to remote, hybrid and on-site as defined in below:

The definitions of the '**remote**', '**hybrid**' and '**workplace/office/on-site**' categories in the 'work location' variable, do not include the 'client' and the 'vehicle' categories, which are part of the Eurofound data set. For our project we excluded "clients and vehicle" locations from the original population, as they do not align with the RMAP focus. For more details given in the Eurofound reports (Eurofound 2023a; Eurofound, EWCTS 2021 [Questionnaire⁶](#); [Methodology⁷](#)).

All graphics demonstrate the distribution of each work location in respective categories. **It is important to keep in mind that these graphs are not related to the total distribution of each category; instead, they are only representing the distribution of remote-hybrid-on-site workers in each category.**

These distribution graphics are important because it highlights that the data is skewed towards the on-site workers (over 50%), which will also affect the following graphs' interpretations.

It is important to consider that the proportions of these new created three categories-based results may differ from the original population. We do not aim to compare with the original population and distributions.

The data was re-analysed accordingly, summarised mainly descriptively in terms of comparing remote work and hybrid work and workplace raw distributions.

The summary of the analytical statistics are presented under a separate title to evaluate potential differences between the groups on certain variables. Following the analysis of the chi-square results, some models were created for the final evaluation of the potential factors associations with work location groups by Logistic Regression analysis. Technical explanations of the analytical findings and the codebook for the logistic regression analysis are provided in Appendix A.3.4. Details of the logistic models can be found in Appendix 4

⁶<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/surveys/european-working-conditions-surveys/ewcts-2021/ewcts-2021-questionnaire>

⁷<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/surveys/european-working-conditions-surveys/ewcts-2021/ewcts-2021-methodology>

Calculation details:

Re-coding 'work location' information and key points

To assess the location of work, the 'loc_work' variable was adjusted according to the remote- hybrid and workplace definitions and created the 'loc_work_adjusted' variable. The loc_work variable consists of 8 options: 'client', 'emp_prem – own business', 'from emp_prem - own business and other', 'from emp_prem - own business AND home', 'home', 'other loc combinations', 'vehicle', 'working from home and somewhere else'. As stated, due to the aim of the analysis to examine the remote-hybrid-workplace/workplace framework and its potential effects on several variables, we excluded the 'client' and 'vehicle' options.

- The 'workplace/office/on-site' variable was constructed through the aggregation of the 3 variables, namely 'emp_prem – own business', 'from emp_prem - own business and other', and 'other loc combinations'.
- The 'hybrid' variable was assigned only to the 'from emp_prem - own business AND home' option.
- The 'remote' variable was constructed through the aggregation of the 'home' and 'working from home and somewhere else' options. At the end of the process, the 'loc_work_adjusted' variable contains three types of working locations remote, hybrid and workplace.
- The visual graphs are created by using loc_work_adjusted, which is the aggregated version, instead of using the 'loc_work' variable consisting of 8 options in the original data.
- The distribution in the graph demonstrates the **number** and **percentage** of these three working types in the loc_work_adjusted variable (defined work location).
- Other categoric variables were used as previously calculated versions in the given dataset (Eurofound Methodology 2021). WHO-5 well-being scores are calculated based on the definition provided by the transformation of the 0-100 scale (WHO, 1998; Eurofound, 2023).

Health outcome	Information Variable categories were used from the data received. No recalculation was performed.	Related Q /data, Recoding based on exist versions
Physical Burnout	Physical Burnout level	Q29g, Q29, Q30b, Q30c Variable categories were used from the data received.
Strain (High)	Yes/no	Q90d, Q90e calculated variable used
Depression Risk	Depression Risk (normal, at risk, clinical) calculated version used	M2B; calculated v. used from data
Anxiety	Anxiety level	Q78h; calculated v. used from data
Headache and eye strain	Self-reported experience (yes/no)	M2b/Q78f; calculated v. used from data
Upper body muscle pain	Self-reported experience (yes/no)	Calculated v. used from data
Back pain	Self-reported experience (yes/no)	Calculated v. used from data
Presenteeism	Experience last year (yes/no)	Core/Q84a; calculated v. used from data
Mental health and wellbeing WHO-5	Cheerful and in good sprit, calm and relaxed, active and vigorous, fresh and rested, daily life filled that things interest (categorical calculated variable used in the data)	Core; Q87a, Q87b, Q87c (Score recalculated by using categorical data received; according to the definition)
Wellbeing worry	Self-reported frequency level, Likert	Calculated v. used from data received
Wellbeing tiredness	Self-reported level, Likert type	Calculated v. used from data received
Wellbeing concentrations	Self-reported level, Likert type	Calculated v. used from data received

Table 4: Information for health and well-being related variables

2.3.4 WHO-5 Score

The index consists of five self-reported statements assessing a person's feelings over the past two weeks. The responses use a Likert scale with 6 response options scored from 0 to 5, where higher scores indicate better well-being. The raw total scores range from 0 to 25, with 0 representing the worst possible quality of life and 25 representing the best. To convert the raw score to a standardised percentage (ranging from 0 to 100), the

raw score is multiplied by 4. A standardised score of 0 indicates the worst possible quality of life, while a score of 100 indicates the best possible quality of life (Topp, 2015).

2.4 Literature Search Strategy and Selection Process Overview

The search strategy was based on defined keywords from the deliverable title and involved a systematic search of scientific literature, interdisciplinary sources, and grey literature reports.

This approach was used to explore and present the literature in detail, first to understand the general distributions and main themes in the literature to define RWAs related trends, and nested search for specific subheadings for exploratory narrative reviews. The report's aim is to provide an exploratory mixed research-based summary of the results and produce a research-based insight into the related RMAP work packages.

2.4.1 Topic Modelling and BERTopic search

Sources of information:

- SCOPUS® (Interdisciplinary): SCOPUS® (Interdisciplinary) scientific data was searched to establish the related literature on RWAs. The analysis related to RQ1 was conducted using this data (see Figure 2 and 5 for LDA and BERTopic Flow diagrams, respectively and Appendix 2, A.2.1 for search query).

Strategy:

The methodology includes a combination of Topic Modelling (with LDA, included expert opinion), machine learning and deep learning concepts. BERTopic is a method used in artificial intelligence (AI) and specifically in the field of natural language processing (NLP) to get an overview of the interdisciplinary literature. Topic modelling is an approach to studying research clusters to gain insight into future directions. For clustering, topic modelling is one of the machine learning techniques using unstructured data with LDA, which is a widely used technique for automatically discovering topics from large collections. In this part of the report, a systematic literature search was evaluated using topic modelling from the interdisciplinary literature database SCOPUS® (George and Sumathy, 2023).

This part of the research provides a comprehensive picture on working and living conditions, including health and well-being, by combining a search strategy defined for this report (Appendix 2, A.2.1). To explore the

current interdisciplinary literature, topic modelling (Figure 2) was used to discover latent themes after collecting document titles, abstracts and keywords (Gerlach et. Al., 2018).

This comprehensive literature search on Scopus yielded 14,060 interdisciplinary scientific published journal papers in the initial search. To delineate clusters for remote-related interdisciplinary literature this approach was refined by thematic coding of the clusters by investigating hierarchical clusters by the authors after initial evaluation multiple times to find the best coherence.

Figure 2: Flow diagram of the LDA Topic Modelling Process

Keywords defined in the search strategy from the retrieved data were repeatedly searched in the SCOPUS® database between March and June 2024 (Appendix2, A.2.1). The third model used a total of 7.975 data points obtained via the search. During the data pre-processing phase, 117 records with the phrase "[No abstract available]" in the Abstract column and 35 repetitive records in the 'Title and Abstract' columns were removed. This left us with a total of 7.823 records. The main authors of this report ranked the topics (blindly in relation to the RMAP D1.3 objectives) and the topic names with the highest coefficient of coherence from the combination of the keywords were created (Figure 3). Global distribution of the topics can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Topic Modelling Coherence values of the number of topics

Figure 4: Country origin of publications in Scopus (legend based on 7823 paper count)

In addition to topic modelling, we used a hybrid supervised model to understand the main picture and identified cluster topics in the scientific interdisciplinary literature. Recent studies have shown the feasibility of treating topic modelling as a clustering task by extending the process with BERTopic, which generates documents embedded with pre-trained transformer-based language models. Some studies have suggested that LDA-based topic modelling may provide better information when combined with different models, such as Bi-directional Encoder Representations of Transformers (BERT) and supervised approaches (Grootendorst, 2022).

For selected hierarchical clusters in Topic Modelling, the most frequently identified keywords are listed and human-curated into new categories to combine and apply the BERTopic analysis. The content experts evaluated the topics with the most coherence, and the remote work-related thematic names were created from coefficients of keywords. Considering the paper distribution of the 14 topic clusters identified for 7,823 articles examined within the scope of the relevant search query (Appendix 2, A.2.1) in the Scopus database.

Figure 5: Flow diagram of the BERTopic Modelling Road MAP

Following the LDA Topic Modelling analyses, it was considered appropriate to perform a BERTopic Modelling analysis to better define the focus of the research area. To this end, the authors evaluated all versions of the 14 identified topics, to restructure the hierarchical cluster, based on the word's topics of 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13 and 14 in LDA Topic Modelling (details in Appendix 2, Supplementary Figure 2). Then these were filtered and used as a new dataset input for BERTopic Topic Modelling (Figure 5). According to the results of BERTopic Topic Modelling (4862 papers assessed), 62 topics were initially identified. Later, topics that were close enough to each other were merged, leaving 15 topics without outliers.

All topics are named by using the first 10 keywords of their respective topic keywords. Once the topics are classified, the corresponding frequencies of thematic areas of the topic are displayed with a heat map and by year. For the similarity matrix and inter-topic distance map of identified topics, please see Appendix 2, Supplementary Figure 2 and Supplementary Figure 3.

Articles were downloaded and included in the review pool selection process. Articles focusing solely on the Covid-19 period were excluded.

2.4.2 Systematic Literature Search

Sources of information:

- SCOPUS® (Interdisciplinary): After conducting initial searches in SCOPUS using defined keywords, a search strategy was developed for each research question to narrow down the focus according to the relevant PECOs.
- PubMed (Health), Cochrane Library, Web of Science, Medline, PsycINFO: These databases were searched, and peer-reviewed research articles and reviews were included.

Strategy: The scientific peer-reviewed literature search started with identification of relevant keywords and synonyms of each category. The search considers synonyms to explore different combinations of questions and based on relevant search engines. Search results from SCOPUS (Interdisciplinary), PubMed (Health) and Cochrane Library, Web of Science, Medline, and PsycINFO were combined after the elimination of the duplicates. Then, a two-stage blind selection procedure was applied to retrieved items.

The selection process is conducted after the preliminary literature search, based on the (RQ 2-6) selected keywords listed below. Combination of the versions of keywords (remote work, working condition, living conditions combined with the (work-life balance and health and well-being) nested search applied regarding the specific outcome in the main pool with relevant keywords for exploratory narrative review. Loneliness separately searched. Environmental aspects separately searched. Keywords are presented in Table 5.

Keywords were categorised into groups related to RWAs. A list of synonyms for remote work and related search terms was used in the initial search process, and the keywords were repeated across various search engines to filter out irrelevant terms. The search strategy included the population 'all,' exposure 'remote work*,' and outcomes 'working and living conditions,' along with their synonyms, in alignment with the RMAP objectives. This process generated a large pool of publications, which was then used for nested searches with comparison and outcome options associated with subtitles in line with the D1.3 research questions. The search was narrowed down related to work-life balance, health and well-being as outcomes, and gender and caregiving responsibilities as comparators.

The primary focus was on peer-reviewed, open-access journals, with relevance to the topic and determined by consensus among at least two researchers. Due to the exploratory nature of the study, systematic reviews, theses, dissertations, and peer-reviewed conference proceedings were also included to enrich the context.

Flow diagrams are presented in Figure 6 and 7. The RMAP D1.3 framework was employed in the narrative review due to the exploratory and mixed focus of the main objectives. Given the interdisciplinary nature of the topic and the intersection of themes, articles relevant to all themes within the scope of the research questions, as well as those that were concept-based for contextual enrichment, were selected and utilised. The corresponding numbers are detailed in the relevant flow diagrams.

Papers that combined different data sources were transferred to the Covidence platform for the selection process. Following a blind evaluation by two authors and the reaching of a consensus, the documents were retrieved for extraction. With an exploratory focus, qualitative insights and main findings were extracted regarding by thematic relevance, methodology, as determined under the related research question with defined Population: All; Intervention/Exposure: RWAs; Comparisons: N/A; Gender, Caregiving responsibilities, urban/rural outcome: Work-life balance and Health and Well-being.

Information relevant to each research question (RQ) is summarised as subtitles in the literature review section. This summary integrates findings from both grey literature and contextual references.

RQ element	Selected keywords
1: Remote work* (relevant synonyms by technical search engines consulted during the initial search processes)	"Telework*" OR "Flexible Work*" OR "Hybrid Work*" OR "Remote* Work*" OR telecommut* OR "Virtual work*" OR "work* from home" OR "Remote employment" OR "Flexible work* arrangements" OR "Work* flexibility" OR "non* standard work*" OR "non* standard work* schedules" OR "home* office" OR "future of work" OR "distribut* work" OR "asynchronous work" OR "async* work" OR "return to office" OR "digital nomad*" OR "work* remot*" OR "remote job*" OR "work from anywhere" OR "work* online" OR "smart work" OR "distance work" OR "remote agile work" OR "E-work" OR "home* based work*" OR "virtual employment" OR "mobile work*" OR "online work*" OR "off* site work*" OR "asynchronous work" OR "cloud work*" OR "work*remote*"
2: Outcome*: Working Condition (included AND with remote work-related keywords)	"work* hours" OR "position" OR "job status" OR "Access to support" OR "job demand" OR "work* demands" OR "Work* Stress" OR "work* location" OR "Work* Condition" OR "work* environment" OR "commute to work" OR "social security" OR "Social insurance" OR "income security" OR "Job Security" OR "income" OR "Job Stability"

<p>2a: Organisational aspects* (Included AND with remote work-related keywords)</p>	<p>"Health Services" OR "Occupational Health and Safety" OR "Occupational Safety and Health" OR "Occupational health" OR "Employee Health" OR "Employee services" OR "Social Services" OR "Self* help" OR "wellness" OR "social support" OR "food service*" OR "Health Services" OR "Occupational Health and Safety" OR "Occupational Safety and health" OR "Turnover" OR "Work* life interface" OR "Opportunity for growth" OR "Autonomous work" OR "Opportunity" OR "Administrative justice" OR "Organizational justice" OR "Employee participation" OR "Engagement" OR "Commitment" OR "Satisfaction" OR "Quality of work* life"</p>
<p>3: Living Condition*(combined with previous boxes as one of outcome)</p>	<p>"Living condition*"OR "Resident* Selection" OR "home arrangement*" OR "Social Condition "OR "accommodation preference" OR "Resident* preference "OR "Resident* Characteristic*"OR "living arrangement*"OR "residential mobility" OR "infrastructure" OR "workspace at 4home"OR"leisure space"</p>
<p>3a: Location*(combined with as a comparator)</p>	<p>OR "Rural" OR "urban" OR "rural* urban difference*"</p>
<p>4: Health and well-being, Work-life balance*(combined with as an outcome)</p>	<p>Burn*out" OR stress OR "Job "accident" OR "Life* Work* Imbalance" OR " OR "Sleep" OR "ergonomic*" OR "Wellbeing" OR "Well-Being" OR "Happiness" OR "Sick Leave" OR "Sick-Leave" OR "Absenteeism" OR "Work* Life Balance" OR "Work* Life Conflict" OR "Work* Family Balance" OR "Vacation" OR "Quality of Life" OR "Life Quality"</p>
<p>4a: Gender & caregiving responsibilities*(combined with as a comparator)</p>	<p>"Social gender" OR "Gender role*" OR "Disability" OR "Parenting status" OR "Marital Status" OR "Care responsibilities" OR "Dependents"</p>
<p>Loneliness (separate search for loneliness)</p>	<p>(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Loneliness" AND "Telework*" OR "Flexible Work*" OR "Hybrid Work*" OR "Remote* Work*" OR telecommut* OR "Virtual work*" OR "work* from home" OR "Remote employment" OR "Flexible work* arrangements" OR "Work* flexibility" OR "non* standard work*" OR "non* standard work* schedules" OR "home* office" OR "future of work" OR "distribut* work" OR "asynchronous work" OR "async* work" OR "return to office" OR "digital nomad*" OR "work* remot*" OR "remote job*" OR "work from anywhere" OR "work* online" OR "smart work" OR "distance work" OR "remote agile work" OR "E-work" OR "home* based work*" OR "virtual employment" OR "mobile work*" OR "online work*" OR "off* site work*" OR "asynchronous work" OR "cloud work*" OR "work*remote*")) AND (intervention AND stud* OR experiment* OR quasi*) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD , "COVID-19"))</p>
<p>Environmental health (separate search for environmental and public health)</p>	<p>"Remote work" AND ("environmental health" OR "planetary health" OR "environmental impact" OR "ecological impact")</p>

PI/ECO* P: Workers; I/E: RWAs, C - O: alternate depending on the RQ exploratively

Table 5: Systematic Search keywords list⁸

⁸ This list used with different combinations according to PE(I)CO in systematic search, the information given in this report includes exploratory review for each. A separate systematic review process will be prepared for publication during the project period

Figure 6: Flow diagram of literature selection process for RWAs and working and living conditions and work-life balance and health and well-being related outcomes through gender lens

Figure 7: Flow diagram⁹ of RWAs and Loneliness related interdisciplinary literature search and selection process

⁹ Page et.al.,2021)

2.4.3 Grey Literature

Sources of information: Grey literature was identified through librarian records, including websites, open-access reports, theses, and search results. The identification and elimination processes are summarised in the flow diagram (ProQuest, OAlster, SSRN, WHO-IRIS, European data retrieved) (Figure 8). Additionally, institutional reports and policy documents were considered and topic focused selected valid electronic documents included from [Eurofound](#), [EU-OSHA](#), [ILO](#), [WHO](#), [OECD](#)

Figure 8: Flow diagram of grey literature selection process

Institutional reports were used to extract definitions, terminology, and relevant information across various chapters of this report, aiming to foster a shared understanding of working and living conditions. The methodologies of these reports were carefully examined to identify key definitions and variables, with a particular focus on the background, introduction, and aspects of working and living conditions within the conceptual framework of RWAs.

A notable effort for ensuring consistency in terminology, through collaborative efforts, has been observed across reports from the ILO, OECD, EU-OSHA, and Eurofound. These insights informed the terminology section of the introduction, based on the summaries derived from these evaluations.

Further analysis was conducted to extract information related to RWAs and to highlight key aspects of future research. Reports from Eurofound, EU-OSHA, OECD, and others were reviewed (Table 6); key terminology and content are cited when appropriate. A summary of this information is presented in the following tables.

The institutional reports	Reference
<p>Eurofound: A new round of the European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS) using computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI). This approach allowed for the collection of data on working conditions across Europe during the pandemic, covering topics such as employment status, working hours, job security, and work-life balance. For the first time, the respondents were contacted via computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI). The survey methodology¹⁰ and the questionnaire¹¹ used in the EWCS 2021 can be found in Eurofound EWCTS 2021 Methodology (Eurofound, EWCTS 2021 Questionnaire; Eurofound, EWCTS 2021 Methodology; Eurofound. European Working Conditions Telephone Survey, 2021).</p>	<p>(Eurofound EWCTS 2021)</p>

¹⁰ The detailed methodology of the survey: <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/surveys/european-working-conditions-surveys/ewcts-2021/ewcts-2021-methodology>

¹¹ **The questionnaire of the EWCS 2021: <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/surveys/european-working-conditions-surveys/ewcts-2021/ewcts-2021-questionnaire>

<p>OECD: The OECD 2021 report titled "The Future of Remote Work: Opportunities and Policy Options for Trentino" explores the potential impacts of teleworking on individuals, locations, and businesses. It discusses the benefits and challenges associated with remote work, such as increased flexibility, productivity, and potential disparities in access to remote work opportunities. The report provides policy recommendations to leverage the advantages of remote work while addressing its challenges, particularly in the context of the Trentino region. Here link.</p>	<p>(OECD, 2021)</p>
<p>EU OSHA: The report on hybrid work addresses new opportunities and challenges in occupational safety and health (OSH). It highlights how the shift to hybrid work models, combining remote and on-site work, has created both benefits and risks for workers' health and safety. The report emphasises the importance of adapting OSH policies and practices to ensure worker well-being in hybrid work environments, considering factors like ergonomic setups, mental health support, and clear communication protocols.</p>	<p>(EU-OSHA, 2023a)</p>

Table 6: The three key institutional reports regarding RWAs used in the analysis

Reports searched to summarise the key aspects on working and living conditions, related terminology and their methodological approaches were summarised in the Table 7-8.

Institution/Report name/ Release date	Methodology	Key aspects on 1-Working and living condition 2-Work-life balance and Health and wellbeing
<p>Eurofound</p> <p>The changing structure of employment in the EU: Annual review 2023 (Eurofound, 2024) 23 November 2023</p>	<p>Quantitative Analysis of employment patterns using statistical data and surveys</p>	<p>1-Examines the evolving employment patterns, highlighting the impact on job quality, working conditions, and living conditions such as income levels, job security, and quality of life. 2-Analyzes employment trends and their indirect impact on work-life balance and overall well-being, including flexible working arrangements, job security, economic stability, and job satisfaction.</p>

<p>Psycho-social risks to workers' well-being: Lessons from the Covid-19 pandemic (Eurofound, 2023b) 23 November 2023)</p>	<p>Mixed-methods, Surveys and case studies examining the impact of the Covid-19 on mental health and work-life balance</p>	<p>1-Focuses on the psycho-social risks faced by workers during the Covid-19 pandemic, emphasizing mental health and working conditions, indirectly affecting living conditions through stress.</p> <p>2-Highlights the impact of the Covid-19 on work-life balance, focusing on increased stress and the need for better work-life integration, and emphasises the psycho-social risks to mental health and well-being.</p>
<p>Gender Equality at Work (Eurofound, 2020a) 3 March 2020</p>	<p>Quantitative Gender-based analysis using workplace surveys and economic data</p>	<p>1-Focuses on gender disparities in the workplace, focusing on working conditions, equal opportunities, and pay equity, and how these disparities affect living conditions, including income inequality</p> <p>2-Discusses gender disparities in work-life balance, highlighting the challenges faced by women in balancing work and family responsibilities, and addresses the impact of gender inequality on health and well-being, including stress and work-related health issues.</p>
<p>Working conditions and sustainable work: An analysis using the job quality framework (Eurofound, 2021b) 26 February 2021</p>	<p>Quantitative, Job quality framework analysis using survey data and job performance metrics</p>	<p>1-Investigate working conditions through the job quality framework, identifying key aspects that contribute to sustainable work environments and their implications for long-term living conditions. emphasizing the importance of job quality and flexibility.</p> <p>2-Analyzes the role of work-life balance in sustainable work environments and discusses the relationship between sustainable work practices and overall well-being, including job satisfaction and health.</p>
<p>Working conditions in the time of Covid-19: Implications for the future (Eurofound, 2022) 29 November 2022, Updated 8 December 2022</p>	<p>Mixed Methods Case studies and surveys on the impact of the Covid-19 on working conditions</p>	<p>1-Explore how the Covid-19 has affected working conditions, discussing remote work, job security, and health and safety concerns, with implications for living conditions such as economic stability and work-life integration.</p> <p>2-Examines the impact of the Covid-19 on work-life balance, including the challenges of remote work and maintaining boundaries between work and personal life, and explores how Covid-19 has affected health and well-being, including physical and mental health challenges faced by workers.</p>

Table 7: Potential key aspects regarding working conditions, work-life balance and health and well-being in related Eurofound reports

Institution/release date	method	Key aspects 1-Working and living conditions 2-Work-life balance and health and wellbeing
OECD: Teleworking through the gender looking glass: Facts and gaps (Touzet, C., 2023) (13 February 2023)	Quantitative Comparative analysis of teleworking impacts using survey data and gender studies	1-Investigates the gender-specific impacts of teleworking on satisfaction and gender gap in teleworking opportunities and access. 2-Investigates the gender specific impacts of teleworking, focusing on how these differences, affects household dynamics and time management, and explores how teleworking influences health and well-being, particularly in terms of stress, mental health, and the ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance.
The future of remote work: Opportunities and policy options for Trentino (OECD, 2021) (2021/07)	Qualitative, Policy analysis and surveys on remote work practices and impacts	1-Discusses the future potential and policy considerations for remote work, including its impact on working conditions, flexibility, commute time, and job satisfaction, and living conditions such as geographic mobility, associated factors with work-life balance, and community dynamics. 2-Explore the potential of remote work to improve work-life balance and examines the health and well-being benefits of remote work, such as reduced stress from commuting and the ability to create a more comfortable working environment.
Safe and healthy working environments for all, Hybrid Work: New Opportunities and Challenges for Occupational Safety and Health (ILO, 2023; EU-OSHA, 2023a)	Includes comprehensive review existing literature, surveys, and data analysis on hybrid work	1- Discusses the future potential and challenges of remote work, focusing on work intensity, ergonomic risks, impact on working conditions, job satisfaction, and geographic mobility. 2 - Explores the benefits of remote work for work-life balance and health, including reduced commuting stress and improved mental well-being.

Table 8: RWAs related OECD, ILO, EU-OSHA reports with information on working conditions, work-life balance and health and well-being

These reports explored the potential associations between variables to develop an understanding on the context and its terminology. Four main report-based variables and related information are listed in Tables 9-12. The report “Impact of teleworking on workers’ health and well-being: a survey study” by EU-OSHA (EU-

OSHA, 2024a) investigates variables related to physical and mental health, work-life balance, productivity, and occupational safety issues. The results are listed in subsections of the literature review.

Investigated Variables	Definitions	Investigated Measures
Mental health and Well-being	The state of mental health, including aspects	Mental well-being scores from mental Well-being Surveys (e.g., WHO-5 Well-Being Index) self-reported stress, anxiety, and isolation
Work-life balance	Based on time management and boundary settings between work and personal life, and the impact on family and social life	Wellbeing scores, the ability of balance professional responsibilities with personal life
Physical health and wellbeing. Workspace Ergonomics	The design and arrangement of the workspace to fit the worker's needs, preventing discomfort or injury.	Evaluation of workspace ergonomics, workspace assessments surveys, discomfort back pain, MS complaints
Occupational health and safety	Associated exposure, hazards and risks in TWAs	Evaluation of workstation setup, adherence safety protocols, risk assessment explores new safety risks in home working environments, ergonomic practice safety guidelines.

Table 9: Key definition of concepts related to RWAs: Impact of teleworking on workers' health and well-being (EU-OSHA, 2024a)

Investigated Variables	Definitions	Approach, measures
Employment Patterns	Trends and changes in job types, sectors, and employment status within the EU.	Employment shifts by sector and occupation, Labor Force Surveys, Employment Records
Job Quality	Various aspects that determine the overall quality of jobs, including pay, security, and working conditions.	Job satisfaction, job security, working conditions Job Satisfaction Surveys (e.g., Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) by Spector)
Remote Work	The practice of working from a location other than the traditional office, such as home.	Percentage of employees teleworking, changes in remote work rates, Surveys, Employment Records

Working Conditions	The conditions under which work is performed, including hours, safety, and physical environment.	Working hours, safety measures, physical work conditions, Working Conditions Surveys (e.g., EWCS)
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Table 10: Key definition of variables related concepts from ‘The changing structure of employment in the EU.: Annual review 2023’ (Eurofound, 2024)

The Annual Review Report 2023 provides a comprehensive analysis of how employment structures evolved in the EU, focusing specifically on the period from 2008 to 2023 (Eurofound, 2024). It includes key points related to remote working arrangements. This report highlights the fast recovery of employment levels in EU27 countries after the pandemic under the influence of remote working arrangements (RWAs). The report addresses demographic changes affecting the labour supply and the flexibility provided by RWAs for inclusiveness. Other key focus areas are the occupational shift, growth of the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) sector, and the increase in high-skilled jobs under RWAs. The facilitation of RWAs allows for the participation of a diverse labour force from various locations. The report provides insights about RWAs gender employment patterns, denoting an increase in the share of women employed in remote work-friendly occupations. It specifically examines how remote work has influenced job quality, highlighting trade-offs between the positive aspects (e.g. flexibility and reduced commuting) and the potential negatives (e.g. isolation and overworking).

Term	Definitions	Investigated Measures
Job Quality Framework	A structured approach to evaluating job quality based on multiple dimensions such as income, job security, and work environment.	Income, job security, work environment quality Job quality indicators, job satisfaction by surveys
Sustainable Work	Work that provides long-term social, economic, and environmental benefits.	Longevity of job roles, economic stability, environmental impact surveys, sustainability assessments

Table 11: Key definition of concepts from the report ‘Working conditions and sustainable work: An analysis using the job quality framework’ (Eurofound, 2021b)

The job quality framework based on the ‘Working Conditions and Sustainable Work: an analysis using the job quality framework’ report (Eurofound, 2021b) analyses job quality (Table 11). Explored dimensions include the

physical environment (including exposure to hazards, ergonomic conditions and the physical demands of the job); measures of the work intensity dimension, work pace, pressure to meet tight deadlines and the mental demands of the job; skills and discretion. The analysis includes the level of skills required for the job and opportunities to improve skills, including autonomy in the role. Social environment focuses on important relationships at play, including support from colleagues and supervisors and exposure to adverse social behaviours. Work-life balance as an outcome but under the job quality indicators assesses the compatibility of work demands with personal life, including working hours, flexibility and the ability to balance work with other responsibilities.

Job prospects investigate the opportunities for career advancements, job security and the potential for income growth in this report. Earning accepted as a dimension measure for the adequacy and fairness of earnings including pay levels related to the cost of living and perceptions of pay equity. The report highlights current trends and changes in these dimensions, including references to RWAs on the report measures by comparing different occupational categories.

The report, entitled '**Lessons from the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic**' and published by **Eurofound (Eurofound, 2023b)**, draws upon data from the European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS) conducted in 2021. The report presents an analysis based on a theoretical model of job stressors (e.g. high work intensity, adverse social behaviour) and job resources (e.g. social support, job autonomy) with the objective of assessing the prevalence and impact of psycho-social risks. Additionally, there has been an increase in the number of reports related to adverse social behaviour, discrimination and high work intensity, particularly among remote workers. It has been stated that significant challenges in balancing work and personal life, which has led to negative impacts on health and well-being.

This report covers a range of sectors and occupations and highlights significant variations in experience and outcome among remote workers. The report identifies four challenges pertaining to the job quality of remote workers, as indicated by the following job quality indicators: **In terms of work intensity**, remote workers reported higher levels of intensity, with longer hours and higher demands. With respect to **work-life balance**, difficulties were reported in maintaining this dependency on the family caregiving responsibilities and individual needs, with **blurry boundaries** between work and personal life. A **lack of sufficient support communication** process and information flow, coupled with a reduction in face-to-face interaction, has led to an increase in perceived isolation and the emergence of adverse social behaviours. The **remote working**

environment is identified as a potential source of stress and degradation of mental health, including exposure to adverse behaviours and an overall decrease in well-being. The findings indicate that **while remote work offers some flexibility, it also brings significant challenges for the job quality, work intensity, work-life balance, and mental health, leading to decreased levels of employee job satisfaction, motivation, engagement and productivity.** It is important to address these issues by providing a robust support system and policies tailored for specific work – job environments and their content. Mitigation strategies should be based on the requirements of policies, improvements to job resources, support for work-life balance and the assurance of a safe and supportive work environment (Table 12).

Investigated Variables	Definitions	Investigated Measures
Psycho-social Risks	Factors in the work environment that may affect workers' mental health, such as stress, anxiety, and depression.	Frequency of the psycho-social risks related variables and associations particularly coincidence of teleworking and work -life interference worsens mental well-being (stress, anxiety, depression among workers Self-reported Surveys,
Mental Health	The state of psychological well-being and the absence of mental illness.	Measures of psychological well-being and mental health status Surveys (WHO-5)
Work Environment	The setting and conditions in which work is performed, including physical and social aspects.	Evaluation of physical and social work conditions questionnaire based on work environment

Table 12: Key definition of concepts related aspects in the report 'Psycho-social risks to workers' well-being: Lessons from the Covid-19 pandemic' (Eurofound, 2023b)

We evaluate another report to account for the definitions and variables related to 'gender equality in working life by Eurofound' (Table 13). The report is based on the EWCS data and uses other studies to analyse gender disparities using related terminology. It focuses on the Covid-19 period based on RWAs, and particularly the job quality and psycho-social factors. The report indicates that women were slightly more likely to work remotely when compared to men. Remote work increased the work intensity in both men and women, 5% more in women compared to men. Similarly, women reported more significant challenges due to additional household responsibilities and higher stress levels related to work-life balance with childcare. Slightly different levels of support (5%), higher levels of isolation, and mental health issues were reported and more so among

women. (e.g. Persistent gender pay gap indicated, women receive 14% less than men, greater pay disparities in male-dominated sectors, work-life balance related challenges mentioned for both genders).

Investigated Variables	Definitions	Investigated Measures	Findings in General (not focused on RWAs)
Gender Disparities	Differences in treatment or outcomes between genders in the workplace, such as pay gap and career progression.	Gender pay gap, career progression rates	persistent gender pay gap indicated, 14% less than men, greater pay disparities in male-dominated sectors
Work-Life Balance	The equilibrium between personal life and work responsibilities.	Work hours, personal time, flexibility work-life balance scale	Work-Life Balance Scales, Surveys
Equal Opportunities	Fair access to resources and opportunities regardless of gender.	Access to promotions, training, resources pay equity, career advancements, access to training and developments,	Underrepresented in senior roles 33% managerial positions, 5% less access to training and opportunities

Table 13: Key definition of concepts in the report 'Gender Equality at Work' (Eurofound, 2020a)

3. RESULTS OF THE EWCTS DATA RE-ANALYSIS

This section provides a micro-data overview of working location related distributions listed under the Research objectives as well as corresponding RQ2-6 by using relevant data EWCTS-2021.

Under this section, re-analysis aims to explore the potential effect of remote working arrangements in the received data. To achieve this, the descriptives and potential associations explored within the dataset by a cross-sectional survey design. This analysis is based on existing variables and newly created ones by using the existing categorical variables. **Technical explanations and detailed descriptive and analytical results from the reanalysis of the data can be found in the Appendix 3.**

The results are provided as a summary regarding the D1.3 objectives, an additional summary of distributions regarding gender give insight to understand RQ6.

The results of this report are not suitable for comparison with the original population. The data analysis in this report does not represent original population as detailed in the methodology reanalysis section.

In the first section Findings given which include the subtitles on location (urban-rural) and socio-demographics (gender, education, age); household information related doing housework and caregiving responsibilities (RQ-6).

Second section summarises working life variables give insights on the research questions RQ2-4 by picturing the general characteristics of the working life variables, and job quality indicators.

Third and fourth sections provide a picture on self-reported well-being and health related outcomes mental health of the individuals align with the research objectives.

Summary of the analytical results includes comparisons and some univariate associations as a snapshot of data analysis without detailed adjustments. These analyses **do not allow causal interpretation/consideration of endogeneity but give us an idea for associations for potential emphasis on certain conditions.**

3.1 SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS RELATING TO WORK LOCATION

This section provides an overview, summarising the findings related to the research objectives of D1.3, including the main characteristics of working and living conditions, a descriptive picture of job quality indicators, work-life balance variable results, and WHO-5 well-being and health outcomes. **Detailed descriptive and analytical results from the re-analysis of the data can be found in Appendix 3.**

The graphs in this section illustrate the distribution of each work location within the respective categories. It is important to note that these graphs do not represent the total distribution of each category; rather, they show the distribution of remote, hybrid, and on-site workers within each category.

At the end of this section, **a summary of the multivariate analysis is provided alongside the univariate analysis.**

Figure 9: Distribution of work locations in total

As seen in Figure 9, workers are mainly **working on-site (58.0%)**, 42% remote and hybrid (21.6% remote, and 20.4% hybrid) work locations. Figure 10 shows the remote work location density, according to the country of origin.

Figure 10: Remote work density according to the country of origin in Europe

As in the previous case, data and graphics do **not represent each country's total number of observations**. Instead, they demonstrate the **distribution of the working location within each country**. Consequently, Kosovo, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Albania, Serbia, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Slovenia and Cyprus have over 70% on-site workers. Kosovo is the leading country for on-site working location with a percentage of 89.3%, whereas the U.K. has the lowest ratio for on-site work location with a percentage of 37.8%. Countries like the U.K., Norway, Sweden, Ireland, Netherlands, and Finland have more than 50% of their working locations moved to hybrid or remote. The United Kingdom has the highest percentage of remote workers (44.9%), while Kosovo has the lowest (3.3%) (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 4).

3.1.1 Demographic characteristics

The work distribution shows that on-site work is the predominant mode of working in most countries, for both men and women (Figure 11). Norway, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom employ significant portions of remote and hybrid workers, for both genders (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 5). Kosovo, Bosnia & Herzegovina and Albania on the other hand employ high percentages of on-site workers, with minimal remote and hybrid workers. Most of the other countries show a balanced distribution of remote, hybrid, and on-site work, for both genders.

Figure 11: Distribution of working location by gender

22.1% of all females work remotely, 21% work in a hybrid setting, and 56.9% work in an on-site setting. On the other hand, 21.1% of all males work remotely, 19.9% work in a hybrid model, and 59% work on an on-site. This suggests a slightly higher frequency of remote and hybrid work locations for females, and a higher frequency of working on-site for males.

Gender and age group distributions according to work location are shown in Appendix Supplementary Table 1. Workplace/on-site work has highest percentage among the 16–24-year age group, followed by the 45+ and 25-34 age groups, respectively in this population.

Gender and age show significant associations between remote and workplace work when the hybrid category is included in remote work. There was no significant association between remote and hybrid work for gender.

Remote and hybrid workers tend to have higher education levels, with 67.1% of them holding tertiary education degrees, compared to 54.4% of on-site workers (Figure 12). There was a significant difference in educational levels of workers based on their work locations. Please see age distribution in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Distribution of working location by level of education

Figure 13: Distribution of working location by age groups

In rural areas, 16.9% of employees are working remotely, 12.8% are working hybrid, and the majority of 70.5% are working on-site. Meanwhile, 16.1% of employees are working remotely in urban areas, 14.3% are working hybrid, and the remaining 69.6% are on-site (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Work locations according to residence

For urbanity, no significant associations are observed for both workplace -remote and remote-hybrid comparisons (Appendix Supplementary Table 2). Among individuals in urban areas, 16.1% work remotely, 69.6% work in the workplace, and 14.3% work in a hybrid model. For those in rural areas, 16.9% work remotely, 70.5% work in the workplace, and 12.6% work in a hybrid model. The total sample consists of 71.8% from urban areas and 28.2% from rural areas. **Household size shows a significant association between remote and workplace work.**

Household Size:

The data indicates that as household size increases, there is a general trend towards a higher proportion of on-site work and a lower proportion of remote work. Hybrid work remains relatively consistent across different household sizes. **Working remote and hybrid combined was significantly different among households with one person (43%) and two persons (45.2%) and lowest among households with 6+ persons (28.7%).**

Conclusion: Housework results

Time Spent on Childcare: Significant associations are found between remote and workplace working and between remote and hybrid working across different frequencies of childcare involvement.

Time Spent on Caregiving for Relatives: Significant associations are observed between remote and workplace working and between remote and hybrid working across different frequencies of caregiving for relatives.

Time Spent on Housework: Significant associations are noted between remote and workplace working, and between remote and hybrid working across different frequencies of housework involvement.

People who had daily (23.9%) or several times a week (20.7%) housework duties had higher ratios for working remotely compared to hybrid.

Time Spent on Childcare:

For individuals who provide daily childcare, 20.7% work remotely, 57.6% work in the workplace, and 21.7% work in a hybrid model (Appendix Table 16). The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

As presented the details of the findings related to housework and caregiving responsibilities can be found in Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 7-9. Among men, daily housework is more common in remote workers (26.6%) compared to on-site workers (17.9%). These findings suggest that remote work may be associated with a higher likelihood of daily housework engagement, while on-site work is more often linked to a lack of participation in housework duties.

3.1.2 Work life characteristics

Self-employed individuals have a higher proportion of remote (25.5%) and hybrid work (24.3%) compared to employees (21% and 19.9% respectively). Employees predominantly work on-site (59.1%) (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Distribution of work location according to employment type

When it comes to sector type, the not-for-profit sector or NGOs has the highest proportion of remote workers (31.1%), and hybrid work (24.2%) combined. The public sector has the highest percentage of on-site workers (58.4%) with relatively low remote work (17.1%). A balanced distribution can be seen in the private sector with 23.2% remote, 18.6% hybrid workers, and public-private organisations with 23.6% remote and 23.3% hybrid workers (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Distribution of work locations by sector

Figure 17: Distribution of work location according to part-time and full-time employment

Full-time workers are composed of those who are mostly on-site (57.3%), who are working remotely (21.8%) and in hybrid arrangements (21.1%), respectively. Similarly, Part-time workers predominantly work on-site (61.5%), while 21.3% of them work remotely and the remaining 17.3% work in hybrid settings (Figure 17).

Figure 18: Work location according to working hours

Working hours and work location are presented in Figure 18. The majority of on-site workers (63.7%) reported working 48 hours or more per week, while the largest proportion of remote or hybrid workers (58.2%) reported working between 35-40 hours per week.

As presented in Figure 19, among all employees who use a computer for work, 49.2% are on-site workers, 26.6% are working remotely, and the remaining 24.2% work in hybrid locations. For those who do not use a computer for work, the vast majority are on-site workers (91.1%), with very few working remotely (3.7%) or in hybrid locations (5.2%).

Figure 19: Distribution of working location by usage of computer

Comparative results on work-life characteristics

Significant associations are found between remote and on-site working (work location variable is workplace) and between remote and hybrid working across different levels of work experience.

Results underscore the importance of considering work-related variables such as the work experience, job sector, and income level when analysing remote working trends. Different job sector type and income levels exhibit distinct patterns of remote, workplace, and hybrid work, which are crucial for policymakers and organisations to understand and address effectively.

Work Experience (seniority): For individuals with less than one year of work experience, 15.0% work remotely, 68.0% work in the workplace, and 17.0% work in a hybrid model (Table 14). The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P = 0.003$).

Sector type: In the private sector, 23.2% work remotely, 58.2% in the workplace, and 18.6% in a hybrid model. In the public sector, 17.1% work remotely, 58.4% in the workplace, and 24.5% in a hybrid model.

The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Working from workplace was significantly more common among public (58.4%) and private (58.2%) sector workers, while it was lowest among workers in the not-for-profit sector, or NGOs (44.7%). Also, the private sector had the lowest ratio (18.6%) for hybrid work locations. The difference between hybrid and remote work arrangements were found to be statistically significant.

Sector type	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
The private sector	9711	23.2	24412	58.2	7809	18.6	41932	64	~0	
The public sector	3071	17.1	10483	58.4	4387	24.5	17941	27.4		
A joint private-public organisation	621	23.6	1397	53.1	613	23.3	2631	4		~0
The not-for-profit sector or NGOs	413	31.1	593	44.7	322	24.2	1328	2		
Other	410	24.2	951	56.1	333	19.7	1694	2.6		
Employment Type										
Employee	12125	21	34112	59.1	11468	19.9	57705	87.4	~0	0.852
Self-Employed	2118	25.5	4178	50.3	2017	24.3	8313	12.6		
Part Time/Full Time										
Part-time	2327	21.3	6719	61.5	1886	17.3	10932	16.6	~0	~0
Full-Time	11895	21.6	31499	57.3	11580	21.1	54974	83.4		
Seniority										
Less than a year	1439	18.4	5199	66.6	1174	15	7812	11.8	~0	
1 to 4 years	4870	23.3	12028	57.5	4011	19.2	20909	31.6		~0
5 to 9 years	2698	22.6	6708	56.2	2531	21.2	11937	18		
10 or more	5285	20.7	14430	56.6	5780	22.7	25495	38.5		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

Table 14: Working life characteristics according to the work location

Employment Type: Among employees, 21.0% work remotely, 59.1% work in the workplace, and 19.9% work in a hybrid model. Among self-employed individuals, 25.5% work remotely, 50.3% work in the workplace, and 24.3% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test shows a significant association between remote and workplace working (P ~0), but no significant association between remote and hybrid working (P = 0.852).

Part-Time/Full-Time Employment:

Among part-time workers, 21.3% work remotely, 61.5% work in the workplace, and 17.3% work in a hybrid model. Among full-time workers, 21.6% work remotely, 57.3% work in the workplace, and 21.1% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Sector type: Significant associations are found between remote and workplace working and between remote and hybrid working across different sectors.

Employment Type: Significant associations are observed between remote and workplace working but not between remote and hybrid working.

Part-Time/Full-Time Employment: Significant associations are noted between remote and workplace working, as well as between remote and hybrid working.

Seniority: Significant associations are found between remote and workplace working and between remote and hybrid working across different levels of seniority. People with experience of more than 5 years in senior positions had the lowest ratios (56.2% for 5-9 years and 56.6% for 10 or more years of seniority) for working from the workplace compared to remote and hybrid combined.

Part-time workers had significantly higher ratios for working from the workplace rather than remote and hybrid combined compared to full-time workers. In the off-site working context, full-time workers had significantly higher ratios for hybrid working rather than remote working compared to part-time workers.

Seniority: For those with less than a year of experience, 18.4% work remotely, 66.6% work in the workplace, and 15.0% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test shows significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Boss Gender:

Significant associations are observed between remote and workplace working, but not between remote and hybrid working, **based on the gender of the boss**. For individuals with a female boss, 21.6% work remotely, 58.2% work in the workplace(on-site), and 20.2% work in a hybrid model.

Computerized System Effects:

For individuals, whose work is influenced by computerised systems 27.8% largely work remotely, 49.0% work in the workplace, and 23.2% work in a hybrid model.

Significant associations are noted between remote and workplace working, and between remote and hybrid working, based on the extent to which computerised system.

Using Computer:

Significant associations are found between remote and workplace working and between remote and hybrid working for individuals who use a computer compared to those who do not. **For those who do not use a computer, 3.7% work remotely, 91.1% work in the workplace, and 5.2% work in a hybrid model**

3.1.2.1 Job Quality Indicators Descriptives

Categorical variables of job quality indicators (Eurofound, 2021b) are summarised descriptively based on the available categorical data. Related figures can be found in Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 15-16.

These job quality indicators were also included in the logistic regression model to evaluate their associations with work location and burn-out in two separate models. These are the components of physical work environment, work intensity, physical demands, skills and discretion, job tasks, organisational characteristics, working time quality arrangements, job prospects, social work environment and earnings. The results relating to work location by job quality indicators and gender are presented below:

Insecure Work: For **men** experiencing insecure work, **on-site** work is more common (63.9%), with hybrid work being the least common (17.9%). or **women** experiencing insecure work, **on-site** work is also predominant (61.2%), but the distribution between remote (16.9%) and hybrid (21.9%) work is more balanced (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 15).

Work Intensity: Men and women experiencing high work intensity show a similar distribution across work locations, with a slight increase in remote work for those experiencing high work intensity. Both genders have a higher proportion of on-site workers among those experiencing lower work intensity (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 15).

Physical Demand: Men and women facing physical demands are predominantly on-site workers, with a very low percentage in remote and hybrid locations. Men and women not facing physical demands have a more balanced distribution among remote, hybrid, and on-site work (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 15).

Social Discrimination: Men experiencing social discrimination have a higher percentage of on-site work (69.3%) compared to those who do not (57.8%). Women experiencing social discrimination have a higher percentage of on-site work (63.8%) compared to those who are not experiencing it (55.9%) (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 15).

Unsocial Working Time: Unsocial working times for both men and women have a higher percentage in remote and hybrid locations, compared to those with regular working times. On-site work is more prevalent among men and women with regular working times (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 15).

Autonomy: Men and women with autonomy in their work tend to have higher remote and hybrid work percentages compared to those without autonomy. A larger proportion of women with autonomy work remotely (25.8%) compared to men (24.2%) (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 16).

Flexible Working Time: Flexible working time is more common among men and women in remote and hybrid locations. Men with flexible working time have a significant proportion in remote work (27.3%) compared to those without (16.8%) (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 16).

Intrinsic Rewards: Men and women who have intrinsic rewards have a similar distribution across work locations, with a slight increase in remote work for both genders (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 16).

Self-Realisation: Men and women who experience self-realisation in their work have higher percentages of remote and hybrid work (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 16).

Social Support: Men and women in remote and hybrid locations report similar levels of social support compared to those in on-site work. The percentage of women who feel social support and work in hybrid settings (21.5%) is nearly identical to that of men (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 16).

Learning and Development: Individuals who reported positive learning and development opportunities are more likely to work in remote and hybrid locations compared to those without such opportunities. (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figures 16).

3.1.2.2 Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) Risks:

The reported OSH risks vary across work environments. On-site workers report a higher percentage of OSH risks (31.3%) compared to hybrid or remote workers (24.1%). Please see Figure 20 for distributions.

- A detailed breakdown shows that **remote workers** have the highest percentage (82.0%) of employees reporting no occupational risk, followed by office workers (68.7%) and hybrid workers (60.1%).
- Hybrid workers (39.9%) report more risks compared to office workers (31.3%) and remote workers (18.0%). These findings indicate that work location influences the prevalence of certain health outcomes and the perception of occupational risks, with remote work environments generally perceived as safer.

Figure 20: Occupational safety and health risk according to the work location

3.1.2.3 Work-Life Interface Analytical Results

As presented in Table 15, for individuals who work daily during their free time, 23.1% work remotely, 47.3% work in the workplace, and 29.6% work in a hybrid model. Of those who work several times a week during their free time, 27.9% work remotely, 43.1% work in the workplace, and 29.0% work in a hybrid model. For those who work several times a month during their free time, 26.6% work remotely, 47.1% work in the workplace, and 26.3% work in a hybrid model. For those who work several times a month during their free time, 26.6% work remotely, 47.1% work in the workplace, and 26.3% work in a hybrid model.

	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Ability to work in free time										
Daily	804	23.1	1646	47.3	1028	29.6	3478	5.3	0	~0
Several times a week	2497	27.9	3852	43.1	2587	29	8936	13.6		
Several times a month	3325	26.6	5899	47.1	3293	26.3	12517	19.1		
Less often	4691	23.9	10895	55.5	4027	20.5	19613	29.9		
Never	2800	13.4	15712	74.9	2461	11.7	20973	32		
Working during sickness (presenteeism)										
Yes	4921	25.5	9929	51.5	4437	23	19287	29.1	~0	0.012
No	8627	19.9	26276	60.7	8383	19.4	43286	65.4		
I was not sick	764	20.9	2184	59.9	700	19.2	3648	5.5		
Ability to take time off										
Very easy	6961	28.1	12589	50.9	5197	21	24747	37.8	~0	~0
Fairly easy	5654	21.3	15258	57.5	5620	21.2	26532	40.5		
Fairly difficult	1108	13.7	5370	66.3	1619	20	8097	12.4		
Very difficult	515	8.3	4635	75.1	1023	16.6	6173	9.4		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

Table 15: Ability free time scheduling according to the work location

The chi-square test shows significant associations between working during free time and remote & hybrid combined working and workplace working ($P = 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

People who had no or less often the ability to work in their free time had higher ratios (55.5% and 75.9% respectively) for working from the workplace compared to people with more availability to work in their free time.

Ease of Taking Time Off:

For individuals who find it easy to take time off, 28.1% work remotely, 50.9% work in the workplace, and 21.0% work in a hybrid model. Of those who find it easy to take time off, 21.3% work remotely, 57.5% work in the workplace, and 21.2% work in a hybrid model. For those who find it difficult to take time off, 13.7% work remotely, 66.3% work in the workplace, and 20.0% work in a hybrid model (Table 15). From those individuals who find it very difficult to take time off, 8.3% work remotely, 75.1% work in the workplace, and 16.6% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations, both between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Individuals who find **it easy to take time off are more likely to work remotely or in a hybrid model**, whereas those who find it difficult or very difficult to take time off are predominantly workplace-based, with significantly different for working remotely.

3.1.2.4 Work-life balance

Self- Reported Work-Life Balance

Regarding the work-life balance for men versus women, among men, those who report their work-life balance as 'not at all well' are predominantly on-site workers (68.4%), followed by hybrid (17.9%) and remote (13.7%) workers. Similarly, among women who report their work-life balance as 'not at all well,' 63.2% are on-site workers, with 24.5% in hybrid work and 12.3% in remote work. For both men and women, those reporting a

good work-life balance ('well' or 'very well') are more frequently found in remote or hybrid work locations, though a significant proportion still work on-site (Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 11)

Engagement

On-site workers have a higher level of 'high engagement' compared to remote or hybrid workers (58.3% vs. 41.7%) (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Work location according to the engagement level

Working with an Illness (Presenteeism) distributions:

Regarding presenteeism, among those who do not work during sickness, 60.7% work on-site, 19.9% remotely, and 19.4% in hybrid locations. Among those who work during sickness, a higher percentage work remotely (25.5%) and in hybrid locations (23%) combined, compared to those who do not work during sickness (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Distribution of work locations according to working during sickness (presenteeism)

People who said they did not work when they were sick were mostly working from the workplace (60.7%), indicating that **remote and hybrid work was associated with more presenteeism**. 48.5% of the people who worked when they were sick were working in remote or hybrid locations, compared to 39.3% of people who were not working when they were sick in the same locations.

Comparative results:

- For individuals who worked with an illness, 25.5% work remotely, 51.5% work in the workplace, and 23.0% work in a hybrid model (Table 15).
- Of those who did not work with an illness, 19.9% worked remotely, 60.7% worked in the workplace, and 19.4% worked in a hybrid model.
- For those who were not sick, 20.9% worked remotely, 59.9% worked in the workplace, and 19.2% worked in a hybrid model.
- The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working (P ~0) and between remote and hybrid working (P = 0.012).

Key points**Working with an Illness (Presenteeism):**

There are significant associations between remote and on-site working and between remote and hybrid working for those who have worked while ill compared with those who have not worked while ill or have not been ill in the last year. There was a gradual decrease in the proportion of presenteeism among on-site workers compared with hybrid and remote workers. .

Working during Free Time:

Significant associations are observed between remote and on-site working and between remote and hybrid working across different frequencies of working during free time. **Daily ability to work in free time was higher among hybrid workers than remote workers and on-site workers.**

Ease of Taking Time Off:

Significant associations are noted between remote and on-site working, and between remote and hybrid working, based on the ease of taking time off. Ease of taking time off difficulty trend was higher among hybrid workers than remote, highest among on-site workers.

These results highlight the varying impact of working conditions, such as working during free time, the ease of taking time off, and night work (Appendix 3, Supplementary Table 10) on the choice of working location. Understanding these factors is crucial for developing policies and strategies that address the **workforce's diverse needs.**

3.1.3 WHO-5 Well-being results (KPI)

The index consists of five self-reported statements about a person's feelings over the past two weeks, with the related findings summarised below. Additionally, index points were calculated as outlined in the reanalysis approach. Comparisons of the sub-items including 'feeling cheerful and in good spirits,' 'feeling calm and relaxed,' 'feeling active and vigorous,' 'waking up feeling fresh and rested' and 'finding daily life fulfilling' details are provided in Appendix A3.7

Here is a brief summary of descriptive findings for these subitems:

- Regarding WHO-5 Cheerfulness subitem, the percentage of those feeling cheerful most of the time was higher among on-site workers than hybrid or remote workers, and higher among hybrid workers than remote workers.
- Similarly, in terms of WHO-5 relaxation and activeness, the well-being of on-site workers appears to be better than that of remote or hybrid workers. For individuals who feel relaxed all the time, 14.8% work remotely, 70.8% work in the workplace, and 14.4% work in a hybrid model. For individuals who feel active all the time, 14.2% work remotely, 69.7% work in the workplace, and 16.1% work in a hybrid model.
- In the same way, regarding the WHO-5 items for feeling rested and finding work interesting, on-site workers reported a better sense of well-being. According to the results, for individuals who feel rested all the time, 15.6% work remotely, 68.5% work in the workplace, and 15.9% work in a hybrid model. Of those who find their work interesting all the time, 16.7% work remotely, 65.8% work on-site, and 17.5% work in a hybrid model.

WHO-5 Score

The total scores of the WHO-well-being index differed between workplace (office) and remote work locations (including hybrid), with office workers scoring higher (Figure 23). In three work location comparison, the hybrid workers have higher well-being index score than office (workplace/on-site) and remote, respectively (Figure 24). We also observed that the hybrid model delivers more favourable results than fully remote working in some of the WHO-well-being sub-items.

Figure 23: WHO-5 Well-being Index mean score distribution according to the working location

In Figure 23 box plot compares the WHO-5 well-being index scores between two work location groups: remote-hybrid and workplace (on-site). The median well-being score is slightly higher for on-site workers compared to those in remote-hybrid arrangements. However, **the interquartile range (IQR) for both groups is similar, indicating comparable variability in well-being scores within each group.**

Outliers are present in both groups, with several on the lower end of the scale, particularly among remote-hybrid workers. This suggests that while most remote-hybrid workers have well-being scores clustered around the median, a few individuals report significantly lower well-being. **On-site workers show a slightly broader distribution, but with fewer outliers.** Overall, the plot indicates that while the average well-being scores are slightly higher for on-site workers, remote-hybrid workers experience similar variability in well-being, with some reporting lower well-being outcomes. **This suggests that work location alone may not fully account for differences in well-being, and other factors may contribute to these variations.**

Figure 24: Mean values of WHO-5 total well-being scores comparison between remote, hybrid and on-site workers (a boxplot graphic) and in gender groups

The box plot (Figure 24) illustrates the distribution of WHO-5 well-being index scores across three different work locations: remote, hybrid, and workplace (on-site). **The median well-being score is highest among hybrid workers, followed by remote workers, and lowest among on-site workers.** The interquartile range (IQR), represented by the box, indicates that hybrid workers not only have higher median scores but also a broader range of well-being scores compared to on-site and remote workers, suggesting greater variability in well-being within this group.

Overall, the **findings suggest that hybrid work arrangements may be associated with better overall well-being**, as reflected in higher and more variable WHO-5 scores.

The analysis of the WHO-5 well-being subitems reveals significant associations between working location (remote, hybrid, and on-site) and various aspects of well-being, including cheerfulness, relaxation, activeness, feeling rested, and finding work interesting. The findings highlight the influence of work location on mental well-being and suggest that hybrid work may offer a more balanced well-being experience compared to fully remote or on-site work.

Cheerfulness: On-site workers report higher levels of cheerfulness compared to hybrid and remote workers

Relaxation: On-site workers feel more relaxed than those working remotely or in hybrid settings.

Activeness: Higher levels of activeness are reported by on-site workers, followed by hybrid and then remote workers.

Feeling Rested: On-site workers are more likely to feel rested compared to remote and hybrid workers.

Finding Work Interesting: On-site workers find their work more interesting than remote and hybrid workers.

Other well-being associated variables that include: i-**worrying about work** (at home), ii-**feeling tired after work** and iii-**concentration problems at work**. Descriptive findings (Appendix 3, Supplementary Table 9) indicate that:

- Among people who never reported feeling worried about work, 14.9% work remotely, 71.2% work at the office, and 13.9% work in a hybrid setting. In contrast, among those who reported feeling worried about work all the time, 17.8% work remotely, 60.0% work on-site, and 22.2% work in a hybrid setting. Please see Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 12 for gender-based distributions of worry about work.
- Among those who reported 'never feeling tired after work,' 16.8% work in a hybrid model, 62.0% work on-site, and 21.2% work remotely. In comparison, of those who reported 'always feeling tired after work,' 13.9% work remotely, 70.7% work on-site, and 15.5% work in a hybrid model. Please see Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 13 for gender-based distributions of feeling tired after work.

- For individuals who never experience concentration problems at work, 17.9% work remotely, 64.7% work on-site, and 17.4% work in a hybrid model. In contrast, among those who always have concentration problems at work, 16.0% work remotely, 67.4% work office, and 16.6% work in a hybrid model. Please see Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 14 for gender-based distributions of concentration problems at work.

3.1.4 Health-related outcomes

In this section, we summarised the data related to various health outcomes, including physical and mental burn-out, strain, anxiety, depression, upper body muscle pain, and headaches. We examine how these outcomes vary across different work locations in alignment with research objective 6.

Based on the self-reported findings in the categorical data, we observed a notable association between work location and various health outcomes.

Summary of various health related outcomes

- **Physical Burn-out:** More prevalent among on-site workers (33.4%) compared to remote or hybrid workers (28.0%).
- **Anxiety:** Levels are similar between on-site (32.2%) and hybrid/remote workers (32.9%).
- **Backache and Headache:** Reported by 53.1% and 55.0% of hybrid/remote workers, and by 52.7% and 53.6% of on-site workers, respectively.
- **Upper Body Muscle Pain:** Slightly higher among hybrid/remote workers (56.8%) compared to on-site workers (55.3%).

These results suggest that work location associated both the prevalence of certain health issues and perceptions of occupational safety, with remote work generally perceived as offering a safer environment.

- **Physical burn-out** is more prevalent among on-site workers (33.4%) compared to those working remotely or in hybrid settings (28.0%) (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Physical burn-out according to work location

- **Anxiety** levels are relatively similar, with 32.2% of on-site workers and 32.9% of hybrid/remote workers experiencing this condition (Figure 26).

Figure 26: Anxiety according to work location

- **Backache** and **headache** frequencies were 53.1% and 55.0%, among hybrid/remote workers, respectively, and 52.7% and 53.6% among on-site workers respectively (Figures 27-28).

Figure 27: Backache according to work location

Figure 28: Headache according to work location

- **Upper body muscle pain** is reported by 55.3% of on-site workers and 56.8% of hybrid/remote workers (Figure 29).

Figure 29: Upper body muscle pain by work location

3.1.5 Analysis on Emotional Burn-out, Physical Burn-out, Strain, and Depression Across Work Locations: Gender Lens

Mental health outcomes are also analysed by gender, such as the emotional and physical burn-out in relation to working locations (RO 6).

Emotional Burn-out:

- **Among men experiencing emotional burn-out:** 63.2% work on-site, 22.8% remotely, and 14.0% in a hybrid model. For women, 61.3% work on-site, 21.3% remotely, and 17.4% in a hybrid setting.
- **Among those not experiencing emotional burn-out:** The proportion of remote work is slightly higher for both genders, with 24.4% of men and 22.6% of women working remotely. Hybrid work is represented by 17.5% of men and 17.2% of women (Figure 30).

Additionally, according to the results of the logistic regression analysis, several factors were identified as risk factors for emotional burn-out: being female, being in the 25-44 age group compared to the 16-24 age group, job insecurity, work intensity, presenteeism (working during sickness), discrimination, and night work. Conversely, the analysis also revealed several protective factors against emotional burn-out: autonomy, flexible working hours, social support, intrinsic rewards, opportunities for self-realisation, training opportunities, the ability to work during free time, the ability to take time off when needed, and low noise exposure (Appendix 5, Supplementary Table 4).

Figure 30: Distribution of presence of burn-out according to the work location and gender

Physical Burn-out:

- **Physical burn-out** is more prevalent among on-site workers, with 62.7% of men and 61.5% of women affected. In contrast, 16.9% of men and 16.8% of women experiencing physical burn-out work remotely, while 20.4% of men and 21.7% of women work in hybrid settings.
- **Men and women who do not experience physical burn-out** show a higher tendency to work remotely, with 24.4% of men and 23.7% of women working remotely (Figure 31).

Figure 31: Distribution of physical burn-out according to work location and gender

Strain:

- High-strain work is predominantly on-site, with 78.9% of men and 75.8% of women belonging to this category. Remote work is less common among high-strain workers, with only 7.3% of men and 8.8% of women working remotely (Figure 32).
- For those not in high-strain jobs, remote work is more common (23% for men and 22.6% for women).

Figure 32: Distribution of strain according to work location according and gender

Depression:

- Among men who are not at risk of depression, 59.2 % work on-site, 20.0% remotely, and remaining 20.8% in a hybrid setup. For those at risk of clinical depression, remote work increases to 24.0% (Figure 33).
- Women who are not at risk of depression mostly work on-site (56.8%), with 21.1% remote and 22.1% hybrid. For women at risk of clinical depression, remote work is slightly higher at 24.5%.

Figure 33: Distribution of clinical depression by work location and gender

These findings suggest that individuals experiencing emotional or physical burn-out, high strain, or those who are at risk of depression are more likely to work on-site. However, those not experiencing these conditions tend to have a higher proportion of remote work, regardless of gender. This pattern highlights an important potential link between on-site work and increased health risks or stressors.

3.2 Summary of the univariate and multivariate analyses

The summary of previous findings can be found in Table 16. The data shows that 58% of workers are on-site, 21.6% work remotely, and 20.4% work in a hybrid model. Men are slightly more likely to work on-site (59%) compared to women (56.9%), while the gender distribution for remote and hybrid work is relatively even. Education levels are higher among remote and hybrid workers, with 67.1% holding tertiary degrees, compared to 54.4% of on-site workers. Younger workers (ages 16-24) are predominantly on-site (74.9%).

Factor	On-site Work	Remote Work	Hybrid Work
Overall Distribution	58.0%	21.6%	20.4%
Gender	Men: 59%, Women: 56.9%	Men: 21.1%, Women: 22.1%	Men: 19.9%, Women: 21%
Education	54.4% with tertiary degree	67.1% with tertiary degree	67.1% with tertiary degree
Age Group (16-24)	74.9%	13%	12.2%
Housework (Men)	53% daily, 77% never	26% daily	-
Housework (Women)	58% daily, 68.8% never	22% daily	-
Childcare (Men)	60.3% never	20% daily	21% daily
Childcare (Women)	56% never	20% daily	21% daily
Night Work	77.5%	29.9% rarely	27% rarely
Working Hours	48+ hours/week: 58%	35-40 hours/week: 50%	35-40 hours/week: 50%
Computer Usage	49.2%	26.6%	24.2%
Work-Life Balance (Men)	Not at all well: 71.5%	12.9%	16.5%
Work-Life Balance (Women)	Not at all well: 68.7%	15.5%	15.9%
Engagement Level	High: 42.6%	High: 38%	High: 38%
Anxiety	32.2%	32.9%	32.9%
Physical Burn-out (Men)	65%	15%	19%
Physical Burnout (Women)	62%	17%	19%
Strain (High)	Men: 79%, Women: 76%	Men: 7%, Women: 9%	Men: 13%, Women: 13%
Depression Risk (Men)	59%	24%	20%
Depression Risk (Women)	57%	24%	21%
Occupational Health Risk	31.3%	24.1%	24.1%

Table 16: Summary of descriptive associations driven from univariate analysis

Key Aspects

- The distribution of work locations reveals that workplace-based work remains predominant across most countries and demographics, with significant variations based on gender, education, age, and other factors.
- On-site work is most common in Kosovo and other Eastern European countries, while remote and hybrid work is more prevalent in the U.K. and Nordic countries in their own population.
- Men and women show similar patterns in work locations, though **women slightly favour remote, and hybrid work more** than men.
- **Higher education levels are associated with increased remote and hybrid work**, and younger workers are more likely to work on-site.
- **Housework and childcare responsibilities are more evenly distributed among remote and hybrid workers**, while on-site workers tend to engage less in these activities.
- Job quality indicators such as **autonomy, flexible working time, and learning opportunities are more prevalent** in remote and hybrid work settings.
- Health outcomes, including burn-out, anxiety, and musculoskeletal pain, vary slightly with work location, with on-site workers generally reporting higher levels of physical strain and health risks.
- **Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) Risks:** On-site workers report higher OSH risks (31.3%) compared to hybrid/remote workers (24.1%). Remote workers are most likely to report no OSH risks (82.0%), followed by on-site workers (68.7%) and hybrid workers (60.1%).

Summary of Logistic regression initial models for work location associated factors including urbanity:

The data illustrates significant associations in work location possibilities and potential impacts on various variables.

Factors associated with work location were analysed via a logistic regression model (Appendix 5, Supplementary Table 3). The analysis identifies key factors that are significantly associated with the odds of working on-site versus remotely in this data analysis. **Urbanity was associated with 28% lower odds of working on-site. Age is a significant factor**, with older age groups associated with a lower likelihood of working on-site. **High work intensity and flexible working hours were associated** with reduced odds of working on-

site, while physical demands, discrimination, unsocial working hours and opportunities for self-realisation were associated with increased odds of working on-site. Full-time employment was also significantly associated with increased odds of working on-site. These findings highlight the importance of considering demographic and job quality factors in relation to RWAs. Logistic **regression analysis of work at the workplace vs remote comparisons including urbanity significant results summarised in Table 17.**

Variables (result vs ref.)	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval	Significance
Urban location	0.722	[0.572, 0.91]	***
Gender (woman vs man)	0.994	[0.807, 1.225]	
(16-24 ref.)			
Age Group 25-34	0.671	[0.454, 0.992]	**
Age Group 35-44	0.464	[0.308, 0.701]	***
Age Group 45-55	0.523	[0.339, 0.808]	***
Age Group 56+	0.42	[0.258, 0.683]	***
Job Quality Indicators (false vs true)			
Work Intensity	0.759	[0.613, 0.941]	**
Physical Demands	2.406	[1.821, 3.178]	***
Discrimination	1.501	[1.085, 2.076]	**
Unsocial Working Hours	1.756	[1.165, 2.647]	***
Flexibility of Working Hours	0.497	[0.343, 0.722]	***
Opportunities for Self-realization	1.471	[1.16, 1.865]	***
Physical Risks	1.928	[1.455, 2.554]	***
Full-time Employment	1.988	[1.422, 2.78]	***
Rarely Night Work	0.477	[0.364, 0.626]	***
Sometimes Night Work	0.636	[0.448, 0.903]	**
Often Night Work	0.639	[0.426, 0.957]	**
Several Times a Month Free Time	1.667	[1.095, 2.538]	**
Less Often Free Time	3.997	[2.45, 6.519]	***
Never Free Time	7.619	[4.514, 12.857]	***
Fairly Easy to Take Time Off	0.634	[0.444, 0.906]	**
Computer Usage	0.084	[0.053, 0.133]	***
Total Household Size	1.251	[1.171, 1.337]	***
Low Noise Exposure	0.561	[0.441, 0.715]	***
*, **, *** significance level $p < 0.05$, 0.01 , 0.001 ; job insecurity, work-life balance, job strain seniority, presenteeism were not significant in the initial model.			

Table 17: Summary of the Logistic regression analysis model of work location associated factors

Another logistic regression model was performed to analyse the factors associated with emotional burn-out which included work location as an independent variable model (Appendix 5, Supplementary Table 4). In this model, work location serves as an independent variable, which does not significantly affect burn-out. Sex is

found to be associated significantly. If all other variables are kept unchanged, women are 1.2 times more likely to experience burnt-out than men (p-value <0.0001). That ranges between 11% to 36% more than men (95% CI). Work-life balance matters significantly. Those with better balance are less likely to have burned-out. Subjects with not at all well, are 3.1 times more likely to experience burnt-out. Presenteeism is also shown to be associated significantly with emotional burn-out. Individuals who work during sickness are 1.6 times more likely to experience burn-out, compared to those who do not.

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval	p-value
Gender			
Woman (vs Man)	1.225	[1.106, 1.357]	0.000 ***
Age Groups			
25-34 (vs 16-24)	1.256	[1.015, 1.555]	0.036 **
35-44 (vs 16-24)	1.254	[1.009, 1.558]	0.041 **
45-55 (vs 16-24)	1.223	[0.978, 1.530]	0.077 *
Job Quality			
Job insecurity	1.588	[1.395, 1.807]	0.000 ***
Work intensity	2.415	[2.123, 2.748]	0.000 ***
Discrimination	1.974	[1.726, 2.258]	0.000 ***
Autonomy	0.873	[0.790, 0.965]	0.008 ***
Flexibility of working hours	0.554	[0.469, 0.654]	0.000 ***
Social support	0.728	[0.645, 0.822]	0.000 ***
Intrinsic rewards	0.629	[0.558, 0.709]	0.000 ***
Opportunities for self-realisation	0.734	[0.661, 0.815]	0.000 ***
Training opportunities	1.139	[1.023, 1.268]	0.018 **
Work-life Balance			
Well (vs Very well)	1.320	[1.172, 1.485]	0.000 ***
Not very well (vs Very well)	2.174	[1.870, 2.527]	0.000 ***
Not at all well (vs Very well)	3.102	[2.488, 3.867]	0.000 ***
Night Work			
Rarely (vs Never)	0.860	[0.750, 0.986]	0.031 **
Sometimes (vs Never)	0.780	[0.653, 0.931]	0.006 ***
Ability to Work in Free Time			
Several times a week (vs Daily)	0.763	[0.610, 0.954]	0.018 **

Table 18: Summary table of Logistic regression analysis results for Burn-out

Summary of the associations for emotional burn-out

The logistic regression analysis examining **emotional burn-out** (burnout_emot) identifies several significant predictors (Table 18). Particularly **gender plays a critical role**, with women being 1.2 times more likely to experience emotional burn-out than men, indicating a statistically significant difference. **Age also influences** the risk of burn-out, with individuals aged 15-34 and 35-44 being 26% and 25% more likely to experience burn-

out than the youngest cohort. **The importance of work-life balance is highlighted**, as individuals with a **poor work-life balance ('not at all well')** are **3.1 times more likely to report burn-out**. Frequency of night work affects burn-out, with those who rarely or sometimes work nights being 14% and 22% less likely to experience burn-out, respectively, although these effects are not significant for those who often or always work nights.

The availability of leisure time is a significant determinant, with those with less frequent leisure time being 55% less likely to experience burn-out than those with daily leisure time. The ease of taking time off work is inversely correlated with the likelihood of burn-out, suggesting that those who find it more difficult to take time off work are less likely to experience burn-out. In addition, people who answered 'yes' to a particular presentation were 1.6 times more likely to experience burn-out. Working less than 48 hours a week is associated with a 14% reduction in the risk of burn-out, and lower noise levels correlate with a 26% reduction in the likelihood of burn-out. Conversely, factors such as work location, physical demands, unsocial working conditions, physical risk, supervisor's gender, private sector employment, full-time employment, seniority, ICT use, and household size have no significant effect on risk of burn-out.

4 RESULTS OF LITERATURE REVIEW

The results are organised according to the research questions: Organisational arrangements, virtual team, psycho-social factors, occupational health and safety, formulated under the working conditions sub-chapter. Location and home-based work environment given under the living conditions. The characteristics of work-life balance, impacted by working and living conditions, are categorised into two groups: Work-life interface components related to working conditions and life-work interface components. These categories are discussed in a separate section. Health and well-being, and mental health are combined in ensuing chapters. The gender perspective is summarised separately. The flow diagrams of nested search for subtopics in the publication pool of working and living conditions are not included. Topics that are not in line with the aim of RMAP D1.3 are not included. In addition to the primary selection procedure outlined in the flow diagrams, the BERTopic literature pool was further utilised through nested searches for pertinent keywords within subtopics, thereby enhancing contextual understanding. To enrich the context, we also included systematic reviews used for topic summaries, along with reviews from diverse disciplines and secondary research perspectives grounded in theoretical frameworks relevant to the subtopics. Furthermore, institutional reports, government documents, conference proceedings, dissertations, theses, discussions, and working papers were reviewed to capture a broad range of literature.

4.1 Topic Distributions and Trends

This section provides the key topic trends and distributions related to RWAs in scientific publications over the past ten years and summarises the focal points of interest that have emerged in academic and professional discussions within publications (**Research Objective 1: Distributions of publications, distributions of topics, and trends over the years**). This summary **provides a scientific insight into trends across key topics from 2010 to early 2024, highlighting their current relevance, future potential, and identifying critical gaps that may shape the future of work**. In this context, **the findings are derived from heat map data, which illustrates the occurrences and trends of specific topics over time, from 2010 to early 2024**, particularly in relation to RWAs (Remote Working Arrangements) topics (Figure 36) and **Topic Words (a list of the most repeated and statistically significant coherent keywords for each topic, which highlighted the key areas of focus within**

those trends, Table 19; time trends graphics in Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 6). **This approach provides a macro perspective insight on remote work associated working and living conditions aspects.**

Figure 34: Global distribution of publications in numbers ([hyperlink](#))

The distribution of papers by country and the distribution of papers by topic are presented in the Figures 34 and 35, respectively).

The distribution of scientific publications across different locations, countries, and institutions is crucial due to geographical and cultural considerations. Remote work experiences and outcomes can vary significantly depending on regional differences, including distinct labour regulations, organisational cultures, infrastructure, and socio-economic conditions. Interpreting research from various locations helps capture this diversity, providing a more comprehensive understanding of remote work globally. Cultural norms around work-life balance, communication styles, and hierarchical structures also deeply influence remote work dynamics, with publications reflecting these nuances and offering insights into how remote work adapts to local expectations. Additionally, institutions vary in their support for remote work, including technological infrastructure, training programmes, and policy frameworks based on the location.

Finally, the distribution of research across different locations emphasises the importance of local and global perspectives, policy impacts, and equity in access to remote work. By examining papers from various regions, we can understand how different policies shape remote work practices, ensure diverse perspectives are included, and address disparities in access to remote work opportunities. This comprehensive approach is essential for developing effective, inclusive remote work strategies globally.

Over time, trends in publication outputs may reflect shifting research priorities as well as the growing global interest in remote work. Line graphs according to the years of groups can be seen in Appendix 3, Supplementary Figure 6.

Virtual Teams

Trends: Over the past decade, the concept of virtual teams has gained substantial traction, particularly during the Covid-19 pandemic (2020-2023), when remote work became a necessity. The trend peaked in 2023, reflecting widespread adoption and the challenges associated with managing distributed teams. The first quarter of 2024 suggests a continuation in this trajectory, with projections indicating that virtual teams will remain a critical focus area, albeit with a shift towards optimising hybrid models that blend remote and in-person collaboration.

Topic Words: The words clustered around the theme of virtual teams, include ‘team, virtual, environment, work, knowledge, design, project, communication, user, collaboration.’ This sequence reflects a focus on how teams’ function in virtual environments, emphasising work processes and exchange of knowledge sharing. Project design and communication seems to be among key areas, with collaboration and user experience being essential components in these settings.

Infrastructure

Trends: Infrastructure has consistently been a critical enabler of workplace productivity, especially as digital transformation accelerated over the past decade. Interest in this topic has seen steady growth, particularly in the post-pandemic era, as organisations sought robust systems to support remote work. The data for early 2024 suggests that this trend will continue, with ongoing investment in digital and flexible infrastructure solutions to meet the demands of a decentralised workforce.

Topic Words: The words clustered around the theme of infrastructure, are ‘mobile, system, cloud, network, service, data, application, technology, device, user.’ This sequence reflects the dominance of mobile and

cloud-based systems, emphasising the critical roles of networks and services, followed by data management and the application of technology. The integration of devices into this infrastructure fosters a user-centric approach.

Organisational Arrangements

Trends: Organisational arrangements have undergone significant scrutiny over the past ten years as companies navigate evolving work environments and the need for more agile structures. Interest in this topic grew steadily, peaking in 2023 as businesses explored new models to remain resilient in the face of disruptions. Early 2024 data suggests that this exploration is far from being over, with continued interest in refining organisational structures to optimise remote and hybrid work environments.

Topic Words: The words clustered around organisational arrangements are ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, as ‘telework, workflow, business, work, company, employee, technology, teleworking, new, social.’ This sequence underscores the central role of telework in optimising workflows and business operations, focusing on how companies and employees adapt to new technologies and teleworking practices, while maintaining social dynamics.

Work-Life Balance

Trends: Work-life balance has been a persistent concern throughout the past decade, particularly during the pandemic, when the boundaries between professional and personal life got blurred. The trend draws consistent interest, with a significant resurgence in the past few years, as employees and employers alike grapple with maintaining balance in a remote work setting. The trend is expected to continue growing in 2024, pointing to the ongoing need for strategies that support healthy work-life integration.

Topic Words: The words clustered around work-life balance are ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, as ‘work, family, employee, working, flexible, life, hour, time, flexibility, conflict.’ This sequence reflects discussions on managing the interplay between work and family life, with a strong emphasis on flexibility in working hours. The recurring theme of conflict between work and personal life denotes the ongoing challenge of striking a balance.

Gender

Trends: Gender-related publications have fluctuated in prominence over the past decade, with a notable rise in attention in recent years, particularly as diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) initiatives have gained

momentum. The topic peaked in 2023, reflecting broader societal movements and policy changes aimed at promoting gender equality. Early 2024 data suggests that this focus will continue to strengthen, with an increasing emphasis on integrating gender discussions within broader DEI frameworks.

Topic Words: The words clustered around gender-related issues are ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, as ‘woman, career, work, gender, female, working, men, home, flexible, family.’ This sequence reflects a focus on the career challenges faced by women, particularly in balancing work and family responsibilities. The emphasis on flexibility and the roles of men and women at home highlights points to broader societal shifts towards gender equality in the workplace.

Digital Labour Market

Trends: The digital labour market has attracted a rapidly growing interest over the past decade, especially as work increasingly shifted online. The trend gained significant momentum post-2015 and surged during the pandemic, reflecting the growing relevance of gig work, remote jobs, and the digital economy. The first quarter of year 2024 indicates that this trend will continue, driven by ongoing developments in technology, automation, and the need for new regulatory frameworks.

Topic Words: The words clustered around the digital labour market are ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, as ‘platform, employment, worker, work, labour, gig, market, social, online, economy.’ This sequence characterises the digital labour market, with a strong focus on platform-based employment. The nature of work in an online economy is central, with significant attention given to the social implications and labour dynamics of these emerging markets.

Caregiving Responsibilities

Trends: Caregiving responsibilities have garnered moderate attention over the past decade, with a marked increase during the pandemic as the need to balance work and caregiving became more pronounced. The trend peaked in 2023, and the data for early 2024 suggests stable interest, highlighting the importance of continued support for caregivers within the workforce, particularly in remote and hybrid work settings.

Topic Words: The words clustered around caregiving responsibilities are ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, as ‘mother, child, family, care, work, parent, father, working, hour, policy.’ This sequence underscores the significant role of mothers in family care, with an emphasis on how caregiving responsibilities are balanced with work. The importance of parental roles, including both mothers and fathers, is reflected,

with particular focus on how working hours and policies are associated with the ability to manage these responsibilities.

Work Location

Trends: The relevance of work location has evolved significantly over the past ten years; particularly as remote work has diminished the need for traditional office spaces. Interest in this topic has grown steadily, peaking in 2023 as organisations and individuals navigated the implications of location-independent work. The trend is expected to remain strong in 2024, with continued exploration of digital nomadism and the legal and logistical challenges of managing distributed teams.

Topic Words: The words clustered around location-related trends are ordered by frequency and statistical coherence as ‘home, digital, housing, work, nomad, rural, space, worker, tourism, country.’ This sequence reflects an increasing focus on digital nomadism and the impact of remote work on housing and rural spaces. The keywords suggest a shift towards exploring job opportunities beyond traditional urban centres, including the effects on tourism and local economies.

Topic Name	Top 10 Keywords	Count
Virtual Team	['team', 'virtual', 'environment', 'work', 'knowledge', 'design', 'project', 'communication', 'user', 'collaboration']	741
Infrastructure	['mobile', 'system', 'cloud', 'network', 'service', 'data', 'application', 'technology', 'device', 'user']	682
Organisational Arrangements	['telework', 'workflow', 'business', 'work', 'company', 'employee', 'technology', 'teleworking', 'new', 'social']	569
Work-life balance	['work', 'family', 'employee', 'working', 'flexible', 'life', 'hour', 'time', 'flexibility', 'conflict']	557
Gender	['woman', 'career', 'work', 'gender', 'female', 'working', 'men', 'home', 'flexible', 'family']	341
Digital Labor Market	['platform', 'employment', 'worker', 'work', 'labour', 'gig', 'market', 'social', 'online', 'economy']	297
Caregiving Responsibilities	['mother', 'child', 'family', 'care', 'work', 'parent', 'father', 'working', 'hour', 'policy']	280
Location	['home', 'digital', 'housing', 'work', 'nomad', 'rural', 'space', 'worker', 'tourism', 'country']	263
Commuting	['travel', 'trip', 'time', 'commuting', 'transport', 'activity', 'model', 'telecommuting', 'transportation', 'mode']	257
Occupational Health	['health', 'work', 'worker', 'occupational', 'risk', 'safety', 'intervention', 'physical', 'workplace', 'related']	221

Legal Regulation Needs	['tax', 'work', 'law', 'union', 'worker', 'remote', 'regulation', 'labour', 'working', 'legal']	213
Environmental	['energy', 'workshop', 'climate', 'building', 'lighting', 'air', 'community', 'occupant', 'office', 'environmental']	135
Disabled People	['disability', 'health', 'work', 'accommodation', 'employee', 'people', 'employment', 'factor', 'workplace', 'employer']	127
Mental Health	['mental', 'health', 'sleep', 'stress', 'anxiety', 'work', 'depression', 'pandemic', 'covid', 'working']	95
Ageing Workforce	['retirement', 'older', 'age', 'worker', 'employment', 'workforce', 'work', 'aging', 'working', 'health']	84
Other/outlier	['acoustic', 'sound', 'noise', 'office', 'speech', 'auditory', 'open', 'plan', 'environment', 'quality']	13

Table 19: Paper counts by topic name and the most frequent 10 keywords in each BERTopic analysis

Figure 35: The distribution of topic clusters in the literature based on the latest BERTopic analysis adjusted TF-IDF scores

Topics/Year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Virtual Team	18	16	14	20	23	22	28	18	25	28	27	72	84	92	35
Infrastructure	28	17	17	21	25	30	29	27	31	35	38	48	56	62	30
Organisational Arrangements	9	12	20	14	10	11	18	14	19	31	33	39	46	51	17
Work-life balance	16	13	17	22	16	23	20	21	21	21	25	39	32	35	31
Gender	8	6	10	13	5	13	11	7	17	18	28	21	22	47	15
Digital Labor Market	3	2	8	3	9	6	11	16	19	18	26	29	26	50	23
Caregiving Responsibilities	6	7	10	10	10	11	15	6	8	14	18	27	19	41	11
Location	4	3	4	4	9	14	13	12	11	12	19	26	39	34	22
Commuting	5	5	7	6	14	9	10	12	15	13	23	14	21	22	18
Occupational Health	2	6	3	5	6	8	6	6	7	15	21	29	29	29	11
Legal Regulation Needs	2	4	5	5	6	2	4	5	7	6	16	24	31	50	15
Environmental	4	4	0	4	3	3	1	2	3	2	7	24	22	28	12
Disabled People	3	2	3	4	6	5	7	6	3	2	5	13	19	12	6
Mental Health	1	0	0	1	0	1	3	1	2	1	6	18	16	20	16
Aging Workforce	5	4	3	7	5	2	1	1	6	7	6	9	5	2	2

Figure 36: Heat map of topics in the literature according to the years as the highest numbers (BERTopic by Years)

Commuting

Trends: The topic of commuting has seen relatively stable interest over the past decade, with fluctuations reflecting changes in work patterns, particularly during the pandemic when commuting became less relevant. The early 2024 data suggests a stable interest in understanding its role within hybrid work models and its broader impacts on transport and commuting patterns.

Topic Words: The words clustered around commuting, ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, are 'travel, trip, time, commuting, transport, activity, model, telecommuting, transportation, mode.' This sequence reflects discussions around the time and logistics of travel, with an increasing emphasis on telecommuting as an alternative. The keywords suggest ongoing exploration of evolving commuting patterns and their implications for modes of transportation.

Occupational Health

Trends: Occupational health has become an increasingly important topic over the past decade, with significant growth in interest during the pandemic as organisations sought to protect the well-being of their remote workers. The trend has stabilised in recent years, with ongoing interest in preventive health measures and the use of digital tools to promote occupational health. Early 2024 data indicates that this topic will continue to be a key area of focus, particularly in addressing long-term health risks associated with remote work.

Topic Words: The words clustered around occupational health, ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, are 'health, work, worker, occupational, risk, safety, intervention, physical, workplace, related.' This sequence reflects discussions centred on the health of workers, with significant attention given to occupational, risk, safety, intervention, physical, workplace, and related aspects. The emphasis on health underscores the importance of creating supportive and well-managed working environments.

Legal and Regulatory Needs

The need for legal regulations in the evolving work landscape has witnessed a sharp increase in attention over the past decade, particularly as remote work and digital labour markets have posed new legal challenges. Interest in this topic peaked in 2023, with early 2024 data suggesting continued strong focus on the need to develop comprehensive legal frameworks that address the complexities of modern work arrangements.

Topic Words: The words clustered around legal regulations, ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, are 'tax, work, law, union, worker, remote, regulation, labour, working, legal.' This sequence reflects related

publications on tax matters coherent with work, union and worker aspects, as well as regulatory considerations within the context of remote work.

Environmental Aspects

Trends: Environmental concerns have gained significant traction in workplace discussions, particularly in the wake of increased remote work, highlighting both positive and negative environmental impacts. The trend grew notably after 2021, peaking in 2023, and the early 2024 data suggests stable or slightly increased interest, emphasising the importance of sustainable work practices and corporate responsibility in reducing the carbon footprint of remote work practices.

Topic Words: The words clustered around environmental concerns, ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, are 'energy, workshop, climate, building, lighting, air, community, occupant, office, environmental.' This sequence reflects a focus on energy efficiency, climate impact, and building design. The words indicate a growing interest in creating sustainable and healthy work environments, both within physical offices and across the broader community.

Disability

Trends: The discussion of workers with disabilities have been a steady but less prominent area of focus over the past decade. Interest in this topic peaked in 2022, reflecting a growing awareness of the importance of accessibility in digital work environments. While the trend saw a slight decrease in 2023, the early 2024 data indicates stable interest, underscoring the need for continued efforts to create inclusive workplaces that fully support employees with disabilities.

Topic Words: Words clustered around the disability theme, ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, are 'disability, health, work, accommodation, employee, people, employment, factor, workplace, employer.' This sequence reflects discussions that emphasise the importance of disability, health, workplace accommodation, and inclusive employment practices. The focus is on ensuring that workplaces are accessible and supportive for people with disabilities, with a strong emphasis on disability-related health supports, employment factors, and the role of employers.

Mental Health

Trends: Mental health has seen a dramatic rise in attention over the past decade, particularly as the pandemic highlighted the challenges of isolation and stress in remote work environments. The trend has continued to grow, with 2023 showing attracting significant interest in 2023, and early 2024 data indicates that mental health will remain a critical focus area as organisations seek to support their employees' well-being in a rapidly changing work landscape.

Topic Words: Words clustered around the mental health theme, ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, are 'mental, health, sleep, stress, anxiety, work, depression, pandemic, Covid, working.' This sequence reflects discussions centred on mental health, with a particular focus on sleep associations, stress, anxiety, and depression. While studies focusing solely on the Covid-19 were excluded from keywords in the first place, discussions related to the pandemic continue to influence remote work-related publications.

Aging Workforce

Trends: The aging workforce has witnessed a declining interest over the past decade, with minimal attention in recent years. The first quarter of 2024 continues this trend, suggesting that the challenges faced by older workers in a digital economy may be underexplored. This highlights a gap in current discussions that might benefit from research focused on lifelong learning, adaptable career paths, and the impact of technology on older employees.

Topic Words: Words clustered around the aging workforce theme, ordered by frequency and statistical coherence, are 'retirement, older, age, worker, employment, workforce, work, aging, working, health.' This sequence reflects discussions centred on retirement, employment, the importance of age in workforce aging, and health-related aspects. The recurring focus on age-related challenges points to the need for policies that support older employees as they continue to contribute to the workforce.

Conclusion

This analysis indicates that the focus on key areas such as virtual teams, infrastructure, organisational arrangements, and work-life balance remains strong, driven by ongoing adaptation to the post-pandemic work environment. Given the proportion of the early 2024 data, as compared to the trends of the past decade, it is clear that many topics are likely to see continued or even increased interest throughout the year. However, important gaps persist in areas such as the integration of gender within broader Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion initiatives, the sustainability of digital labour markets, and support for aging workers and workers with

disabilities. Addressing these gaps will be essential in shaping a more inclusive, sustainable, and resilient future of work.

The keywords from each topic trend reveal the underlying themes and areas of focus that have shaped publications over the past decade. From virtual collaboration and digital infrastructure to gender equality and mental health, the workplace has undergone a significant transformation. Understanding these key areas provides insight into the current state of work and pinpoints where continued attention and research are needed to address emerging challenges and opportunities.

4.2 Systematic Search and Narrative Review Results

This section provides an exploratory review of the scientific literature on the relevant Research Questions, accompanied by additional supportive contextual literature in the subtitles of the report. Furthermore, it includes defined topic modelling themes driven from complementary literature and incorporated in the existing body of knowledge in an effort to uncover working and living conditions, as well as the concept of health and well-being, particularly in the context of RWAs. The literature review is structured according to the sections outlined in the proposal with a view, to comply with and convey the information defined therein, as well as in the conceptual context.

The process included alignment with the research questions and R-MAP objectives, searching existing literature, screening for inclusion, and incorporating information from primary studies. The studies reviewed were selected and evaluated through a rigorous process based on their relevance to the research questions. This process involved carefully selecting and excluding exploratory contextual materials to ensure that all relevant research elements—such as **RWAs, working and living conditions, and outcome keywords like work-life balance, health, and well-being**—were included in reviews, discussion papers, proceedings, and pertinent theses. These studies are summarised here, to **highlighting the exploratory nature of this report and aiming to enhance understanding of RWAs and their potential future impacts**. The literature provides various insights into working conditions, work-life balance, remote work, and potential outcomes. This step adopted an exploratory approach, and it did not use a specific bias tool for the assessment of publications due to comprehensive title of the report, and lack of comparability among the varying interdisciplinary methodologies regarding the concept of RWAs, related measures variables, and variety of theoretical differences. After the selection and elimination process, considering the relevance of the research questions

and the exploratory contextual contributions, the publications included in the narrative review were chosen. These publications consist of literature, including discussion papers, and a limited number of proceedings on specific subfields relevant to the topic as well as the subtopics under the research question.

These are summarised in this section, manifesting the exploratory characteristics of this report towards enhancing the understanding of RWAs and their potential future impacts. The literature provides various insights into working conditions, work-life balance, remote working and related potential outcomes.

Key findings include the rapid evolution of new forms of employment, characterised by a lack of standardisation and common concepts across different household types (Table 20).

Qualitative studies	Findings and Policy Recommendations
(McNaughton et. al., 2014)	A strong desire exists for assistive technologies in home-based work setups, with a recommendation for policies that provide such technologies to disabled workers.
(Pollak et. al., 2023)	A strong majority of participants identified a need for clearer remote working arrangements to enhance productivity and job satisfaction.
(Mandl, 2021; Eurofound, 2023a)	The diversity of new employment forms requires Remote Working Arrangements to address diverse worker needs and conditions.

Table 20: Key findings and policy recommendations from qualitative studies

Summary of the mixed studies

The qualitative studies offer in-depth insights into the experiences and perspectives of workers in remote and hybrid work settings. Before the Covid-19 outbreak, McNaughton and colleagues (2014) revealed a strong desire for **assistive technologies among disabled workers** in home-based setups, recommending policies that **facilitate the provision** of such technologies (McNaughton et. al., 2014). Pollak and colleagues identify a significant need for clearer telework policies to enhance productivity and job satisfaction, based on professional perspectives (Pollak et. al., 2023). Additionally, Mandl and colleagues, in a presentation based on Eurofund data, point to the need for flexible policies to accommodate diverse needs of workers in various employment forms (Mandl, Eurofound, 2021).

Studies	Findings and Policy Recommendations
(Harunavamwe and Kanengoni, 2023)	The combined effect of technostress, work-life conflict, and role ambiguity needs to be managed to enhance employee well-being and productivity .
(Prasad et. al., 2023)	Their significant results for occupational stress affecting mental health, highlighting the need for support systems for remote workers .
(Rodríguez-Modroño, 2022)	Indicates that rural workers were less likely to work from home compared to urban workers , suggesting a need for policies that address infrastructure disparities.
(Kwon and Kim-Goh, 2023)	Telework and telecommute options improved work-life balance and productivity , recommending more support for telework infrastructure and policies .
(Wheatley, 2021)	Driving/travelling jobs are more often unpaid, highlighting the need for policies that address the compensation and support for travel-heavy jobs.
(Heiden et. al., 2021)	Due to the cross-sectional design of the study, it suggests more longitudinal studies to understand the long-term effects of telework.
(Palumbo, 2020)	Home-based telecommuting negatively affects productivity for some workers, recommending mixed models to cater to different productivity needs .
(Fakih, 2018)	Visible minority workers have less access to vacation leave, suggesting policies that promote equitable leave opportunities .
(Giovanis, 2017)	The positive effects of teleworking on happiness were significant for women , recommending policies that support telework for better work-life balance for female employees.
(Wood et. al., 2013)	Findings suggest fluctuating workloads impact employee well-being , recommending workload management policies to mitigate stress.
(Rojanasarot et. al., 2023)	This study finds that RWE significantly improves job satisfaction , recommending policies that support flexible remote work environments.

(Kurowska, 2018)	The impact of home-based work differs by gender , with women experiencing more work-life balance challenges , recommending gender-sensitive remote work policies .
(Lee and Kim, 2018)	Right to Request Flexibility Act highlighted as a policy recommendation to improve flexible working conditions.
(Tsang et. al., 2023)	The negative relationship between family-work conflict and job performance suggests the need for supportive policies that help balance family and work responsibilities.
(Foden, 2020)	Job quality can be improved by reducing excessive work hours and supporting flexible work arrangements, suggesting the implementation of comprehensive job quality policies.

Table 21: Key findings and policy recommendations from quantitative studies

Summary of Quantitative and Semi-quantitative Studies

Quantitative studies provide substantial data on the effects of remote work on employee well-being and productivity (Table 21). Harunavamwe and colleagues (2023) report that factors such as technostress, work-life conflict, and role ambiguity significantly impact employee well-being and productivity, emphasising the need for management strategies to mitigate these issues (Harunavamwe et.al., 2023). Similarly, Prasad et al. (2023) call attention to the mental health challenges linked to occupational stress in remote work settings, stressing the importance of support systems for remote workers. Paul (2022) and others observe that rural workers are less likely to work from home compared to their urban counterparts, indicating a need for policies that address infrastructure disparities (Paul, 2022; Rodríguez-Modroño, 2022). Other studies recommend improving telework infrastructure and compensating for travel-intensive jobs to enhance work-life balance and job satisfaction (Kwon and Kim-Goh 2023; Wheatley, 2021). As discussed by Kurowska, the gender impact of home-based work calls for more policies on gender-sensitive remote work to better support the work-life balance of female employees (Kurowska, 2018).

Key points

Quantitative studies reveal that remote work significantly impacts employee well-being and productivity. Key findings include:

- Technostress, work-life conflict, and role ambiguity are major factors affecting well-being and productivity, highlighting the need for effective management strategies.
- Mental health issues related to occupational stress in remote settings underscore the importance of support systems for remote workers.
- Rural workers face greater challenges in remote work compared to urban workers, suggesting a need for policies to address infrastructure disparities.
- Recommendations include improving telework infrastructure and compensating for travel-heavy roles to enhance work-life balance and job satisfaction.

Studies	Findings and Policy Recommendations
(Kossek et. al., 2023)	The review highlights the conceptual and practical challenges in work-life flexibility policies and suggests a need for a coherent framework to address boundary control and implementation.
(EU-OSHA, 2021)	The reports identify risks and hazards associated with remote work, recommending that policies should address ergonomics, mental health, and work-life balance.
(Eurofound, 2024)	The heterogeneity of new employment forms necessitates flexible policies to cater to diverse worker needs and conditions.
(Elmendorf, 2021)	The hybrid work model does not discriminate based on location, recommending policies that support flexible work arrangements to accommodate various worker preferences.

Table 22: Key findings and policy recommendations from reviews

The reviews assessed in this report presented in Table 22 demonstrate the richness of the current literature in terms of the number of qualitative, quantitative and review studies; yet these studies are mostly based on different theoretical frameworks. For the purposes of this report, **their findings and arguments have been considered not mature enough, and hence not included in the gathered scientific evidence base.**

However, we have also observed **that the impact of remote working on the intensity and dynamics of control is not clearly defined, which may affect working and living conditions in terms of work-life balance and associations with health and well-being.** There is a need for further studies that can provide data to assess mutual theories to comprehend the developmental aspects of the control criticalities of the changes, which keep evolving with significant momentum themselves.

Analytical review reports have revealed that there are **two main and contradictory views on autonomy:** that RWAs increase managers' control over workers and that technology makes it possible to **track how work is accomplished** with data and compliance to supervision; and that **RWAs reduce control over workers**, and that technology reduces direct supervision and peer pressure, depending on the nature of the work.

Binding and protective influences are discussed in terms of **employee involvement versus directive and authoritative elements.** Employees are reported to be influenced by **leadership characteristics;** it has been argued that delegating or directive leadership characteristics are critical for employees' coping mechanisms and may play a weaker role in RWAs, if they are not modified as needed. Overall, a critical finding emerges: **'Employee choices are shaped by the manager's sense of ownership style'**, calling for further research on managers' ownership styles and their leadership characteristics.

Elmendorf et. al. (2021) proposes the hybrid working model as the most appropriate working arrangement when it alternates between teleworking and face-to-face working. The hybrid model is seen as an intermediate formula for enhanced productivity and work-life balance, maintaining the benefits of the face-to-face team, information sharing and collaboration. It is also argued that while fully-fledged remote working modality relies on high skills, **hybrid working can be applied without discrimination according to level of skills.**

The systematic reviews and other reviews highlight the significant developments and challenges in the field of remote work and occupational health. Kuijer et. al. (2024) provides an extensive overview of 50 years of research on musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), emphasising the importance of ergonomic interventions in the workplace. Their review points to the need for continuous monitoring and adaptation of workplace

ergonomics to mitigate MSDs (Kuijjer et. al., 2024). Kossek and colleagues discuss the conceptual and practical challenges in work-life flexibility policies, advocating for a coherent framework to address boundary control and implementation (Kossek et. al., 2023). Other reviews focusing on occupational safety and health risks of remote work, call attention to the necessity for policies that address ergonomics, mental health, and work-life balance (EU-OSHA 2021; Capecchi, 2021) The heterogeneity of new employment forms also entails flexible policies to cater to diverse worker needs and conditions (Eurofound, 2018b).

Based on the information provided by Eurofound reports, information is combined from a variety of study designs as observational, exploratory, and descriptive and combination of literature review, data analysis, and qualitative case studies. There were no accessed randomised, controlled experimental studies. The case studies were based on the employment forms identified as increasingly important across multiple countries, rather than using a random or representative sampling approach (Eurofound, 2018b) Different types of employment forms have been identified based on the case studies. These employments forms in relation to RWAs, which lack standardised practices with respect to the contract type, sector, company size place of work, or employment status, including self-employment or freelance status. New patterns are emerging for RWAs, influenced by the adaptability of the existing examples, infrastructure, as well as legislative frameworks. RWAs also connect the employee sharing and new developmental practices, indicating new forms of cooperative HR management (Eurofound, 2015). Geographical distance, non-standard types of employment, and strategic transition period assessments are foreseen as key aspects of further developments. RWAs also need to be evaluated for their potential in cross-company contracts, cross-country contracts, and research pilot practices are needed to formulate employee-friendly solutions. These aspects have been identified as research gaps, relevant for the long-term regulation of RWAs at various levels.

Positive effects on employee flexibility have been established by the literature; however, work-family conflict adversely affects productivity when working from home. These negative effects vary depending on the amount of time spent at home. Additionally, enhancement of job satisfaction and mitigation of work-life conflict through remote working are also significant.

One notable quasi-experimental study highlights the benefits of remote work eligibility on job satisfaction and organisational commitment, although it shows no significant effect on work-life balance. Even though this report evaluated systematic reviews, it is important to consider systematic reviews as comprehensive overviews that often lack statistical power without meta-analyses. **Longitudinal studies** only show some

demographic differences on their own populations, especially higher levels of leave of absence for men and for elderly workers. **Cross-sectional surveys dominate the current research designs**, focusing on metrics such as job satisfaction, work-life conflict, and productivity.

Summary of these studies highlight the multifaceted nature of work-life balance as well as the importance of considering different factors for a better understanding of employee outcomes, such as gender, age and job level.

- Significant findings summarised in subtitles include the negative impacts of family-work conflict on work-from-home productivity, moderated by the duration of work-from-home; and the positive effects of remote work on job satisfaction and work-life conflict.
- Mixed methods and quasi-experimental studies highlight the benefits of remote work eligibility on job satisfaction and organisational commitment, although there is no significant effect on work-life balance.
- Longitudinal analyses reveal demographic differences, such as higher vacation leave for men and older employees. These studies underscore the multifaceted nature of work-life balance and the importance of considering a variety factors, such as gender, age, and job level, in understanding employee outcomes.
- The reviewed articles from 2024 provide a comprehensive overview on different aspects of the work-life balance, focusing aspects on flexibility, overwork and non-fixed working hours.
- Cross-sectional surveys highlight the factors that contribute to work flexibility and the balance between academic vocation and pressure in academic communities.
- Longitudinal studies emphasise the role of flexible working arrangements in promoting gender equality.
- Experimental studies examine the relationship between overwork, paid leave and flexible working arrangements, while qualitative studies explore the implications of variable working hours in a globalised, technology-driven context.

4.2.1 Potential effects of RWAs on Working Conditions

This section provides findings on the RQ2 ‘how RWAs might influence organisational and individual working conditions’ (e.g. the form and nature of employment, costs for employees and employers, organisational services, psycho-social factors, job quality indicators, occupational health and safety services, and employee services).

The report places special emphasis on points i, ii, iii, and iv, exploring these items within the context of this particular question. These points are analysed based on the literature to identify their characteristics as antecedents of the concept of ‘organisational working conditions’ including ‘individual working conditions’ and ‘work-to-life-interface’.

Subtitles highlight potential effects of RWAs on working conditions by presenting findings from related literature. This section focuses on literature on R-MAP to provide an exploratory perspective for further developments in this field, offering visionary interdisciplinary solutions.

This chapter summarises the potential effects of RWAs on **the nature of employment, working style, working hours, income, job quality indicators including psycho-social factors and working environments, virtual teams, distance to work, organisational services, and occupational health and well-being services.**

Additionally, **the outcomes of these factors** are discussed in relation to **productivity, job satisfaction, engagement, commitment, and motivation**, which affect the personal and organisational outcomes of the working time, income, and organisational services. These considerations are examined within the context of remote work and the cycle of work-life balance in this chapter.

Working conditions are investigated in the literature at an individual level, organisational level, and some national level, with data and effects observed in different contexts including international institutional websites, thesis research reports, and governmental policy websites. This report primarily seeks to summarise this broad range and **varied** levels of information **with a specific aim**. Summary tables **provide** examples of recent **findings**, and other extracted material will be used **for further detailed evaluation**.

The term ‘working conditions’ encompasses a wide range of organisational arrangements inherent to the nature of employment (ILO, 2022; EU OSHA 2022a). On the organisational side, working conditions include work processes and procedures, job characteristics, pay arrangements, social security coverage, working

hours, employee benefits, flexibility arrangements, commuting arrangements, occupational health and welfare services, as well as the organisation and procedures of these health services. On the individual side, working conditions cover skills, seniority, income, job security, commute time, personal benefits, and other aspects related to work-specific roles and tasks. In this context, working conditions are explored within two main frameworks: **'organisational working conditions,'** which encompass employee services and organisational functions, and **'individual working conditions.'** In addition, working conditions determine an individual's exposure to her working environment and related processes. The time spent by the worker in the physical, chemical, psycho-social, ergonomic and biological environment, such as the location of the workplace, is closely related to the elements determined by individual characteristics related to work and skills, and these environmental interactions (EU-OSHA, 2021). For this reason, working conditions can also be referred to as **workplace elements and individual elements.** Workplace elements describe the organisational framework and structure for the provision and performance of work, while individual elements include the rights and duties of the employee, in the context of their level of skills and personal environment (Eurofound, 2023a; WHO/ILO 2021; ILO 2022).

The specific conditions of RWAs and the characteristics of working styles may vary according to the sector, occupation, employment type, and location characteristics that are subject to existing labour regulations (WHO/ILO, 2021; ILO, 2022; Eurofound 2023a; Dias et. al. 2022). Remote work is not universally applicable to all occupations, and its advantages must be weighed against potential disadvantages such as heightened work intensity and stress (Eurofound, 2023a).

While direct comparison of different layers and levels in the literature is not feasible, it is possible to identify an evaluation approach that focuses on common findings. **As the literature pool expands, new variables and related areas are likely to emerge.**

4.2.1.1 Potential effects of RWAs on the form and nature of employment:

Over the past decades, employment has been significantly influenced by transformations in the employment landscape, mostly driven by digitalisation, the move towards environmentally friendly practices in the EU, and socio-economic reforms accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic (Vanhercke B. and Spasova S., 2022). In 2021, the Covid-19 pandemic led to a significant rise in remote hybrid and remote working, as indicated by the fact that 22% of employees occasionally work from home. Prior to recent views on hybrid and remote working

(Wilson et. al., 2008; Opong Peprah, 2024), self-reported surveys after the pandemic showed that a significant majority of employees, over 60%, strongly preferred to continue working in a hybrid or remote arrangement. This led to a significant interest in working remotely at least some of the time throughout an employee's career (Eurofound, 2023a).

Provision of excellent working conditions with a special focus on the health and well-being of employees through increased safety measures as well as the implementation of directives aimed at protecting the rights of employees, as emphasised by the European Union, also applies to remote work¹². The focus of Eurofound's 2021-2024 initiative is on researching sustainable work and working conditions to continuously monitor job quality and workplace practices through publishing reports¹³. Eurofound reports and literature include efforts to examine how the process of ensuring remote working conditions, with a focus on employee health and well-being, has influenced work and family life after the Covid-19 pandemic. These efforts aim to shed light on future trends through surveys and studies (Eurofound, 2021b). **The findings reveal continuing challenges as well as the possibility of significant societal changes through the restructuring of the form and nature of employment for the future direction of implementation of working life policies and directives aimed at protecting workers' rights, including remote work, as emphasised by the European Union, yet comprehensive evidence of the relevant dynamics is still lacking.** Hybrid work models combining remote and in-office work have been promoted as a new norm, with benefits such as time and cost savings (Przybyl, 2022).

The findings reveal **continuing challenges** and the possibility of significant societal changes **through the restructuring of the form and nature of employment for the future** direction of implementation of working life policies and directives aimed at **protecting workers' rights, including telework, as emphasised by the European Union, but holistic evidence of the relevant dynamics is still lacking.**

The form and nature of employment have been profoundly influenced by Covid-19, and these effects are expected to continue as we enter a new era, particularly affecting employment relationships on a global scale (Kiran, 2021). This resulted in **different practices in temporary, flexible work and increasing inequalities in**

¹² <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/health-and-well-being-work>

¹³ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/sustainable-work>

opportunities and among office workers and manual workers, which might ultimately negatively impact vulnerable employees. Flexible forms of employment have become widely accepted and efficient, facilitated by technology differently across countries and sectors (Malousis et. al., 2023; Przybyl, 2022).

The forms of employment in Europe are influenced by institutional frameworks, historic-cultural factors and general labour market trends (Rhein, 2019; Dimova, 2019; Eurofound, 2024) and shifting towards more atypical forms of work, which poses a challenge to the traditional social security system. Remote work originated as a voluntary work arrangement that makes use of information and communications technology (Türkeş and Vuță, 2022). The pandemic had a diverse impact on employment, affecting different socio-economic groups, work arrangements, and industries. This necessitated the implementation of immediate fiscal measures to mitigate these consequences (Kashni and Thakur, 2021).

The shift in the very nature of employment away from traditional full-time jobs has also influenced the share of labour in the EU. It is stated that the main contributors to the labour share decline are shifted towards part-time and temporary employment; in contrast, service industries and highly skilled workers have seen gains in labour share because of this transition (Dimova, 2019).

Typical full-time employment with indefinite contracts is associated with labour law and social security protections, but these are not extended to many atypical workers, including flexible and remote workers. Previously, atypical workers were heterogeneous and ranged from low-skilled seasonal workers to high-skilled specialists on short-term contracts, but for home-office or remote working, this heterogeneity of the skill levels narrowed down regarding the computational or remote working skills. The increase in atypical employments has led to a need for adjustments to protect these workers since many rights and protections have been built around standard employment relationships. New forms of employment in the European market are one of the important changes in the context of technological and civilisational change of new generations who recently involved in the labour market after the pandemic and remote schooling (Grewiński and Kawa, 2021; Uścińska, 2020).

The incidence of atypical employment, such as temporary and part-time labour has first declined after pandemic period and subsequently rebounded to pre-pandemic levels (Mitri and Sartor, 2022). The Covid-19 pandemic has drawn more attention to flexible types of employment, with remote work particularly prominent (Przybyl, 2022).

During and after the Covid-19 pandemic, **the focus has shifted to discussions on the benefits of remote working, rather than its challenges and disadvantages.** This is particularly important in the face of **labour shortages in some sectors, inequalities and the need to adapt to future developments.** **Remote opportunities have triggered change and created challenges with respect to access to remote work in different sectors.** The desire to work remotely has spread rapidly and it became clear that there is a need for infrastructure, skills, technological development and adaptation in different sectors in coordination with stakeholders, consensus and compromise.

Remote work yields benefits such as improved work-life balance and independence. However, it also presents problems, including longer working hours, blurred lines between work and home life, and gender inequalities. The diversity of the sectors, professional roles, and access to remote work vary significantly depending on the work demands, e.g., office vs. manual workers, which can affect work-life balance in the long term. Flexibility was highlighted as an emerging trend for work-life arrangements even though it does not necessarily operate both ways (Eurofound 2021b, 2023a).

Eurofound report investigating psycho-social factors found that telework was limited to specific sectors and high-level positions, impacting more traditional office work environments. One of the main concerns of remote work was the accelerated polarisation of the labour market exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic (Braesemann et.al, 2022). Mid-wage jobs are most likely affected, and there was a shift in knowledge-intensive jobs as well as IT and professional roles in well-paid sectors (Figure 37). In contrast, there are labour shortages in healthcare, construction, and information technologies (Eurofound, 2023a).

The typical employment model, characterised by full-time, permanent work with a single employer, has declined over the past few years. In 2015, most of the workforce was engaged in traditional/typical forms of employment. This share dropped to approximately 5 % (Eurofound, 2023a, p. 38) by 2021. This decline in typical work settings indicates a transition towards more flexible work arrangements, which reflects broader shifts in the labour market facilitated by digital transformation and solving employee preferences.

Employment in the EU has increased more rapidly since 2019 compared to before that year.

On average, annual employment growth after 2019 was more than twice as fast as in the period before, despite facing stronger demographic challenges (Eurofound, 2024).

The most significant shifts in employment have been occupational rather than sectoral, with professional employment growing nearly twice as fast from 2019 to 2023 compared to the previous decade.

European labour markets are increasingly gender-equal, with women contributing to nearly two-thirds of the net employment growth over the last twenty years (Eurofound, 2024).

Transition of Working Style (Virtual team)

Digital transformation also brings different team, organisational culture and climate related transformation. Work design factors such as interdependence on results, task complexity and work resources interact with team virtuality to influence the functioning of teams, especially remote teams. Research shows that virtual work can improve job control, group cohesion and performance (Robertson et. al., 2022). However, there are also challenges such as communication problems, technical difficulties and potential barriers to information sharing (Schröder et. al., 2021; Handke et. al., 2020). Another study indicates that **implementing new ways of working might not lead to changes in psycho-social work characteristics, well-being, or job-related outcomes** (Nijp et. al., 2016). They assess the potential effects on satisfaction, motivation, productivity as an organisational outcome of psycho-social factors of remote work. Researchers indicate that there were no significant changes in job demands and social support, and they found that no significant time-group interactions for job demands, job autonomy, and support from colleagues and supervisors within the intervention group (Nijp et. al., 2016) as well as indicating that New Ways of Working (NWW) did not result in any notable changes to these major psycho-social work characteristics, and no significant changes were observed in job demands and social support (Nijp et. al., 2016). **Effective virtual teams can increase the productivity** as well based on the information flow and **accessibility** of the supported working life elements. It has been reported that 33% of employees felt more connected in virtual teams and 48% reported increased productivity, but this is not generalisable (Axtell, 2022). **Effective virtual workforce management** can increase team effectiveness and retention, with 52% of managers focusing on improving communication (Depoo and Hermida, 2024). **Job design factors such as task interdependence and job resources** have a significant impact

on virtual team functioning (Handke et. al., 2020). **While short-term negative effects may occur in virtual teams, it is indicated negative effects tend to diminish or disappear in long-term teams** (Ortiz de Guinea et. al., 2012). **Trust, leadership and communication** are defined as **key determinants** of virtual team performance (Garro-Abarca et. al., 2021). In another research, workers surveyed in Japan reported that the average productivity of working in a work-from-home (WFH) compared to working in a normal workplace was approximately 60-70% (Morikawa, 2023; Morikawa, 2024).

Self-employment non-attached work styles

Self-employment and freelance working are becoming increasingly important in the modern labour market. Freelancers have the opportunity to manage their careers through flexible working hours and project-specific tasks. This independent working style allows individuals to better manage their work-life balance and offers professional freedom, free from the constraints of traditional employment models. However, such working arrangements can also present challenges such as insecure working conditions and irregular income. Therefore, self-employment and non-attached work models deserve careful consideration in terms of the opportunities and challenges they present.

In this broader context, structured work climate and culture procedures provide a sense of order and consistency within organisations and shape the working environment. These procedures clarify employee expectations, define roles, and standardise work processes. A structured work climate encourages behaviours that are consistent with the organisation's values and can increase employee engagement. Especially when integrating new ways of working and technological advances, these structured procedures strengthen the ability to adapt to change. There is also the possibility that structured work climate procedures that mature the culture may, in theory and in practice, make it difficult to configure values with new ways of working and to take into account the concept of disengagement. De Carvalho and colleagues examine the use of technology in remote work, highlighting its benefits and challenges (De Carvalho et. al., 2022). The study involved 60 respondents working in home office settings, using electronic survey. Key advantages identified include non-displacement (63.3% completely agree), freedom with clothing (55% completely agree), and flexibility (51.7% completely agree), contributing to improved quality of life and productivity. However, challenges such as social isolation (56.7% completely disagree), increased working hours (26.7% partially agree and 18.3% completely agree), and career progression difficulties (31.7% partially agree) were also noted. The study points to **the**

need for organisations to support remote working with appropriate technological tools as well as legal frameworks to ensure a balanced and productive home office environment, with clear work climate procedures to increase the maturity of remote working arrangements.

The practicality and advantages of remote working have led to its modification and increased adoption. With a marginal increase, remote work has become a significant form of employment after the pandemic (Eurofound, 2023a). The growing prevalence of gig economy jobs reflects a significant shift towards temporary, project-based employment facilitated by digital networks for high-skilled office workers. A slight decline was observed in the rate of self-employment. In 2015, the proportion of the workforce was 15%, whereas in 2021 it went down to 12% (Eurofound, 2023a). The reduction in traditional employment signifies a shift towards a broader range of work arrangements. The prevalence of flexible work has significantly risen, with a notable transition towards alternative employment arrangements such as gig and platform jobs and temporary and part-time positions. The reduction in typical employment might be explained by the growing prevalence of gig and platform jobs, which offers an alternative form of employment for those seeking flexibility and autonomy. The emergence of gig and platform work represents one of the most significant evolvments observed in the labour market compared to the period between 2015 and 2021(Eurofound, 2015, Eurofound, 2021a, b). While these populations are not comparable, the proportions of each population in Eurofound reports can be seen in Figure 37.

Figure 37: ICT base increase of remote work in the EU Member States

It is crucial for the labour protection legislation to be extended from traditional to non-traditional forms of employment, such as temporary, part-time and gig work. This includes guarantees of fair wages, job security, the right to form trade unions, and participate in collective bargaining (Grewiński and Kawa, 2021; ILO, 1996).

To summarise, targeted policies are essential to ensure that the labour market adapts appropriately and fairly to significant changes in employment patterns. These policies are in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly the SDG 8 (decent work and economic growth) and SDG 10 (reducing inequalities) (Crawford, 2022; United Nations, 2015). Supporting workers in gig and platform jobs is indeed crucial considering advantages and disadvantages of remote working arrangements (ILO, 2021b; EU-OSHA, 2022b). Given the growing popularity of this type of employment, it is crucial to enact legislation that provides social security and benefits for these workers, thus protecting their well-being and job security. This includes providing traditional workers with health insurance, pensions, and other social protection (Eurofound, 2020a).

This requires the development of adaptable RWAs, and regulations based on the forms of employment and programmes that enable workers to achieve a good work-life balance between work and private life. It is crucial to adopt measures to promote techniques to reduce work-related stress and burn-out, especially for those involved in remote working and hybrid models by incorporating the remote employment types and related processes (EU-OSHA, 2023b; Eurofound, 2020a).

Developing and improving adaptability aspects and new challenges in working life, based on continuous training and the opportunity to improve in all aspects, and will make it easier for workers to adapt to changing employment patterns and technological developments. This is particularly important for older workers and those affected by technological developments under the RWAs (Grewiński and Kawa, 2021).

Remote work arrangements affect the form and nature of employment, including **employment contracts and job roles** based on the **skill and developmental access opportunities** of individuals and organisations as well as system dynamics.

Conclusion

- Increase in Freelance and Contract Work:** There has been a notable rise in freelance and contract-based employment due to remote work, providing flexibility but also contributing to job insecurity (Table 23). Kwon and Jeon (2018) found that remote work has facilitated the growth of non-traditional employment arrangements, which offer flexibility but often lack the security of permanent positions (Kwon and Jeon, 2018).
- Challenges in Job Security:** This shift towards freelance and contract work can lead to increased job insecurity. Eurofound (2023a) highlighted that while such arrangements provide flexibility, they also create uncertainties regarding job stability and access to traditional employment benefits (Eurofound, 2023a).

Aspect	Findings	References
Increase in Freelance and Contract Work	Rise in non-traditional employment, offering flexibility	Kwon and Jeon (2018), <i>Review of Public Personnel Administration</i>
Challenges in Job Security	Increased job insecurity due to lack of permanent status	Eurofound (2023), <i>The changing structure of employment in the EU</i>

Table 23: Findings and related references for freelance and contract work, and challenges in job security

- Shift to new ways of working, non-attached, project-based assignments:** Remote work supports a shift towards flexible, project-based assignments, allowing employees to manage tasks asynchronously. Roberts and Costantini (2021) noted that job roles have adapted to accommodate remote execution of tasks, leading to a more flexible approach to job responsibilities (Roberts and Costantini, 2023).
- Adapting to Remote Execution (Table 24):** This shift necessitates the adaptation of job roles to remote work environments. Eurofound (2024) emphasise the need for redefining job roles to align with remote work capabilities, supporting effective task management and collaboration in virtual settings (Eurofound, 2024).

Aspect	Findings	References
Shift to Project-Based Assignments	Supports flexibility and asynchronous task management	(Roberts and Costantini, 2023), <i>Contemporary Japan</i>

Adapting to Remote Execution	Necessitates redefinition of job roles for remote work	Eurofound (2024), <i>Working Conditions and Sustainable Work: New Forms of Employment</i>
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Table 24: Findings and related references for shift to project-based assignments and adapting remote execution

In conclusion, the changes in employment relationships in Europe between 2015 to 2021 illustrate the significance of flexibility and adaptability in the labour market. These developments reflect emerging expectations and increasing uncertainties. Effective policy implementation is crucial to addressing the challenges and capitalising on the opportunities presented by these developments. The ultimate aim should be to ensure that all workers and society can benefit from the transition to new employment models. By aligning these arrangements with the SDGs, Europe can promote fair and sustainable economic growth.

4.2.1.2 Quality of work/Job quality indicators and psycho-social factors

According to the report on ‘Psycho-social risks to workers’ well-being: Lessons from the Covid-19 pandemic’ by Eurofound in 2021, the proportion of employees in the EU with high mental well-being scores fell to 37%, compared to 45% in 2015. Women generally report lower mental well-being scores than men. Results show that in 2021, a higher percentage of men (16%) felt job insecurity, compared to women (13%). Job insecurity appears to decrease with age: the youngest workers (16–24 years old) were the most insecure, followed by the 25–34 and 35–44 year olds with the older age groups (45–55 years and 56 years or older) experiencing the lowest level of insecurity. Against such a backdrop, the report highlights the increase in the frequency of teleworking and its unevenly rapid spread across the workforce (Eurofound, 2022c). Managers, professionals, technicians and associate professionals, particularly in financial services, other services, education and public administration, are most likely to telework at least occasionally. This unequal access suggests the possibility that it may exacerbate social inequalities, and teleworking jobs might outnumber on-site jobs. It is therefore recommended that future policies consider providing flexible working options for low and medium skilled employees to improve work-life balance. Despite flexible working hours, task autonomy and career opportunities in different locations, RWAs have a greater impact on their health and well-being compared to on-site workers due to the greater psycho-social risks associated with work-life interaction and work intensity (Eurofound, 2022c).

Psycho-social factors at work

Psycho-social hazards, risk factors and relationships are well known in occupational health domain, and new aspects are introduced by the 'new normal' as well as remote working arrangements. (ILO, 2010; Leka et.al. 2011).

Job stress refers to the psychological strain or adverse psycho-physiological reactions that occur in response to various job stressors or stimuli, particularly as work patterns change within the 'efforts rewards imbalance model' (Siegrist, 2016). According to WHO, job stress occurs when job demands and pressures do not match the employee's knowledge, skills and requirements and challenge the employee's ability to cope (Leka et. al., 2011; Leka et. al., 2003). Occupational health psychology, which encompasses various applied disciplines such as health psychology, industrial/organisational psychology and occupational health, outlines the psycho-social characteristics of workplaces that lead to the development of health problems in employees and explores effective ways of introducing changes to the workplace that will benefit employees' health without negatively affecting work productivity (Landy FJ. and Conte JM., 2016). An interdisciplinary perspective and seeking solutions for addressing **remote work patterns and psycho-social factors are particularly important** in this sense **to measure and follow up and control the hazards** (EU-OSHA, 2021).

Increasing demands for change and adaptation have been triggering significant modifications in overall work organisation and management issues, particularly due to growing mutual expectations and rapid mobility of social parties as well as given the tripartite structure of employees, employers and the state. Remote workers may experience higher levels of stress, depression, and isolation, impacting their mental health and overall well-being (Buomprisco et. al., 2021). Psycho-social risks may differ between micro, mezzo and macro levels and across organisations, sectors and countries. Systematic reviews have concluded that psycho-social pressure/stress is associated with cardiovascular diseases, musculoskeletal disorders, depression, high job demands, low sense of control, and an imbalance between effort and reward are risk factors for mental and physical health problems (Stansfeld and Candy, 2006). In this context, various models to assess psycho-social risks as well as their impact on workers' health and safety and on organisations have been proposed and applied, particularly in Europe (Eurofound 2023a; EU OSHA, 2021). The European Union Council Directive 89/391/EEC, which came into effect in 1989, emphasised the need to formulate a prevention policy for psycho-social risks as well as for other risks (EU, 1989). There are ongoing developments relating to this directive (EU-

OSHA, 2021). Due to earlier developments, mental disorders have been included for the first time in the ILO List of Occupational Diseases, revised in 2010 (ILO, 2010).

Work Organisation and Job Quality

Work organisation is related to the location, environment, conditions, design and management of work as well as its socio-economic context, as outlined by (EU-OSHA, 2007). The European Job Quality Index, updated with 2021 data, shows varying performance across EU member states and highlights the positive relationship between collective representation and job quality dimensions (Figure 38) (Piasna, 2023). Job quality is linked to factors such as self-rated health, well-being, work-life balance, and perceived job security (Pawłowska, 2019). Studies indicate a decline in non-wage job quality over the past decade and slow real wage growth in the post-crisis period (Piasna, 2018). Employment status impacts job quality, with fixed-term contracts generally associated with poorer quality compared to open-ended contracts (Gevaert et. al., 2023). Researchers have developed new models for measuring intrinsic job quality (Cascales and Mira, 2021) and explored the relationship between job quality, innovation, and employment (Moroc and Bărnăuțiu, 2019). Despite policy objectives, progress in improving job quality has been slow (Foden, 2020; Eurofound, 2018a).

Figure 38: Job quality framework components (Source: Eurofound 2023a)

The European Job Quality Index measures job quality across EU member states, demonstrating the relationship between job quantity, quality, and collective representation. As stated in the definitions section, **Job quality** related data was published in the updated version from EWCTS in 2021 (Piasna, 2023). It has been shown that there was a positive relationship between collective interest representation (e.g. unions, worker representation) and various dimensions of job quality. The study indicates that unequal distribution of job quality across different segments of the European workforce 2021 (Piasna 2023). These are **physical and social environment, work intensity, skills and discretion, job tasks, organisational characteristics, working time quality arrangements, job prospects, social environment, earnings, and intrinsic job features**. These are defined as Job Quality indicators (Eurofound, 2015, 2021; Cascales Mira, 2021). The study has identified a strong positive relationship between intellectual assets (e.g. patents, trademarks, designs) and certain aspects of job quality, such as job prospects, skills, and discretion, which in turn has led to an increase in the employment rate. Job quality has been defined as the aspects that contribute to worker well-being, both in terms of material living conditions and quality of life at work. The study has examined relationships between the job quality, employment growth, and various aspects of innovation, including human resources, financial support for research, collaborative networks, and intellectual assets (Moroc, 2019). Workers with fixed-term

contracts tend to have lower job quality compared to those with open-ended contracts. Self-employed workers, except for those who are economically dependent, tend to have higher job quality compared to other employment statuses. Countries with more efficient labour markets tend to have higher job quality indicators for workers according to Geavaert, 2023. Even though it is indicated that non-standard employment contracts are associated with poorer job quality compared to open-ended contracts, there is no direct evidence proving that remote work and labour market efficiency rapidly improves job quality across employment statuses.

There is a lack of specific evidence-based models for 'job quality in remote work' due to the different theoretical models, combinations of measures and lack of comparability of follow-up measures in research. The core concepts are accepted as mutual, but the challenges and diversity of the wide range of components on this issue make interpretation difficult depending on the dimensions (e.g. employee or organisational or system level dimensions may differ in terms of arrangements as well as needs, e.g. system level practice may include participation in the labour force in another country under the specific regulations, but this under the influence of the employment relationship) (Kiran, 2021). It is important to ensure catering to all the needs among the growing number of remote workers by preventing inequalities and decent work (ILO, 2021b; United Nations, 2015). Given its supranational architecture, the EU has the potential to devise a specific model that could be applied in different circumstances, including in the candidate and near neighbourhood countries. This entails a multidisciplinary and reciprocal approach to produce evidence measures for the new RWAs-based model.

Flexible working arrangements have mixed effects, with potential benefits offset by work intensification, blurred boundaries, and professional isolation.

The main conclusion is that flexible working arrangements have both positive and negative impacts on employee well-being, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment.

The quality of working life in remote settings in association with outcome factors, including job satisfaction, productivity, engagement presenteeism is moderated by the availability of support systems (Shiri, 2022). Studies suggest that remote work can enhance job satisfaction and productivity when managed, well but can also lead to burn-out and disengagement if not properly structured (ILO, 2023; EU-OSHA, 2021; WHO/ILO, 2021).

Job Security

Research consistently shows that job insecurity has a negative impact on employee well-being and organisational outcomes. Both quantitative (fear of losing one's job) and qualitative (fear of losing valued job characteristics) job insecurity is a significant stressor (De Witte et. al., 2010; Chirumbolo et. al., 2017). Job insecurity is associated with lower mental health, job satisfaction and organisational commitment, while increasing burn-out and turnover intentions (Urbanaviciute et. al., 2021; Zhai et. al., 2023). Job insecurity, perceived as a threat to employment or job features, can have negative consequences but may also motivate under certain conditions (Klug et. al., 2024; Jiang, 2024). During the Covid-19 pandemic, remote working arrangements presented both challenges and opportunities for employees (De Vincenzi et. al., 2022). Factors that mitigate job insecurity include high skill levels, permanent contracts, organisational support and work-life balance (Rusu et. al., 2023). Conversely, job flexibility can reduce job insecurity. Negative health effects of job insecurity have been well documented since the 1930s, with 88% of studies showing negative effects on workers' health and well-being (Bohle et. al., 2001).

It is of great importance, both for individuals and for society, that the principles of inclusiveness and equal access to the world of work are guaranteed. It is well documented that a lack of engagement with the workplace has a detrimental impact on both physical and mental health. There is a robust correlation between unemployment and an elevated risk of mortality. Empirical evidence suggests that the mortality rate among the unemployed is 20% higher than that of the employed. Furthermore, unemployment is associated with a two- to three-fold increase in the likelihood of poor general and mental health, as well as increased instances of medical consultations, medication consumption, and hospital admissions (Bohle, 2001; Pelletier, 2005; O'Halloran, 2018).

Adoption of remote work practices has significantly influenced labour market dynamics, with non-routine task workers being more suited to remote work yet facing communication challenges (Elsamani and Kajikawa, 2024; Okubo, 2024).

Key aspects	A firm level finding (Bloom, 2023)
Experimental Design	1612 employees were divided into hybrid (odd birthdays) and full-time office groups (even birthdays). The trial ran from August 2021 to January 2022.
Employee Satisfaction	Hybrid working reduced attrition by 33% and improved job satisfaction. Non-managers valued hybrid more than managers.
Working Hours	Hybrid workers reduced hours by 2 hours on home days but increased them on office days and weekends. Flexibility allowed them to manage personal tasks better.
Communication	Increased messaging and video calls even when in the office, indicating a shift towards electronic communication.
Manager vs non-manager	Non-managers were more likely to volunteer and benefit from hybrid work, reporting higher productivity and lower attrition. Managers were less likely to volunteer and reported negative impacts on productivity with higher attrition.
Performance and Productivity	No significant impact on performance reviews or promotion rates. Lines of code written increased by 4.4% but was insignificant.
Work Patterns	Hybrid workers spread work outside of core hours into evenings and weekends. Business trips shifted to in-office days.
Stated Survey Insights	Employees with longer commutes and females reported higher productivity benefits from WFH. Managers' negative views on productivity improved post-experiment.
Company Decision	After a 6-month trial, the company rolled out hybrid WFH to the entire company due to positive impacts on retention and job satisfaction with no negative productivity impacts.

Table 25: Summary table of the important determinants in an intervention study from the US (Bloom et. Al., 2022)

The summary of the findings from the research reports, which points to a significant evolution in the understanding and implementation of work-from-home (WFH) practices at the firm level and national level in United States, provide important insights into the changing route as well. In Table 25, the information extracted from an intervention study, shows the focus on favourable positive outcomes of a hybrid work

model in a technology firm, highlighting reduced attrition, improved job satisfaction, and flexible work patterns. In contrast, the second updated report (summarised in Table 26) provide a broader, national perspective, illustrating that WFH has become a permanent fixture in the American work landscape, with nearly 29% of paid workdays performed from home. The second report also highlights employer and employee preferences, with a notable gap still existing between the two regarding the desired number of WFH days. Industry-specific trends, demographic differences, and the tightening of return-to-office policies further underscore the nuanced landscape of WFH.

Aspects	Findings summary from a level of A national data (Barrero, 2024)
Survey Methodology	The Survey of Working Arrangements and Attitudes (SWAA) has over 200,000 observations from US residents aged 20-64 who earned ≥ \$10K in the prior year. The survey is re-weighted to match CPS worker shares in age-sex-education-earnings cells.
Work-from-Home (WFH) Trends	About 29% of paid days in the US in June 2024 were work-from-home days. The pandemic permanently increased WFH, equivalent to almost 40 years of pre-pandemic growth.
Employer Plans	Employers plan for an average of 2.2 WFH days per week for employees able to work from home. The gap between employee desires and employer plans for WFH fluctuates near 0.5 days.
Employee Preferences	Employees want more WFH days than employers plan to offer. Employers offer fewer fully remote jobs and more fully on-site jobs than employees want.
Industry-Specific Trends	WFH is most prevalent in finance, tech, and professional and business services sectors. Information, finance, and insurance, and professional and business services have the largest share of hybrid and remote workers.
Demographic Differences	Workers in their 50s and 60s are more often fully on-site or fully remote compared to younger workers.
Return-to-Office (RTO) Policies	39% of respondents reported their employer has announced two or more RTO policies since fall 2020. Managers are slowly getting tougher at enforcing RTO policies, with an increase in verbal reprimands and negative performance reviews.

Table 26: Summary findings from a national level evaluation for the US (Barrero 2024)

Remote teams

Virtual teams are becoming increasingly common due to globalisation and technological advances (Schröder et. al., 2021). On the one hand, the ability to reach out to remote talents with ample opportunities, on the other hand, structured working conditions in anonymity require management and productivity. The links between organisational culture and employee productivity, motivation, team dynamics and health are evident and require further analysis. Studies have identified key issues including employee well-being, career development, work-life balance and organisational strategies (Aleem et. al., 2022; Pianese et. al., 2022). Remote working has implications for organisational control, requiring new approaches to align employees with organisational values and goals.

Boundaries

Remote working **changes the concept of the work environment** as well as the conditions arising from the work environment. Virtual teams, including emerging sub-types, create virtual teams and management terminologies whose boundaries and relationships have not been evaluated in terms of assessing the work environment and related elements. This may result in conceptual and functional boundaries being blurred by differences in time and space, making it difficult to achieve standardised working conditions (Spieler, 2017).

Working time, hours, preferences

As working conditions are largely defined with respect to working time and working hours, the literature has largely focused on this issue; but although the term ‘flexibility’ mostly covers non-standard employment characteristics, flexible or different working time arrangements have been evaluated in the context of remote work. However, despite the wide range of publications on the subject and the benefits of flexibility, it also brings to the fore longer working hours and difficulties in separating work and private life. Remote work results in extended working hours and challenges distinguishing work from personal life (Eurofound, 2023a). Increased control over the time devoted to work and the location from which work is performed has been identified as a key benefit of remote working in Gallup research (GALLUP, 2024). An intervention study by Nijp et. al. (2016) shows that there was no statistically significant interaction between condition and time on access to, use of, or satisfaction with work time control (WTC). In this paper, while the pattern of working hours did not change, it was reported that remote working specifically significantly increased the number of hours worked at home, from 4.55 hours to 12.97 hours per week, while commuting hours decreased significantly, from 5.79 hours to 4.84 hours per week. Despite the increased flexibility, weekly working hours rose slightly in the intervention group, from 36.06 hours to 36.56 hours per week. A notable increase in hours worked from

home and reduced control were observed among employees in the intervention group (Nijp et. al., 2016). According to the study evaluating the effects of the new modalities of working hours and location before the Covid-19 pandemic, there was a large shift from workplace office hours to home hours with reduced commuting time; yet there was no change in work schedule (weekdays, daytime) and no change in psychosocial work characteristics, work-non-work balance, stress, fatigue, work-related outcomes, and there was a medium level decrease in health score in the intervention group (Nijp et. al., 2016). This study conducted prior to the Covid-19 indicates that introducing new working arrangements did not significantly increase work time control. It is evident that the perception of the Covid-19 as well as the widespread ethical considerations of the rapidly increasing need for assessment should be carefully examined. Additionally, the sudden post-pandemic optimism may also create uncertainty about the timely perception of certain facts.

Long working hours per week (more than 48) are associated with reduced levels of reported work-life balance and increased work-family conflict, particularly if such long hours are involuntary (Fagan et. al., 2012). Indeed, Fagan et. al. reviewed many studies that have identified long hours of work as an important predictor of work-life conflict and concluded that work-family incompatibility, lower engagement in community life and lower fertility rates are all common outcomes of long working hours.

Payment styles and income

Remote work arrangements can have varying effects on income levels. While some studies suggest potential benefits, others point to inequalities. During and after the pandemic, it is reported that remote workers have had a significant income advantage over non-remote workers, but only for those who spend less time than average on housework/childcare. Women are known to be less likely to fulfil this criterion, and limited evidence has been reported on the ability of women to benefit from remote working (Tan et. al., 2022). Higher levels of remote work are associated with positive impacts on median household income (Gallardo and Whitacre, 2018).

However, shifting to remote work may exacerbate existing inequalities, favouring male, older, highly educated, and high-paid employees. Improvements in the feasibility of working from home (WFH) are likely to increase average labour income. However, probably, the benefits will not be distributed equally. It has been reported that those who are more likely to benefit from WFH are male, highly educated, highly paid and more senior workers (Bonacini et. al., 2021).

The positive aspects of remote work may help to alleviate wage growth pressures and reduce the proportion of national income accounted for by labour. In 2022, 38% of firms expanded remote working opportunities in the previous 12 months to alleviate wage growth pressures. The application of remote work practice has resulted in a reduction of wage growth by 2.0 percentage points over two years. Additionally, the same study reported that the comfort-value shock resulting from increased remote working contributed to a reduction in the labour share of national income by 1.1 percentage points (Barrero et. al., 2021; Barrero et. al., 2022; Aksoy et. al., 2022). Some research suggests a wage premium for occupations with a high homeworking rate, particularly in the highest income deciles (Bonacini et. al., 2021). Conversely, other studies report significant wage penalties for remote work, especially for women with children (Kouki, 2023). The impact of remote work on income satisfaction appears to be multifaceted. It has been reported that the effect of working from home on income satisfaction is twofold. Firstly, there is a subjective view of the importance of working from home. Secondly, there is the objective reality of whether and to what extent the person currently works from home, and to what extent this has a positive impact (Krasulja et. al., 2014).

These processes are influenced by a range of factors, including cost, economic security, job satisfaction and productivity for both employees and employers. Furthermore, there are implications associated with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Table 32 presents a framework for the utilisation of beneficial impacts and the avoidance of harmful consequences, with supporting strategies and citations from the literature.

Employee and Employer Costs

The relationship between working conditions and work-life balance, health and well-being is complex, comprising a multitude of interrelated factors. The implications observed in these areas can be categorised as follows:

- **Reduced Attrition:** Turnover rates among home-based workers decreased by 50%.
- **Improved Job Satisfaction:** Employees WFH reported higher job satisfaction and less use of sick leave.
- **Direct Cost Savings:** Companies realised cost savings in office space and overhead costs (Bloom et. al., 2015).

4.2.1.3 Satisfaction, Engagement, Productivity; Psycho-social Factors and Related Outcomes:

Several theoretical models have been developed to explain consequences related to psycho-social risk factors. Among these, Karasek's '**job demand-job control**' model is widely used, which defines the psycho-social work environment based on the interaction between job demands and the individual's control over their work. High job demands combined with low control can lead to job stress and negative health outcomes (Karasek, 1979). This model was later extended to include social support, underscoring the importance of social interactions at work (Johnson and Hall, 1988). Another influential model is the **Effort-Reward Imbalance** model, which posits that job stress arises from an imbalance between the efforts required by the job and the rewards received, including pay, job security, and recognition (Siegrist, 1996). Both intrinsic factors (individual dedication) and extrinsic factors (workplace conditions) are considered. **Psycho-social Risks in Remote and Hybrid Work:** The shift to remote and hybrid work has introduced new psycho-social risks. Remote working can affect workload as well as work pace and intensity, leading to potential conflicts in work-life balance and inequalities related to gender and caregiving responsibilities. The demand-control and effort-reward models may need to be adapted to include factors specific to remote work, such as technology load and communication load (Eurofound, 2020a).

Psycho-social factors can be addressed by, emphasising the importance of a supportive work environment, clear communication, and fair reward structures (WHO/ILO 2021; Eurofound 2023b). These strategies should be tailored to the remote work arrangements to find effective strategies for relevant stakeholders. These management strategies involve integrating health and safety measures into organisational policies and promoting a positive work culture.

Job satisfaction, motivation, and engagement

Autonomy, support, and recognition are among the variables that influence the job satisfaction of remote workers. In their study, Bell et.al. (2019) discovered a significant correlation between the job satisfaction of remote workers and the degree of autonomy and assistance provided by their organisation (Bell et. al., 2019). Golden and Gajendran (2019) highlighted the need to acknowledge and **provide career advancement** prospects to uphold **job satisfaction** in remote work settings (Golden and Gajendran, 2019).

In an experimental design study, Bloom et. al. found that WFH can reduce costs while significantly increasing productivity and employee satisfaction when appropriate solutions to challenges are provided. Increased Productivity: The study found that working from home (WFH) leads to a 13% performance increase attributed to more working hours and a quieter working environment (Bloom et.al., 2023) (concerns related to gender and caregiving responsibilities).

In another study it has been found that **motivation** is 17% lower for remote workers who didn't have a choice in where to work compared to office workers. Positive changes reported by managers include: - 49% reported lack of commute - 46.3% reported fewer meaningless meetings - 41.2% reported better concentration - 32.2% reported increased productivity - 28.4% reported more autonomy. Negative changes reported by managers include: - 36.2% reported technical difficulties - 32% reported worse concentration at home - 30.5% reported reduced team integration - 30.3% reported communication difficulties - 23.3% reported teams being less organised - 22.5% reported lower productivity. There was a 4-fold increase in the number of US workers transitioning to remote work in 2020 compared to previous years (Ozimek, 2020).

Prasad et. al.et. al. assessed autonomy, technology and teamwork and used intrinsic and extrinsic motivation subscales in a study of the impact of teleworking on motivation and performance. In their findings, the authors recommend that organisations formulate an integrated human resource policy and performance management system that addresses telework concerns, peer-employee interactions, job stress, job satisfaction and motivation are known to positively affect performance with management strategies that reduce anxiety and stress, but job stress and job satisfaction have not been found to be related to telework performance. (Prasad, 2023; Schade, 2021).

Organisational Consequences: Poor management of psycho-social risks can lead to decreased productivity, increased absenteeism, high staff turnover, and occupational accidents. These outcomes not only affect employee well-being, but also the overall efficiency and safety of the organisation (Adi and Fitriani, 2020).

emote working can improve productivity by enhancing job quality and work-life balance. The literature discusses improvements that seem higher in the short term or in response to life needs following the pandemic's confounding effects. However, negative outcomes have been reported for long-term remote workers and highly mobile remote workers (Rodríguez-Modroño and López-Igual, 2021). Volunteering is considered an important determinant and has been shown to reduce employee turnover (Mutiganda et. al., 2022). Despite findings that remote working improves work attitudes and well-being, occupational isolation

and stress are often discussed as risk for productivity, engagement, mental health and related indirect cost (Beauregard et. al., 2019). Successful remote work implementation depends on job characteristics, employee characteristics, management support and technology infrastructure; and interdisciplinary, high-quality research is needed to fully understand the effects of remote work on different job quality indicators (Beauregard et. al., 2019; Lunde et. al., 2022; Vleeshouwers et. al., 2022).

Another dimension of **productivity** is the participation of disadvantaged groups in the workforce, and the creation of a capacity to implement work from home (WFH) arrangements could offer a potential way to reduce inequalities. Particularly by reducing gender differences in willingness to commute near to work among people with disabilities and those with caregiving responsibilities (Pollak 2023; Leonardi et. al., 2024; Arnold et. al., 2024). A preferences-based experiment was conducted among German employees with the specific aim of investigating the value of working from home in the context of the pandemic and of estimating the willingness to pay to avoid commuting by gender (Nagler et. al., 2024). The findings indicated that employees were willing to relinquish, on average, 7.7% of their earnings in exchange for full-time remote working and 5.4% for two-day remote working. Their findings suggest that the willingness to pay for WFH increases significantly with the distance of commuting to work. Particularly the WFH is regarded as a benefit in that it reduces the necessity for lengthy commutes. Researchers suggest that work can reduce, but not eliminate, inequality in terms of labour force participation. Furthermore, the result remained unchanged when young children at home were considered. Considering these new findings, the researchers conclude that it may still be premature to expect the technological advancements to close the gender pay gap.

There are other studies that have reported positive effects with increased productivity and morale (Gueguen and Senik, 2023; Azarbouyeh and Jalali Naini, 2014; Hill et. al., 1998; Bosua et. al., 2013), but they also stress the complexity of the transition period and monitoring difficulties (Lunde et. al., 2022). Studies highlight the challenges of leadership and organisational support components (Edvardsson and Gardarsdottir, 2023) and how to reduce work-related distractions and increase job satisfaction (Chen et. al., 2023) for remote work.

The effectiveness of remote work depends on factors such as work nature, industry characteristics, and home settings (Anakpo et. al., 2023; Eurofound 2023a). Hybrid work models are emerging as a potential solution to maximise well-being benefits (Urien, 2023). However, productivity losses due to health conditions remain a significant concern for employers when we consider potential mental health concern (Rojanasarot et. al., 2023). Remote work adoption continues to influence labour market dynamics (Elsamani and Kajikawa, 2024).

Remote work has become a significant focus in studies on productivity and its related components. Productivity is one of the most extensively studied topics in the literature, with research providing exploratory insights into how remote work affects productivity, highlighting both positive and negative impacts.

Flexible Work Arrangements and Work-Life Balance and Satisfaction: It is clear that work-life balance association has a moderating role in flexible arrangements on satisfaction, engagement and productivity which is given in a separate title.

- SMEs adopting flexible working schedules experienced significant productivity gains, primarily due to improved employee satisfaction and work-life balance (Spector, 1986; Eurofound 2006; Grawitch, 2007; Azar, 2018; Schade et. al, 2021).
- It is highlighted that perceived flexibility positively influences productivity, work-life balance, with the degree of perceived flexibility being a significant predictor of productivity outcomes (Beckel and Fisher, 2022; Anakpo,2023).
- Coworking spaces are other determinants of remote work-related productivity and effective coworking spaces support work-life balance and enhance productivity by providing a structured work environment outside the home (Gupta et. al, 2024; Morikawa, 2024).
- The literature has revealed a strong correlation between work-life balance and productivity, suggesting that policies promoting balance can enhance productivity (Ugemuge et al., 2022; Jeffrey hill, 1998;).

Technological Support and Communication and Productivity:

- Several studies elaborate the key factors that enhance productivity in flexible work arrangements, including clear communication, supportive management, and adequate technology with psycho-social well-being (Wang S., Cheng C. 2024; Anakpo et.al, 2023).
- The importance of both formal and informal communication in maintaining productivity in remote work setting highlighted in consistency in current literature (Jin and Ikeda, 2024; EU-OSHA 2021).

Resilience and Mental Health and Productivity:

- Resilience is a key factor in maintaining productivity during remote work, particularly in managing the work-life interface (Shoman et al, 2021; Boccoli et al, 2023).

- Remote work increased mental health challenges due to additional caregiving responsibilities and the blurring of work-life boundaries, impacting productivity (Itam and Warriar, 2024; Spieler, 2017; Wyatt 2024; Buddhapriya, 2009).
- Association between mental-health and work-life balances evident for productivity; Positive mental health is associated with work-life balance, bio-psycho-social well-being, resilience, life satisfaction, positive mental health, higher job satisfaction, lower turnover intentions, job performance, job engagement and productivity (Anakpo, 2023).

Organisational Support and Employee Engagement:

- Work-life flexibility practices enhance productivity, particularly when aligned with organisational support and culture (Biea, 2023; Hill et. al, 1998; Grawitch, 2010; Kossek, 2015)
- Investing in employee skills and training to boost productivity in remote work environments (Davis, 2024; Tsang et. al., 2023).
- Preventive occupational health and safety approach is important (Capecchi, 2021; EU-OSHA, 2022c; EU-OSHA, 2024a).

Connection with Health Outcomes: Only for the purposes of theoretical connection indicated in here, a separate subtitle was on health outcomes as well as associated organisational influence has been prepared as follows: Psycho-social risks are linked to various health issues, including musculoskeletal pain, substance abuse, and mental health disorders like such as stress, anxiety, and depression. Studies have shown that high job stress is associated with cardiovascular diseases and musculoskeletal disorders due to high workload, low job control, and poor social support (Leka and Jain, 2010; Shoman et.al., 2022).

Conclusion

The implementation of remote work arrangements has the potential to exert a dual impact on productivity. From an organisational perspective, the ability to manage work schedules flexibly can lead to enhanced productivity. This is because employees value the autonomy that such flexibility grants to them. A healthy work-life balance, supported by structured environments such as coworking spaces, has also been demonstrated to enhance productivity. Furthermore, organisations that invest in adequate technological support and clear communication channels tend to observe enhanced productivity outcomes. It is essential that employees have the resilience to maintain high productivity levels, and this is best achieved when they have access to mental health resources and supportive management.

Conversely, remote work can present challenges that might negatively impact productivity. Mental health issues, which can be exacerbated by caregiving responsibilities and isolation, can hinder performance. A lack of structure in the work environment may also lead to a decrease in productivity for some employees, although this can be mitigated by utilising coworking spaces or creating a dedicated home workspace. Finally, inconsistent communication and insufficient support from management can further detract from productivity. Regular check-ins and maintaining open communication channels are essential strategies to address these issues.

4.2.1.4 Occupational Health and Safety (KPI)

Occupational Health and Safety in Remote Work

The prevalence of remote working arrangements under occupational health and safety services has increased significantly because of their considerable impact on physical and mental health and overall well-being. The interconnection between occupational health, work, and well-being has been a long-standing concern among professionals in this discipline. These practices are now receiving greater recognition from a wider range of stakeholders, including employers, healthcare providers, human resources professionals, business managers, and the public.

The traditional concept of occupational health and safety (OSH) focuses on the prevention of occupational diseases and accidents. The current, more holistic concept integrates interdisciplinary fields to promote workforce well-being in a sustainable and environmentally conscious manner.

The provision of OSH services represents an efficacious strategy for the promotion of employee well-being. There is a discernible correlation between an individual's well-being and their productivity, engagement, and satisfaction in the workplace. The concept of well-being is not contingent solely on the state of health; the quality and nature of work also exert a pivotal influence. This is inextricably linked with the context of work, the scope of employee services, and the support provided by organisational arrangements. Engaging and fulfilling work can enhance quality of life and well-being in a cyclical manner.

The findings are organised into key topic areas, including policy and guidelines, implementation and practice, eligibility and approval, monitoring and performance, flexibility and adaptability, health and safety, employee experience, and management and supervision (Table 27-31; Figure 39).

Concept	Critical Findings	Needs	Citation
Occupational Health and Safety	Integration of bio-psycho-social well-being approach. Specific work environments present health risks that can lead to occupational illnesses and injuries.	Bespoke comprehensive OSH services for remote work arrangements. Involvement of stakeholders at all levels.	(Sanders and Karmowska, 2020; Buomprisco et. al., 2021)
Remote Work-related OSH	Focus on ergonomics, health-related behaviours, and accessibility of health and counselling services. Significant economic costs due to ill health. Psycho-social factors play a pivotal role in remote work arrangements.	Policies prioritizing harm prevention and health promotion. Address gender inequalities in OSH.	(Janc et. al., 2024; EU-OSHA, 2024b; Geldart, 2022)
Rehabilitation and Return-to-work	Rehabilitation is crucial for enabling individuals with health issues to resume work. Timely interventions can prevent prolonged absenteeism and reduce the probability of job loss.	Implementation of structured interventions and support systems for rehabilitation.	(Zalmunin, 2021)

Table 27: Summary of Occupational Health and Safety aspects in RWAs.

Literature points to an increasing awareness among managers and employees of the potential negative effects of flexible work, such as work intensification and blurred work-life boundaries. In order to better manage the transition, it has been suggested to invest in improving communication technologies to help offset the professional and social isolation that can occur with remote work. Additionally formulating more formal flexible working policies will be necessary to ensure organisational justice and more equal distribution of the benefits of flexible work across all employees (Sanders and Karmowska, 2020).

Concept	Critical Findings	Needs	Citation
Digital Platform Work	Digital platforms bring new opportunities and risks for workers, including OSH challenges. The employment status of platform workers often shifts OSH risk management onto the workers.	Measures to reduce information asymmetries and power imbalances. Increased transparency and monitoring.	(EU-OSHA, 2022a; EU-OSHA, 2024c)
Psycho-social Factors	Psycho-social factors are crucial in remote work arrangements, affecting mental health and well-being. Challenges include algorithmic management and digital surveillance.	Involvement of digital platform workers in OSH risk prevention and management.	(Ahlers, 2017; Bentley et. al., 2023)

Table 28: Summary of digital platform and psycho-social aspects in RWAs

It has been reported that remote workers experiencing physical and psychological health and safety risks, are often classified as self-employed, and are forced to maintain high ratings to secure more tasks, which leads to increased psychological risks and work intensity. Furthermore, there is a need to generate evidence concerning the means of addressing gender inequalities in exposure to occupational safety and health (OSH) risks for those engaged in remote work. It is also essential to investigate the factors that contribute to an elevated risk profile for women and to identify research gaps in the understanding of cyberbullying, surveillance, and gender-specific occupational safety and health (OSH) policies in remote work (EU-OSHA, 2024b).

Remote work arrangements can have both positive and negative implications for worker health and safety, including overwork, ergonomic, and psycho-social risks (Buomprisco et. al., 2021).

There is a suggested model for designing occupational health and safety management systems that include work-from-home arrangements, with a focus on addressing psycho-social risks (Bentley et. al., 2023).

- Organisations should focus on developing leadership behaviours and management practices that provide instrumental support, build trust, use motivating language, and enable effective communication with distributed workers.
- Organisations should provide training to leaders on transformational and considerate leadership styles, with a focus on the specific safety and health challenges faced by distributed workers.
- Organisations should ensure line managers and supervisors have in-depth knowledge of the conditions and risks faced by distributed workers, which can be obtained through direct experience, shadowing, or training (Nayani et. al., 2017).

The challenges relating to occupational safety and health are particularly psycho-social hazards and risks associated with digitalisation and flexible/remote work, which highlight the importance of formulating recommendations for organisations. Proper workstation setup, work organisation, and the promotion of healthy habits are crucial for mitigating the health risks of remote work. The following measures are recommended (Janc et. al., 2024):

- Ensure that the home office workstation is set up ergonomically in accordance with best practices.
- Limit the time employees spend working at the computer or laptop and incorporate systematic active breaks.
- Promote healthy sleep habits among remote workers.
- Educate employers, occupational health professionals, and employees on the importance of proper home office preparation and organisation to protect employee health.

A study investigating the difficulties experienced in organising OSH services at the workplace for remote workers, conducted prior to the pandemic, indicates that outsourcing and home-based work arrangements are associated with poorer occupational health and safety outcomes (Quinlan and Bohle, 2008).

Other evidence-based strategies needed to be deployed to promote remote worker safety, health, and well-being, as observed mainly during and after the Covid-19 pandemic, such as implementing interventions to enhance safety leadership and motivating remote workers to engage in safe and healthy behaviours; managing role boundaries to reduce occupational safety and health risks for remote workers, and redesigning work to strengthen interpersonal interactions, interdependence, and worker initiative among remote workers (Schall and Chen, 2022).

Several policy documents emphasise the necessity of recognising the occupational safety and health (OSH) challenges inherent to digital platform work. Furthermore, the documents underscore the importance of transparency, monitoring, and enforcement of occupational safety and health (OSH) regulations, as well as the involvement of digital platform workers and their representative organisations in OSH risk prevention and management (EU-OSHA, 2022a).

Concept	Critical Findings	Needs	Citation
Policy and Legislation			
	Remote workers often face physical and psychological health risks, and there is a need for policies to address these risks. The legislative framework for OSH services varies significantly between countries.	Development of evidence-based methodological recommendations and amendments to regulatory documents.	(Esteban et. al.et. al., 2018; Ahlers, 2017)
Research and Development			
	There is a need to generate evidence on addressing gender inequalities in exposure to OSH risks for remote workers. Investigate factors contributing to elevated risk profiles for women in remote work environments.	More research on cyberbullying, surveillance, and gender-specific OSH policies.	(EU-OSHA 2024b); Schall and Chen, 2022)

Table 29: Summary of needs in concepts of policy& legislation, and research & development for RWAs

The advent of digital platforms has brought along a new set of opportunities and risks for workers. The additional occupational safety and health (OSH) risks inherent to this novel form of work differ from those associated with conventional employment. In response to these concerns, several stakeholders have introduced a variety of initiatives towards addressing the associated risks (EU-OSHA, 2024c).

To make remote work more satisfying, safe, and healthy for employees, including aspects such as allocating personal space, incorporating ergonomics, and enhancing self-regulation skills, the following measures are recommended (Geldart, 2022):

- Employers should take responsibility for ensuring the health and safety of their remote workers by providing guidance and resources to help employees establish an ergonomic home workspace.
- Employees should take an active role in advocating for their own health and safety needs when working remotely and in developing self-regulation skills to maintain productivity and focus.
- Future research should explore how employers and employees can collaborate to ensure the health and safety of remote work arrangements.

Non-standard working time arrangements, including remote work, can have significant adverse effects on worker safety, health, and well-being. 20-25% of workers in developed countries have non-standard working hours. The costs of adverse consequences of non-standard work schedules in developed countries are estimated to be in the hundreds of billions of dollars annually. The economic and social costs of non-standard work hours may be even greater in developing countries as compared to developed countries (Wong et. al., 2019).

As remote work poses challenges for ensuring occupational health and safety, labour laws and regulations need to be adapted to this new work arrangement (Esteban et. al., 2018).

While remote work has become more prevalent, it is not without potential negative health and well-being outcomes for employees, including stress, burn-out, blurred work-life boundaries, and feelings of isolation (Lagutina, 2022).

While home-office work has many benefits, there are significant challenges in ensuring proper occupational health and safety protections and labour rights for remote workers. The paper states that legally, remote workers have the same labour rights as on-site workers, but the 'big question is how to put all these guidelines into practice' and guarantee these rights (Esteban et. al., 2018).

Digitisation and flexible/remote work arrangements have both benefits and risks for occupational health and safety, and that more research and policy attention is needed to address the challenges posed by these new developments in the workplace (Ahlers, 2017).

The effects of non-standard work schedules, such as shift work, on workers, organisations, and communities are complex, and the existing literature does not provide clear, unequivocal advice regarding the design and regulation of working time arrangements. The available research is often limited by the circumstances of data collection and can be biased by pre-conceived perspectives, and the literature on working time arrangements is 'sporadic and mixed', which enables stakeholders to selectively use findings to support opposing views (Wong et. al., 2019).

Remote and hybrid work offer benefits such as flexibility and work-life balance, but also challenges such as lost comradery and isolation that require employers to provide support and re-design workplaces. The main conclusion of this paper is that the widespread adoption of remote and hybrid work due to the Covid-19 has led to both benefits and challenges for office workers, and that organisations will need to re-design both physical and digital workplaces to fit the new and emergent needs of employees in hybrid work models (Babapour Chafi et. al., 2021).

Remote work poses potential risks for employee occupational health, entailing organisational strategies for prevention and early detection. The main conclusion of the paper is that the growing popularity of remote work requires a comparative assessment of the medical and social risk factors for remote workers, amendments to regulatory documents, as well as the development of evidence-based methodological recommendations for employers to enable early detection of employees with contraindications to remote work. Addressing the challenges of early detection of mental and physical health issues among freelance workers (Zalmunin, 2021).

According to EU-OSHA 2022 report findings, there are key regulatory gaps concerning occupational safety and health (OSH) in 'digital platform work', and that there are few regulations, policies, strategies, programmes, initiatives and actions directly targeting OSH issues in digital platform work. The report points to unclear employment status and classification of platform workers as self-employed, which lays the responsibility of OSH risk prevention and management onto the workers themselves. Employers may notify the challenges with algorithmic management and digital surveillance, which can have significant negative impacts on the physical and mental health of platform workers. The report also notes that professional isolation, work-life conflicts, and lack of social support can lead to increased stress, burn-out, and other mental health issues for platform workers.

The key recommendations from EU-OSHA reports are as follows:

- Introduce measures to reduce information asymmetries and power imbalances between platforms and workers, such as by clarifying employment status and increasing algorithmic transparency.
- Raise awareness about the importance of OSH among authorities, platforms, and workers.
- Increase transparency to facilitate the work of OSH actors, such as by imposing reporting obligations on platforms.
- Strengthen monitoring and enforcement of OSH regulations by ensuring authorities have the necessary knowledge, means and resources.
- Involve digital platform workers and their representatives in OSH risk prevention and management.

Conclusions for OSH

1. Impact on Well-being and Productivity

- The provision of OSH services promotes employee well-being, with a clear correlation between well-being and productivity, engagement, and job satisfaction.
- Well-being is influenced not only by health but also by work quality, employee services, and organisational support.
- Engaging and fulfilling work can enhance quality of life and well-being.

2. Flexible Working Arrangements

- Flexible work has mixed effects, with benefits offset by work intensification, blurred boundaries, and professional isolation.
- Positive impacts are mediated by leadership styles and management approaches.
- Negative impacts stem from overwork due to blurred work-home boundaries.

3. Implementation and Challenges

Flexible working arrangements have both positive and negative impacts on employee well-being, job satisfaction, and organisational commitment. These impacts are influenced by the leadership styles and management approaches employed by line managers, and the challenges of work intensification and blurred boundaries.

Recommendations

- Increase awareness among managers and employees about the potential negative effects of flexible work.
- Invest in improving communication technologies to offset professional and social isolation.

- Develop formal flexible working policies to ensure organisational justice and equitable distribution of benefits.

These findings highlight the multifaceted impacts of remote and hybrid working conditions, pointing to the need for comprehensive policies and practices to ensure the health, safety, and well-being of workers in these new arrangements.

It may be the case that another aspect of remote arrangements plays a pivotal role during the rehabilitation and return-to-work period. The rehabilitation process has great significance in enabling individuals with health issues to resume their work activities. The implementation of timely and suitable interventions can prevent prolonged absenteeism and facilitate recuperation, thereby maintaining the individual's affiliation with the workplace and reducing the probability of job loss.

The evidence is overwhelming in its support of the assertion that appropriate, well-structured pre-emptive and preventive Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) services are beneficial to health and well-being. For individuals with health issues, including prevalent conditions such as musculoskeletal disorders and mental health concerns, reintegration into suitable employment can prove therapeutically and socially advantageous.

The comprehensive range of remote services for employees, which encompasses awareness, improvement of remote working literacy and hazard communication, as well as emergency preparedness in occupational health, in addition to cultural and climate actions, will facilitate the enhanced achievement of mutual core values enshrined in the international humanitarian legal instruments (United Nations 2015, ILO, 2010, 2021a, 2021b, 2022, 2023, 2024; EU, 1998). It is thus suggested that occupational health policies should prioritise the prevention of harm and the promotion of health through work, with a particular emphasis on the significance of rehabilitation and the provision of accommodating work environments. This approach yields benefits not only for individuals but also for the broader economic and social spheres, thereby underscoring the intrinsic link between work, health, and well-being on a global scale.

Future Directions

The integrated approach to occupational health now integrates biology, psychology, and sociology to promote workforce well-being in a sustainable manner. This approach considers specific health risks in various occupations, including remote work, which often involves ergonomic issues and the need for accessible health and counselling services.

Comprehensive OSH Services

- Provision of comprehensive remote services for employees, including hazard communication and emergency preparedness.
- Addressing psycho-social risks with structured OSH management systems.
- Enhancing safety leadership and communication to support remote workers.

Aspect	Positive	Negative
Occupational Health & Safety	Reduced commuting risks, hazards exposure -workplace related	Ergonomic issues, mental health concerns, infections, hazards in the remote environment, hazard communication and management, connectedness
Quality of Working Life	Psycho-social hazards buffer with flexibility related increased job satisfaction, autonomy	Social isolation, risk of burnout, values creation, organisational culture dynamics related erosion, non-attached culture related difficulties
Work-Home Interface	Improved work-life balance	Blurred boundaries, constant connectivity, lack of information flow, adaptation

Table 30: Positive and negative aspects of RWAs regarding OSH, quality of working life and work-home interface

The positive impacts are mediated by the leadership styles and management approaches employed by line managers while the negative impacts are primarily stemming from work intensification and blurred work-home related RWAs.

Conclusion for OSH

The shift towards remote working arrangements has significantly altered traditional workplace dynamics, impacting occupational health and safety in various ways. The evidence supports the assertion that well-structured pre-emptive and preventive OSH services are beneficial to health and well-being. Occupational

health policies should prioritise harm prevention and health promotion through work, emphasising rehabilitation and accommodating work environments. This approach benefits individuals and the broader economic and social spheres, underscoring the intrinsic link between work, health, and well-being on a global scale (EU-OSHA, 2021, WHO/ILO, 2021; Wütschert et. al., 2022).

Report	Important findings	Recommendations
European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (2022). 'Hybrid work and occupational safety and health (OSH): perspectives and recommendations'		
EU OSHA 2022	- Ergonomics: Many remote workers lack proper ergonomic setups, leading to musculoskeletal disorders.	- Ergonomic Assessments: Provide remote workers with ergonomic assessments and appropriate equipment.
	- Mental Health: Hybrid work can increase stress and mental health issues due to blurred boundaries between work and personal life.	- Mental Health Support: Implement mental health support programmes and ensure access to professional help.
	- Work-Life Balance: Flexible working arrangements are critical for maintaining a healthy work-life balance but can be challenging to implement effectively.	- Clear Policies: Develop clear policies that define work hours and expectations to help maintain work-life balance.
Lenaerts, K., Waeyaert, W., Gillis, D., Smits, I., and Hauben, H. (2022). 'Digital platform work and occupational safety and health: overview of regulation, policies, practices and research', European Agency for Safety and Health at Work.(EU-OSHA, 2022a)		
EU-OSHA, 2022a	- Algorithmic Management: The use of algorithms for task management can cause stress and job insecurity among workers.	- Regulation Updates: Update regulations to address the unique challenges of digital platform work, including algorithmic management.
	- Job Security: Workers in digital platform jobs often face a lack of job security and benefits.	- Job Security Measures: Implement measures to improve job security and access to benefits for digital platform workers.
	- OSH Risks: There are significant OSH risks, including mental health issues, stress, and lack of ergonomic support.	- OSH Standards: Establish OSH standards specifically tailored to the needs of digital platform workers.
European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (2021). 'Risks associated with remote programming work organised through digital labour platforms'		
EU OSHA 2021	- Mental Health Issues: Remote programming work can lead to isolation, stress, and other mental health issues.	- Mental Health Interventions: Provide access to mental health resources and support networks.
	- Ergonomic Challenges: Poor ergonomic setups in home offices can lead to long-term health problems.	- Ergonomic Training: Offer training and resources to improve ergonomic practices in home office setups.

- Social Isolation: The lack of social interaction can cause feelings of loneliness and disconnection.

- Community Building: Facilitate online communities and regular check-ins to reduce social isolation.

Table 31: Summary of OSH-related key findings and recommendations in reports

Figure 39: Summary of the key elements of OSH-related issues indicated in the EU-OSHA reports on RWAs

4.2.2 Potential effects of RWAs on Living Conditions

This section explores literature and provides information on **RQ3**: how RWAs could shape living conditions (e.g. working from home, work location, and household dynamics) to understand the potential effects of Remote Working Arrangements (RWAs) on living environments as well as work-from-home scenarios. This part places special emphasis on various aspects of living conditions on the objectives (i, ii, iii, iv), investigating these in connection with the broader context of the 'life-to-work-interface'. Subtitles highlight potential effects of RWAs on Living conditions by presenting findings from related literature.

4.2.1.1 Environmental, Occupational and Public Health and living conditions (KPI)

This section incorporates additional literature review to better understand the environmental challenges related to living conditions and health aspects. The findings have revealed that primary **ecologically relevant consequences of remote work are energy consumption, commuting and transportation distances, as well as greenhouse gas and carbon emissions**. Of the twelve identified reviewed articles, eight examine the effects of remote work on energy consumption, while five focus on its impact on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. A pilot study conducted in Ottawa, Canada, demonstrated that substituting remote work for unsustainable commuting practices resulted in a reduction in both greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption (Simon & O'Brien, 2023). O'Brien and Aliabadi (2020) report that remote work leads to reduced overall energy consumption, yet they also emphasise that this benefit is negated by increased rebound energy use for non-work-related activities (O'Brien and Aliabadi, 2020). Tenailleau et al. (2021) demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in transportation-related emissions for every 1% increase in remote work (Tenailleau et al.), 2021, as shown in their study conducted in France, while a contrasting case study in Northern Italy revealed a 15% increase in energy consumption in a fully remote work setting (Cattani et al., 2024).

Sirati et al. (2024) demonstrated that **home energy consumption increased** by 10% when 100% of work was conducted remotely (Sirati et al., 2024). A study conducted by using data from the UK Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) database over the period 2008 to 2022 revealed a reduction in emissions of between 3% and 17% for periods of between three and five days spent working from home (Shi et al., 2023). A systematic review by Hook et al. (2020) on the impact of remote work on energy use identified 39 articles that reported a reduction in energy consumption, **while eight articles indicated either a negative or neutral effect** (Hook et al., 2020). This systematic review of the energy impacts of teleworking in 2020 explored **energy savings from**

reduced commuting time and indirect impacts on energy consumption associated with changes in non-work travel and household energy consumption. They synthesised the results of 39 studies from a comprehensive search of 9000 published papers to identify the conditions under which teleworking leads to a net reduction in economy-wide energy consumption and the circumstances under which the benefits may outweigh the unintended effects. They found that eight studies reported that teleworking increased energy consumption or was neutral, while 26 reported that teleworking decreased energy consumption. **It is stated that the non-standardisation of the studies is a limitation, and that the savings identified in the study, include reduced commuting distances and potentially lower office energy consumption,** whereas it has not been possible to make assessments involving non-work travel or home energy consumption. Despite the general positive perception of energy savings, **they point to the issue of uncertainty** and maintain that the available evidence suggests that economy-wide energy savings may be negative or non-existent in many cases.

Available evidence indicates that there are positive effects of remote working on environmental emissions and energy savings due to reduced commuting and office energy use (Caulfield and Charly, 2022). Nevertheless, it cannot be assumed that energy or emission reductions will necessarily occur. The extent to which remote work can reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions is contingent upon many factors, including consumption habits that influence domestic energy consumption, purchasing behaviours, transportation options, and the distance to work of the remote workers (Simon and O'Brien, 2023, Zhang et al., 2023). Considering the socio-economic implications of emissions reduction and remote work is also important. In their recent study, Yongting and Haoying highlight the challenges faced by low-income individuals in reducing their emissions, given the limited remote work options available to them (Zhang et al., 2023).

A further **significant consequence of remote work and living condition related topic is the effect on transportation requirements.** Remote work may result in a reduced need for transportation. Cattani et al. (2023) and Elldér (2020) report a reduction in travel distance and commuting with the introduction of remote work (Elldér, 2022, Cattani et al., 2024). The advent of remote work during the pandemic may have resulted in a shift in commuting patterns. In the US, the adoption of remote working practices has been associated with a reduction in the number of transit trips made (Zhang et al., 2023). In a further US-based case study, a reduction of 15 km per week of travel for workers was calculated (Obeid et al., 2024). In Switzerland, remote workers are observed to engage in more walking and cycling (Wöhner, 2023). Although work-related

passenger car use may have decreased, non-work-related travel may increase. A case study conducted in Paris examined the rebound effect of non-work-related travel. It is estimated that the rebound effect negates up to 68% of gains in travel distance and up to 85% of travel time savings (Kiko et al., 2023).

Aspect	Positive SDG Alignment	Negative SDG Alignment	Strategies to Mitigate Negative Impacts
Housing	SDG 11: Promotes sustainable living, SDG 10: Ensures fair housing	SDG 11: Urban sprawl, SDG 1: Inequities in housing affordability	Provide housing support, promote sustainable housing designs
Utilities	SDG 7: Ensures reliable utilities, SDG 12: Encourages efficient resource use	SDG 7: Increased home energy use, SDG 12: Potential for increased waste	Encourage energy efficiency, promote sustainable utility management
Household Dynamics	SDG 5: Promotes equitable responsibilities, SDG 10: Ensures fair involvement	SDG 5: Exacerbates gender inequalities, SDG 3: Increases household stress	Promote equitable sharing of responsibilities, provide mental health support
Work scheduling at home/ Personal Time Management	SDG 3: Enhances well-being, SDG 8: Promotes productive use of personal time	SDG 3: Risk of burnout from poor time management, SDG 8: Reduces productivity	Encourage effective time management, implement regular breaks, work scheduling improvements
Living Expenses	SDG 1: Reduces living expenses, SDG 8: Contributes to financial stability	SDG 7: Increased utility costs, SDG 10: Creates inequalities in expenses	Provide financial support, promote efficient home office setups
Environmental Impact	SDG 13: Reduces carbon footprint, SDG 11: Promotes sustainable practices	SDG 7: Increased energy use at home, SDG 12: Potential for increased waste	Promote sustainable practices, support use of renewable energy
Network and Strong connections SDG:17	SDG 17: Establishment of collaborative partnerships, pooling resources that can be shared in RWAs and promoting common goals, stakeholder collaboration for enabling opportunities in living spaces through stakeholder collaboration.	SDG 17: Lack of partnership related Risk of uneven access to networks and resources, leading to disparities	Foster inclusive networks, ensure equitable access to resources, promote strong partnerships that support all aspects of sustainable development

Table 32: SDG alignment of living conditions related concepts in RWAs

It is estimated that on-site workers have been diminished by 10% as compared to the pre--pandemic period (2020 to 2022) (Zhang et al., 2023). This corresponds to an approximately 10% reduction in transportation-

driven Green House Gas (GHG) emissions. Therefore, the evidence suggests that a rapid and large-scale reduction of private car use effectively reduces GHG emissions and is necessary (Arnz et al., 2024, Winkler et al., 2023). Although dependent on remote workers' transportation availability and travel habits, remote working generally seems to contribute to **travel-related GHG emissions by reducing passenger car use**.

The need to reduce private car use is also in line with the studies on the effect of growth-based macro-economic systems **on ecology an environmental/planetary/public health**. It is emphasised that the economy's growth makes it much more difficult to keep anthropogenic GHG emissions within planetary boundaries (Haberl et al., 2020). Therefore, degrowing the countries' economies that have already exceeded their share of planetary boundaries, namely global north countries, is essential (Cuny and Parrique, 2023; Hickel and Kallis, 2020; Hickel et al., 2022). Eventually, sufficiency and need-based macroeconomic models are needed to ensure safe operating space. Remote working arrangements could be in alignment with these macroeconomic models (please see the SDG alignment of living conditions related concepts in RWAs in Table 3232).

4.2.1.2 Living Location

This section addresses the relationship between work and home locations under the **environmental/planetary/public health influence, work-life balance, health and well-being**, as well as the potential associated characteristics of urban and rural areas with respect to the role of remote working in facilitating transition and adaptation to different living conditions. The acceptability of RWAs is contingent upon its capacity to address gender disparities and work-related organisational aspects in labour force participation. One potential avenue for addressing the discrepancy in labour force participation rates among different population groups is through remote working (Eurofound 2018b; 2021a; OECD, 2021) For example, it is essential to explore the hierarchical barriers that exist in both rural and urban contexts, as well as the individual, occupational, and sectoral factors that influence these barriers. To analyse the impact of RWAs on living conditions, it is first necessary to conduct research that provides a detailed investigation of the dimensions related to these conditions. While there are studies exploring different aspects of the associations in living conditions, the Covid-19 pandemic implications must also be considered, as it has introduced confounding factors that affect the existing literature. A comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting living conditions requires consideration of both obstacles and facilitating factors. The relationship between

working life and living conditions interconnected and may be cyclical, making it crucial to examine key dimensions such as links associated with the acceptability of remote working, and related arrangements, the variables influencing this acceptability, and the differences in various settings. Furthermore, it is important to consider technological developments and disruptions, the use of living space, environmental, neighbourhood characteristic, rural and urban requirements, regional practicality and cross- regional connections, social behaviour, and how these factors interact to impact health and lifestyles. To analyse the impact of RWAs on living conditions, it is first necessary to conduct research to monitor interventions that provide detailed evidence. While there are studies examining labour force participation rates in relation to various socio-demographic and regional characteristics, there is also a need to investigate broader variables and correlates of change. The subtitles aim to provide current literature-based insight for further research areas as follows:

Differences in the acceptability and use of remote work: This leads to the question of whether remote working is perceived as an acceptable and utilised form of work practice. Even though there should be different layers of analysis, the findings from the accessed literature revealed that the focus is mostly on the individual level. The discrepancy between the acceptability and actual utilisation of remote working is more pronounced among women than men in both rural and urban contexts (Nagler et al., 2024; Heatley,. In the United States of America, approximately 48% of women are technically capable of remote working, whereas only 20% have engaged in this practice. Similarly, in the European Union, 45% of women are technically capable of remote work, yet only 11% have engaged in it (Touzet, 2023).

Factors related to occupation, sector and professional position: It is also important to consider factors related to occupation, sector and professional position, organisational arrangements and readiness. It can be observed that although professions usually occupied by women tend to be more conducive to remote work, the actual rates of remote work among women remain relatively low. To illustrate, 87% of those employed in the United States of America in 'management, business and finance' and 64% of those in 'professional and related' roles are engaged in remote work. Although the concept is widely applicable, the actual rates of remote work are approximately 30% and 10%, respectively (Touzet, 2023).

The pandemic is a 'confounding factor': It is of great importance to examine the influence of the pandemic on the labour market, particularly in view of the surge in home-based work due to the spread of the Covid-19, which has been diagnosed markedly higher among women. The proportion of women engaged in remote work

has increased significantly, contributing to a narrowing of the gender gap. This increase has been more pronounced in urban areas, where the prevalence of remote working is greater (OECD, 2023; Touzet, 2023).

Gender differences in propensity to work from home: The following section presents the gender-specific preferences regarding home-based work. It has been clear that prior to the pandemic, the majority of OECD countries demonstrated a greater proclivity for men than women engaging in regular remote work. However, the post-pandemic data indicate that childcare remains a significant challenge, while there has been a notable increase in the prevalence of women working remotely in sectors where remote work was previously less common. The concentration of women in this area has resulted in an increase in their participation in remote work (OECD, 2023; Touzet, 2023).

Individual resources, capacity, awareness and skill requirements: It is evident that there is a need to facilitate greater accessibility to telecommuting, which would allow more people to benefit from this flexible working arrangement. Nevertheless, women continue to encounter significant obstacles in this regard. These challenges are attributed to the intersection of gender and occupational roles and hierarchical positions, which often result in women facing additional barriers to remote working. The practical integration of remote working by women in both rural and urban areas is impeded by several factors (Paul, 2022; OECD, 2023)

Infrastructural requirements for working conditions and living conditions for all: In order to address these inequalities, it is necessary to promote flexible working arrangements that encourage remote working across all demographic groups and to provide support for remote working in general. It is therefore evident that policies aimed at reducing gender and rural-urban inequalities in remote working are required (OECD, 2021; OECD, 2023). The literature on the spatial characteristics of living settings concluded that the quality of the home workstation and the surrounding neighbourhood significantly impact work productivity (Wheatley, 2021).

Home-work environment (KPI)

A comprehensive umbrella review evaluated the experiences of individuals who work from home and identified various factors that may influence their personal perceptions of homeworking (Wütschert et al., 2022). These factors **included barriers, enablers, advantages, and disadvantages. The results, based on three main categories (working environment, personal impact and health)**, were summarised under 19 themes. Researchers emphasised the importance of considering **individual and contextual circumstances when**

researching working from home. This review establishes the importance of retaining flexibility while homeworking for employees, managers and organisations. It highlights the impracticality of a one-size-fits-all approach to working from home, given the significant variations in individual and contextual circumstances (Hall et al., 2024).

Digital platform jobs present both opportunities and risks for workers with additional OSH risks as compared to traditional work (EU-OSHA, 2022b; EU-OSHA, 2022a). Remote programmers, who are often classified as self-employed, face various physical and psychological health and safety risks (EU-OSHA, 2022b).

There is need for understanding OSH challenges in digital platform jobs to ensure transparency monitoring and enforcement of OSH regulations (EU-OSHA, 2023b; EU-OSHA, 2022a; EU-OSHA, 2024b). Marked gender inequalities in terms of exposure to OSH risks among remote workers further highlight the factors contributing to higher risks for women.

The organisation of the working time is important for **a work-from-home design that promotes health** Key considerations for health promoting work from home include ergonomic workstation design, proper organisation of working time, and separation of work and private life. Maintaining proper ergonomic practices and creating well-designed workstations are crucial in preventing musculoskeletal diseases while improving the productivity of individuals working remotely.

Multiple studies have emphasised the important benefits of ergonomic solutions. In a reviewed study, researchers have synthesised the ergonomic risk factors and musculoskeletal disorders in the remote workplace by indicating limitation about the comparison of remote- and office workers ergonomics related research, and they have identified nine ergonomic risk factors, of which the most frequently studied were poor posture, poor working environment, psycho-social risk factors, poor workspace design and excessive workload. These factors were identified as the most predominant at the remote work settings.

The least studied factors at the remote workstation were identified as the power zone, noise, ocio-demographics and repetitive motion. The impact of these factors on the physical, mental and psycho-social aspects of the workers was also examined, with the findings indicating a correlation between these factors and lower back and upper back pain, as well as neck pain. The systematic review highlights the importance of health in employee-specific design and provides guidance for future research in this area. The researchers emphasise that cognitive ergonomic assessments should be considered in the context of decent work as well as physical and cognitive ergonomic assessments in relation to sociodemographic correlates and well-being (Wodajenehet.al.,2022; de Macêdo et al., 2020; Janc et al., 2024). It has been demonstrated that

implementing ergonomic workspace design significantly affected employee health and productivity and provided integrated information that ergonomic training helps decrease musculoskeletal diseases (de Macêdo et al., 2020; Janc et al., 2024, Milaković et al., 2023, Wütschert et al., 2022). Ergonomics and organisational aspects are crucial in establishing an appropriate working environment, and the failure to implement ergonomic interventions or insufficient ergonomic resources contribute to the increase in musculoskeletal problems (Milaković et al., 2023).

Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, the decision to work remotely largely depended on an individual's living conditions outside the traditional office environment. Iscan and Naktiyok (2005) found that remote work is less attractive for employees whose homebases do not have a proper office setup (Iscan and Naktiyok, 2005). Many homes may not have the extra space needed to create a separate workspace, resulting in an inadequate separation between living and working spaces. In addition, successful remote work requires access to the necessary infrastructure, such as high-speed internet, appropriate software and ergonomic furniture, employees with better-equipped offices at work than at home were less likely to choose to remote work when given the option. Another study found that the adaptation and social impact of remote working is governed by the social network of the organisation as well (Scott et al., 2012).

The workspace in living environment's quality, encompassing factors such as accessible space and seclusion, profoundly influences remote workers' capacity to focus and perform efficiently. According to the literature, well-organised living environment enhances efficiency in remote work by offering an appropriate workspace (Ugemuge et al., 2022; Reece et al., 2021). The researchers stressed the significance of privacy in remote settings for upholding productivity.

Ergonomics in living conditions, multifaceted such as physical, cognitive, non-routine work-related living conditions including workstation/work space settings, separation, proper equipment, related living arrangements linked remote work to musculoskeletal and eye problems and mixed results in association with well-being, emphasising the importance of work settings on physical and mental health (Wechsler et al., 2024; de Macêdo et al., 2020, Mekonnen et al., 2019, Milaković et al., 2023). Another aspect considered has been leisure time arrangements; and it is indicated that remote work allows for more leisure and family time, and it can also lead to fewer opportunities for coworker interaction, potentially affecting Davis et al. 2020 highlighted the significance of living environment design on productivity and called for allocating resources

towards the development of efficient workspaces (Davis et al., 2020). work performance and mental health in a non-routine scheduled work (Okubo, 2024).

4.2.3 Potential effects of RWAs on Work-Life Balance

In the preceding two chapters, the elements of work-life balance, including its antecedents, working and living conditions, and related factors have been analysed. This analysis is followed by a conceptual evaluation and a discussion of well-being and its associated outcomes. The following section examines the conceptual transition effects of RWAs in supporting the work-life interface, with the aim of promoting harmony by addressing **RQ4** (on point (vi) of the proposal): how RWAs could impact the balance between professional and personal life. Specifically, it examines the role of RWAs in enhancing well-being by supporting the work-life interface. In this context, work-life balance is considered a “buffer” with an ‘interface’ that influences health and well-being, as well as work-related outcomes such as satisfaction, motivation and productivity.

4.2.3.1 Work-Home Interface and Harmony (KPI)

The work-home interface is crucial in determining the success of remote work arrangements. Effective management of this interface can lead to better work-life balance and increased job satisfaction. However, challenges such as constant connectivity and lack of clear boundaries can negatively impact personal life and mental health (ILO, 2021a; UN News, 2023). Promoting high standards in working conditions, including the areas of ‘health and well-being at work’ are defined as key priority areas by the EU. The EU Directive on measures to improve safety and health at work seeks to protect workers in their own place of work and promote workers’ rights in this area: Remote working frequently blurs the boundaries between professional and personal life, impacting mental well-being and the equilibrium between work and personal life. Shockley et. al. identified effective ways to enhance work-life balance¹⁴, including establishing explicit boundaries and implementing flexible schedules as a supportive interface (Shockley et. al., 2021). Another study examined the impact of remote working on individuals' ability to balance work and personal responsibilities and analysed the link between work and home life. According to these findings, varying experiences of the participants suggest that the interface between home and work can be constructed as a buffer. Some reported a loss of control over their working hours due to the pervasive presence of technology at home, resulting in longer

¹⁴ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/work-life-balance>.

working hours, reduced social interaction and a negative impact on work-life balance. In contrast, others valued the ability to regulate their work involvement by determining when to deal with work tasks, which increased their efficiency and productivity (Pensar and Rousi, 2023).

Due to evolving work structures, it is important to recognise that the intersectionality of personal life and professional duties are increasingly blurred. Several factors influence an employee's performance, necessitating identification. Variations in home environments, such as family size, marital status, access to amenities such as electricity and Wi-Fi, and the presence of distractions, have varying implications on remote working conditions for different individuals within a company. This variation can lead to conflicts during transitions between work and home, particularly when an individual's primary needs are not met. The number of hours worked per week and family type have a significant impact on both work-to-home conflict (WTHC) and home-to-work conflict (HTWC) for employees working from home. Employees with varying core needs (achievement, affiliation, power) have different experiences with respect to WTHC and HTWC, with high achievement need linked to more WTHC, high affiliation need linked to more HTWC, and higher power need linked to fewer WTHC and HTWC. Organisations need to understand how individuals' personalities and key needs interact with the work-from-home environment in an effort to render remote work more effective and harmonised (Bhattacharya and Mittal, 2020).

Figure 40: Key influences on work and non-work well-being, adapted from Standen et. al. (1999)

4.2.3.2 Work-life balance conceptual framework (KPI)

The work-life balance presents the interface between work-supported working life and life-supported working life as two feeding and balancing domains. However, this framework treats remote work as a multidimensional concept and distinguishes the impact of the home environment from organisational distance.

The concept of work-life balance as discussed by Standen et. al., (1999) and based on Warr's 1987 model, highlights the harmonious integration of both work and non-work domains. It emphasises the interaction between the work-organisational domain and the work-family domain, underlining the importance of achieving balance between these areas (Standen et. al., 1999). This model points to the importance of permeability and mutual support between work and life boundaries. It also recommends further research using existing models and literature to explore the interaction between work and family life, emphasising spillover effects on direct well-being in 1999 (Figure 40 summarises this model). In subsequent years, with

technological advances and the development of the new world of work in the post-pandemic era, the framework of the model has retained its multidimensional nature with a variety of additional potential factors.

The shift from working in the office to working from home, and the consequent reduction in commuting time in the work-life balance, while maintaining a predominantly weekday and daytime working pattern, leads to uncertainty about the permeable boundaries with respect to the utilisation of time available in work-life balance.

Despite the spatial flexibility of remote working, the findings of research indicate that basic job characteristics such as job autonomy, job demands and social support remain constant and that control over working time is largely unaffected, suggesting the need for further research in this area (Nijp et. al., 2016).

The same research also shows that new ways of working can be implemented without negatively affecting employees' work-life balance, well-being or work-related outcomes (Nijp et. al., 2016).

The interactions between work and life should be examined considering the parameters associated with each working and living condition. The rapid changes in remote working are now leading to theoretical discussions about the possible effects of remote working on health and life, as well as on living conditions, location and work-life balance. The models in the literature emphasise the role of the implementation of New Ways of Working (NWWF), characterised by flexible working hours and locations supported by ICT (Nijp et. al., 2016). In particular, how the work-home interface and the home-work interface can be transformed into a more supportive domain in complex settings requires further research involving needs assessment as well as an analysis of existing circumstances.

Understanding the challenges and needs is crucial for devising strategies for empowering companies towards the sustainability of enterprises, while considering the health and well-being of employees in the future of work.

Existing literature has analysed work-life balance, work-life conflict, work-family balance and gender dimensions as a common domain of working and living conditions, focusing on potential impacts on work-life balance, imbalance and health, well-being and productivity outcomes. In particular, the role of possible work-life balance relationships is crucial in shaping regulations and their impact on new models (Beckel and Fisher, 2022; EU-OSHA- 2021).

It is widely acknowledged that the work-life balance antecedent encompasses a range of demographic characteristics, including age, gender, geographical location, physical environment and industry/occupation. Furthermore, job characteristics include remote work preferences, individual differences, personality traits, and boundary-related requirements (Mustafa et. al., 2012; Spieler et. al., 2017; Owusu, 2024). Economic factors, including commuting time, economic resources, ergonomic resources (such as training, information and communication technology), and organisational factors facilitate remote work. These factors also exert an influence on the formality of remote work, related procedures, legislation, and so forth. These factors have the potential to affect several different areas, including health, health behaviours, social and family life, and work-related outcomes. These areas are all intricately interlinked with one another, with factors such as satisfaction, absenteeism, and presenteeism being particularly relevant in this context (Shimura et. al., 2021; Rojanasarot et. al.2023). Some of the job characteristics and services, such as social support, social isolation, and relationship quality, are defined as mediators. The literature has been expanded to include new dimensions, such as caregiving responsibilities, dependencies, talent acquisition, infrastructure, the rural and urban divide, and economic and environmental issues. These are investigated in order to identify deficiencies and requirements for future developments that are in line with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015).

When assessing the potential impact of RWAs on work-life balance, work-life balance related RWAs can be viewed as a prismatic structure, with mediating and moderating elements that influence both working life and living conditions, interacting in a cyclical manner. The prismatic role of work-life balance in these relationships is schematised in Figure 41.

Future challenges will be based around new dimensions as well as recent transitions of all these factors in this prismatic transformation (Figure 41). In particular, the literature on work-life balance emphasises that remote work offers employees more flexibility and freedom, increases commitment and satisfaction, and reduces absenteeism. However, there is increasing recognition of the negative consequences, such as isolation, blurring of the boundaries between work and private life, poor physical working conditions and reduced employee motivation and commitment.

Figure 41: Conceptual model showing the antecedents and outcomes including the moderators and mediators for a RWAs with respect to work-life balance (Adapted from Beckel and Fisher 2022).

The benefits of RAWs, in relation to work-life balance, include access to opportunities for employers to enhance their work-life balance thanks to a wider pool of employees in different time zones in remote locations, lower cost of living for employees and employers depending on location, and property costs due to different conditions (Nijp et. al., 2016,).

A holistic understanding of the current situation and needs in each aspect of the interfaces between work and living conditions (work-to-home, home-to-work), in terms of antecedents and consequences, considering relevant factors and moderators, will improve insights for inclusive and early development, including business arrangements between stakeholders. A summary of these factors adapted from Sullivan (2023) are listed in Table 33.

Antecedents		Outcomes	
Individual	Organisational and climate	Individual	Organisational
Individual characteristics Age Gender Profession Skills Remote work preferences Living place	Organisational climate of fear, individualism, competition, lack of organisational and collegial support	Lower trust Lower Job satisfaction Work-family conflict Mental health outcome	Lower individual and team performance Lower commitment Lower creativity Lower engagement High turnover Absenteeism Emotional contagion

Table 33: Organisational and individual consequences of antecedent factors (source Sullivan and Bendell, 2023)

In addition to the individual and organisational aspects, it has also been noted that the ‘system level’ recognises the individual needs of employees (Wang et. al., 2021). In the case of remote work, the responsibility for implementing health-promoting job design usually lies with the employees. This situation gives rise to another concept of work-life balance literacy within the context of remote work.

For example, guidelines for ergonomic interventions, which is one of the most researched topics, are provided to employees to ensure that they effectively implement preventive health-promoting practices while working from home. It is quite significant to provide guidelines for setting up home offices and computer workstations to prevent MSDs and negative mental and physical stress responses of the body by supporting an ergonomic workstation. It is equally important and necessary that policies and practices related to work-life balance interactions are supported and made accessible by the system and that these responsibilities are defined. This includes organising work breaks, structuring the daily schedule, planning and organising supportive leisure activities, and minimising interruptions to the detriment of the employee, which are essential for a sustainable working life (Mojtahedzadeh et. al., 2021).

Maintaining boundaries between work and private life in terms of time, space and mental focus, buffer zones and strengthening the work-life interface according to needs and preferences should be considered as basic elements of a health-promoting work environment (Mustafa and Gold, 2012).

Practices based on the right to disconnect, managing interruptions, breaks and end-of-day practices are important to support and manage the boundary components that affect well-being: environmental boundaries, equipment boundaries and activity boundaries.

4.2.4 Potential effects of RWAs on Health and Well-being

This section evaluates the effects of Remote Working Arrangements (RWAs) on bio-psycho-social health, following the World Health Organization's (WHO) 'holistic approach,' encompassing physical health, mental health, and health behaviours (RQ 5). This evaluation is based on the needs associated with RWAs, with special emphasis on point (vi) of the proposal, which features issues such as loneliness and depression.

4.2.4.1 Holistic Approach to Health and Well-being (KPI)

The concept of well-being has garnered significant attention due to its profound implications on the health and productivity of individuals working outside traditional office settings. The **World Health Organization (WHO) adopts a holistic approach to well-being, encompassing physical, mental, and social dimensions to promote overall health and quality of life** (WHO, 1948; Topp et. al., 2015). This holistic perspective is of great importance in comprehending the complex nature of well-being in remote work environments, where individuals encounter distinctive challenges and opportunities that can influence their health and happiness.

The advent of the Covid-19 pandemic has precipitated a rapid transition towards remote working arrangements, which have the potential to challenge individuals' sense of connection to their workplace and their overall mental health and well-being (Krug et. al., 2021). Such a widespread transition to remote work has entailed a re-evaluation of traditional work structures and practices with a view to ensure the well-being of employees in virtual work environments. By considering the holistic dimensions of well-being, organisations can better support their remote workforce and mitigate the negative impacts of isolation and disconnection.

An integrated approach to well-being considers the interrelatedness of various aspects of people's lives, including physical, mental, social, behavioural, environmental and occupational health (Charalampous, 2022). Furthermore, these aspects are consistent with the World Health Organization's social determinants of health concept, which are defined as the conditions in which people are born, grow, work, live, and age, as well as the broader set of forces and systems that shape the conditions of daily life (WHO Commission on Social Determinants of Health, 2008). These include financial income, gender, race, education, employment, and

social support and cohesion, all having a significant impact on individuals' health outcomes (Harper, 2021). From this perspective, viewing work as a social determinant of health points to the necessity of deploying equity-focused strategies to advance health and well-being in occupational contexts (Wipfli et. al., 2021). It is of utmost importance to gain an understanding of these social determinants and to devise strategies that will foster a supportive work environment and promote the overall well-being of remote employees.

This perspective is particularly pertinent in the context of remote work, where the distinction between personal and professional life can become less clear, potentially leading to increased stress. This underscores the interconnectivity of diverse well-being elements and points to the necessity to address previously overlooked concerns, including detachment from work, evolving living and working conditions, and health-related behaviours. Consequently, strategies that address well-being in a more comprehensive manner, encompassing various dimensions, are essential to ensure an enhanced quality of life for remote workers (CDC, 2019). It provides valuable pathways and mechanisms on the strategies employed by managers to support employee well-being in remote settings by incorporating insights from various disciplines, such as psychology, medicine, and engineering, which enrich our understanding of well-being in remote work environments (Kukytė, 2023; Stasiuk-Piekarska, 2021).

The 'holistic approach' to well-being advocated by the WHO serves as a guiding principle in understanding and promoting health and happiness in remote work environments (Topp et. al., 2015). By addressing physical, mental, and social well-being dimensions, organisations can create a conducive work environment that supports the overall well-being of remote employees.

World Health Organization (WHO) provides a framework for understanding and promoting health and well-being in remote work environments (WHO, 1998). By drawing on insights from research studies that explore the intersection of well-being, remote work, and organisational practices, organisations can cultivate a culture of care and support that enhances the quality of life for individuals engaged in remote work. While transition to and evolution of RWAs is still ongoing, the findings of the Eurobarometer report illustrate the sustained impact of the pandemic on work practices and the ongoing adaptations by employers and employees to enhance productivity and satisfaction in a hybrid work setting. All findings indicate a strong connection with the potential RWAs developments related effects on working and living conditions to shape the 'life.'

4.2.4.2 Physical health and Health behaviours (KPI)

Physical health: Remote working settings might detrimentally affect physical health by reducing physical exercise and elevating the likelihood of musculoskeletal illnesses. A scoping review has found that prolonged sitting associated with working from home increased the risk of musculoskeletal disorders and has defined working at home as a hazard factor for MSDs¹⁵ (Cruz-Ausejo, 2023). Promotion of physical activity among individuals who work remotely is crucial to mitigate the adverse health effects of a sedentary lifestyle (Owen et. al.et. al., 2020). A sedentary lifestyle has been demonstrated to have a detrimental impact on the human body, with a range of adverse effects including disrupted metabolism, reduced insulin sensitivity, impaired vascular function and an increased risk of hormone-related cancers.

Furthermore, it contributes to weight gain, chronic inflammation, and raises the risk of mortality, cardiovascular diseases, cancer, metabolic disorders, musculoskeletal issues, depression, and cognitive decline. In order to improve public health, it is essential to reduce sedentary behaviour and increase physical activity. It is also necessary to manage both work and non-work activities more effectively, and to provide organisational support, as this seems to highlight the buffering role of the work-life interface (Park et. al., 2020). As part of their study, Park et. al. examined the health effects of sedentary lives in remote working settings and suggested incorporating regular physical activity into daily schedules. Meanwhile, Sallis et. al. (2016) emphasised the significance of workplace health promotion programmes that promote physical activity in safeguarding remote workers' health. The interpretation of the urban environmental design has the potential to significantly enhance physical activity. This finding is supported by a growing body of evidence-base that demonstrates the effectiveness of urban planning, transportation, and parks initiatives in addressing the global physical inactivity pandemic (Sallis et al, 2016).

A systematic review conducted in 2011 on the health conditions of remote and mobile workers revealed a higher prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders among remote workers. Furthermore, it has also stressed that evidence-based research in this field is relatively limited (Crawford et. al., 2011). The level of work-home interference remained unchanged. The results demonstrated that there was no statistically significant interaction between time and condition on work-home interference (WHI), indicating that NWW did not impact the equilibrium between work and non-work domains (Nijp et. al., 2016). A medium level decline in

¹⁵ <https://osha.europa.eu/en/themes/musculoskeletal-disorders/research-work-related-msds>

self-reported health condition was observed in the intervention group, with health scores dropping from 7.47 to 7.04 (Nijp et. al., 2016).

The main implications of remote working settings on physical health manifest themselves in musculoskeletal issues, unhealthy behaviours related to obesity, sleep problems, and stress. These factors contribute to cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Additionally, digestive issues, gastrointestinal system (GIS) problems, and immune system-related health outcomes are frequently investigated. Perego et. al. (2024) found that an unhealthy remote work environment can increase cardiovascular risk by reducing vagal modulation (Perego et. al., 2024).

Health behaviours

Remote work also has an impact on health behaviours, with an indirect or direct wide range of health outcomes, emerging as a consequence. From a positive perspective, having greater flexibility, might allow individuals to engage in healthier behaviours in low intensity workload. Remote work has been linked to favourable health outcomes (Tavares, 2017). These might include behaviours such as preparing nutritionally balanced meals, incorporating physical exercise into the daily routine, and striking a more optimal work-life balance. Furthermore, elimination of the commuting necessity can result in reduced stress levels, allowing additional time for leisure activities and familial pursuits.

Currently, there is not a clear understanding of the benefits and challenges of global remote work, particularly in relation to health behaviours, well-being, mental health, work-life balance, job satisfaction, productivity, home office adaptability, and gender equality. Although more studies have focused on these aspects, the impact of remote work on health behaviours and well-being remains crucial and requires further investigation.

Remote work may adversely affect mental health, physical activity, sedentary behaviour, and sleep quality, all of which are linked to chronic conditions (Barone Gibbs et al., 2021; Kantyka & Maciag, 2024; Beckel & Fisher, 2022; Lyzwinski, 2024). To promote well-being, organisations should encourage social support, formulate family-friendly policies, and employ procedures that enable health-promoting home working environments (Keightley et. al., 2023; Lyzwinski, 2024). Women, especially those with children, have reported lower levels of well-being and productivity while working remotely, which may further restrict their ability to maintain healthy behaviours (Lyzwinski, 2024).

Additionally, stress and anxiety related to job security, workload, and unclear communication can lead to irregular sleep patterns and decreased sleep quality. Remote work significantly impacts sleep patterns and overall well-being. A review of the literature shows a correlation between working from home and delayed bedtimes and wake times, along with longer sleep durations (Massar et. al., 2023; Salfi et. al., 2022). Some studies suggest that this shift in the circadian rhythm may benefit individuals with evening chronotypes by reducing their susceptibility to sleep disturbances and depressive symptoms (Salfi et. al., 2022).

However, remote work has also resulted in increased sedentary behaviour and reduced physical activity (Barone Gibbs et. al., 2021; Massar et. al., 2023). While some studies have indicated that remote work may have beneficial effects on psychological and physical stress responses (Shimura et. al., 2021), others have highlighted potential negative impacts on mood and quality of life (Barone Gibbs et. al., 2021). The impact of remote work on sleep and well-being may be contingent on individual circumstances, such as the presence of children (Massar et. al., 2023). These findings collectively highlight the complex relationship between remote work and sleep, pointing to the importance of deploying balanced strategies to maintain health and productivity.

Most remote workers are office workers, and remote working is known to increase sedentary behaviour and decrease physical activity among office workers (Barone Gibbs et. al., 2021; Loef et. al., 2022). It is important to acknowledge that remote work may result in social isolation, which has been linked to adverse mental health outcomes and subsequently, stress-related physical health issues as well as health issues associated with sedentary behaviours (Wilms et.al. 2022). The dissolution of the distinction between work and personal life can result in longer working hours and a reduction in physical activity. Sedentary behaviour and mental health problems can lead to significant health problems and have negative long-term effects on mental health, work productivity and overall well-being (Falk et. al., 2022; Tronco Hernandez et. al., 2021).

Factors contributing to sedentary behaviour include lack of active commuting, non-availability of fitness facilities and blurred boundaries between work and home, depending on residential location, opportunities and environment close to the workplace. However, some workers reported positive adaptation experiences, such as increased flexibility and more time for exercise (Tronco Hernandez et. al., 2021; Cabrita et. al., 2021). Interventions combining height-adjustable desks and online behaviour modification programmes have shown promise in improving mental well-being and work performance as well (Falk et. al., 2022).

To promote physical activity and reduce sedentary behaviour, employers should consider supporting healthy lifestyles, employing flexible working policies and creating social norms around active breaks (Barone Gibbs et. al., 2021; Olsen et. al., 2018; Rudnicka et. al., 2022).

In conclusion, while remote working can facilitate certain healthy behaviours due to increased flexibility, it can also result in the adoption of negative health behaviours if not managed effectively. It is therefore recommended that organisations put into life policies that encourage regular breaks, promote physical activity, ensure clear communication, and support a healthy work-life balance to mitigate the adverse health effects associated with remote work. Nutrition, exercise, sleep, access to healthy behaviour support services, utilisation of health promotion or counselling services, and awareness are all essential factors contributing overall well-being.

In Switzerland, flexible and remote working arrangements help workers achieve recommended daily physical activity levels (Wöhner, 2023). Substantial body of evidence indicates that prolonged periods of sedentary activity, such as sitting at a desk, are associated with an elevated risk of musculoskeletal issues and obesity and cardiovascular disease (Park et.al., 2020). In Sweden, the national data covering the period 2011-2016 – re-analysed for teleworkers indicated that remote workers walk more but cycle less. It has been stated that teleworking significantly influences active travel habits, showing varying effects on walking (Eldér, 2022). The available data are insufficient for full interpretation of the health implications of remote work.

Organisations need to update their toolbox to support employee health and well-being in a work-from-home environment. Bartman and colleagues reviewed successful, evidence-based interventions in four key areas: physical activity and sedentary behaviour, nutrition, loneliness, and stress, and how these can be adapted for a home-based office environment (Bartmann et. al., 2022). Future research and the role of health professionals and policymakers are needed to design effective interventions.

4.2.4.3 Mental health and mental disorders (KPI)

Although remote work has the potential to alter the conventional work setting, it offers a multitude of advantages, including an enhanced work-life equilibrium and a diminished experience of commute-related stress. However, it also presents distinctive challenges to mental health. It is of the utmost importance to gain

an understanding of the mechanisms that connect remote work with mental health to devise effective strategies to promote employee well-being.

Several factors may influence the mental health and productivity of workers in a remote work setting. These include job-related stress, the surrounding environment, and personal characteristics (Shimura et. al., 2021). The influence of remote work on psychological and physical stress responses, in addition to the phenomenon of 'presenteeism,' highlights the complex interrelationship between occupational stressors and individual well-being in the context of remote work environments.

The impact of remote work on mental health has been reported as both positive and negative. A significant body of research has documented the benefits of remote work, including enhanced work-life balance, increased job satisfaction, greater opportunities for professional development, and improved job control, as well as a reduction in stress and strain (Polson et. al., 2022). Conversely, the challenges of remote work from a work design perspective encompass pivotal elements, including work-home interference, ineffective communication, procrastination, an augmented workload that precipitates mental distress and burn-out, and loneliness. These factors underscore the importance of social support, job autonomy, monitoring, effective communication strategies and workload in shaping the remote work experience and influencing individuals' mental well-being (Wang et. al., 2021; Polson et. al., 2022). When considering the impact of altered working hours and environments on mental health, it is essential to examine the intricate interplay between work conditions, gender, age and mental well-being in the context of remote work, which has the potential to give rise to gender-based disparities (Polson et. al., 2022; Skąłacka, 2024).

The mechanisms that affect mental health in the context of remote work are multifaceted and complex. Nevertheless, by addressing these mechanisms and deploying targeted interventions to support mental well-being, organisations can enable a conducive work environment that fosters the mental health and overall well-being of their remote employees.

The mental well-being of individuals can be negatively impacted by remote work due to variables such as social isolation, heightened stress levels, and the merging of work and personal life boundaries. According to Wang et al (2020), distant working practices can result in heightened levels of stress and anxiety due to social isolation and insufficient support (Wang et. al., 2021). Literature based strategies for improving mental well-being, include facilitating access to mental health services and promoting virtual social interactions. Mental health antecedents at both individual and organisational levels are needed to be managed through

organisational support or access to relevant services at the systemic level. This approach is essential to prevent adverse outcomes (Figures 40 and 41, Sullivan and Bendell, 2023), and to implement targeted interventions that promote overall well-being and reduce to risk of burn-out and depression. According to the Eurobarometer, the main factors associated with mental health are presented in Table 34.

Aspect from Eurobarometer (EU, 2023)	Findings
Key Contributors to Good Mental Health	- Being in contact with nature and green spaces (35%) - Sleeping habits (35%) - Sport/physical activity (34%) - Social contact (33%) - Doing something enjoyable (30%) - Healthy eating habits (29%) - Relaxation (27%) - Work/life balance (26%) - Leisure activities (20%) - Reducing the use of digital/social media (9%)
Important antecedents for Mental Health	- Living conditions (60%) - Financial security (53%) - Physical activity (41%) - Social contacts (41%) - Selfcare (35%) - Work environments (18%) - Healthcare facilities (17%) - Educational settings (6%) - Digital spaces (3%)
Perceptions of Mental Health Impact from social media	- A large majority of respondents believe that social media can negatively impact the mental health of children and young people. Opinions are split between believing it has a negative impact when used frequently (43%) and believing it has a negative impact even if used sporadically (44%).
Quality Mental Health Services	- Equally accessible for everyone (39%) - Provided by skilled well-resourced professionals (37%) - Timely and available when needed (34%) - Person-centred, addressing the specific needs of every individual (33%) - Affordable (23%) - Reliable and safe (21%) - Respectful of human rights, dignity, and different cultures and norms (21%) - Includes support system (18%)
Experiences Accessing Mental Health Services	25% of respondents reported encountering issues accessing mental health services, with the most frequently mentioned issue being long waiting lists or delays before diagnosis or treatment (67%). Other issues included services being too expensive (35%) and not knowing any good doctors or specialists (30%).
Personal Experiences with Mental Health Problems	46% of respondents experienced emotional or psychological problems in the last 12 months, with the most common symptoms being feeling sad/down (69%), excessive fears or worries (50%), low self-esteem (42%), and difficulties concentrating (41%).
Professional Help Received	More than half (54%) of those with mental health issues did not receive help from a professional. Only 19% received help from a general practitioner, 14% from a psychiatrist, and 14% from a psychologist.

Table 34: Mental health parameters from Eurobarometer in the context of RWAs

4.2.4.4 Loneliness (KPI)

The interdisciplinary literature review conducted as part of this subtitle focusing on loneliness provides insights into workplace loneliness in remote arrangements, which can be managed by improving information quality, supportive leadership, supportive conditions for job demands, and individual psychological states. Remote work has brought significant changes to workplace dynamics, particularly affecting employee well-being and the experience of loneliness (Cardone and Arwine, 2024). This synthesis of findings from studies examines the various factors contributing to workplace loneliness in remote settings, including information quality, leadership styles, job demands, and psychological states.

It is stated that the interventions can enhance and support communication and address loneliness, resulting in significant improvements in employee well-being and engagement in remote work environments. In a recent study, Chuang and colleagues conducted a one-week, three-wave survey of 462 remote workers in Taiwan (Chuang et. al., 2024). The study's objective was to ascertain the impact of information quality (regarding timeliness and accuracy) on work-family conflict, loneliness and well-being. To this end, the researchers employed the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model as a theoretical framework. The researchers found that organisational information accuracy was inversely correlated with work-family conflict, whereas information timeliness was negatively associated with loneliness. Both factors were found to be positively associated with the well-being of the remote workers. It is recommended that organisations provide accurate and timely information to mitigate the negative effects of work-family conflict and loneliness, thereby enhancing the well-being and productivity of remote workers. The findings of this study highlight the importance of accurate and timely organisational communication in promoting the overall well-being of remote workers (Chuang et. al., 2024).

Information access, leadership and loneliness

Access to information plays a crucial role in reducing conflict and loneliness, thereby enhancing well-being. A study conducted by Bareket-Bojmel et.al. (2023) involving 349 employees from the US and the UK examined the relationship between remote work, loneliness, and work engagement, with a particular focus on the mediating role of hope (Bareket-Bojmel et al., 2023). Using Snyder's Hope Scale and the UCLA Loneliness Scale (Russell, 1996; Snyder et al., 1996), the study found that while remote work does not inherently diminish work engagement, loneliness moderates this effect. The study suggests that interventions aimed at increasing hope could enhance job engagement among lonely remote workers. This highlights the importance of psychological

interventions to sustain high levels of job engagement in remote work settings by promoting empathic communication within organisations, which can help alleviate workplace loneliness and foster a supportive organisational culture and climate.

Jin and Ikeda (2024) further explored the mediating role of empathic communication in the relationship between servant leadership and workplace loneliness. They conducted a survey of 267 employees across 28 provinces in China, using validated scales to assess servant leadership, leader-empathic communication, employee-empathic communication, and workplace loneliness. Their hierarchical regression and serial mediation analyses revealed that although servant leadership does not directly reduce workplace loneliness, it does so indirectly through empathic communication between leaders and employees.

Expanding on the theme of workplace loneliness, Walz et al. (2023) investigated how work and home demands contribute to this issue. Using the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory, Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory, and Social Exchange Theory (SET), they conducted a two-wave survey of German employees. Their results revealed that home demands exacerbate loneliness through home-work interference, a process that is not mitigated by home-based support.

Moreover, the study found that work demands increase loneliness at work through work-to-home interference, with this effect being moderated by workplace support. Some individuals may experience anxiety over the potential blurring of boundaries between their work and personal lives, which could strain their relationships with colleagues. While remote work offers advantages such as reduced commuting and greater autonomy, concerns about isolation and role conflicts may deter some employees from embracing it.

In India, Anand (2024) examined the relationship between perceived information concealment (knowledge hiding) and loneliness at work, including role and task conflict as antecedents, through a two-stage survey of 500 mid-level IT professionals. Based on social information processing theory, the study found that role and task conflict exacerbated perceived information concealment, and that information concealment was associated with increased loneliness at work. The relationship between conflict and loneliness is mediated by information concealment (Anand, 2024). Given the challenges posed by information concealment, the study suggests strategies for managers to eliminate information concealment to enable a positive work environment and reduce loneliness.

Sullivan and Bendell (2023) highlighted that loneliness in the workplace is a widespread problem that has a negative impact on both employee and organisational outcomes such as engagement (Sullivan and Bendell, 2023). Managers have a key role to play in addressing this issue by encouraging the development of relationships and cultivating a people-centric organisational culture. In their research, researchers highlight the importance of initiative-taking managerial strategies such as promoting social connectivity and cultivating a supportive organisational culture to mitigate workplace loneliness and improve organisational health (Figure 42).

Figure 42: Conceptual model summary of associations between remote work and workplace loneliness (KPI)

Engagement in work is conducive to the enhancement of independence in everyday life as well as the maintenance of an individual’s well-being across all aspects of their existence. Active employment serves to mitigate the risk of physical, mental, and social issues associated with long-term unemployment, while also facilitating social inclusion and poverty reduction. It is widely recognised that workplace engagement is linked to positive outcomes for both physical and mental health that might be otherwise influenced by loneliness. Remote work offers a valuable opportunity for individuals who may face difficulties in attending the workplace, such as those with disabilities or those living in remote areas, to work from home. A conceptual model structure is suggested in Figure 43 by the authors.

Bartmann and colleagues conducted a systematic review of existing research on interventions aiming to improve the health of remote workers and highlighted the need for organisations to update their approach to employee health and well-being considering the transition to remote working, focusing on physical activity, nutrition, loneliness and stress (Bartmann et. al., 2022). The review identified key strategies (Table 35) and suggested interventions such as organising virtual social events, designing mentoring programmes, and conducting regular check-ins to reduce feelings of isolation and enhance social connectivity to decrease feeling of loneliness.

Strategy	Description	Loneliness Impact
Active Workstations	Using sit-stand desks and active workstations (e.g., walking/cycling desks) to reduce sedentary behaviour.	Reduces feelings of isolation by promoting physical activity, which can improve mental health.
Active Meetings	Promoting standing or walking during meetings and integrating movement or stretching periods into traditional meetings.	Encourages social interaction and reduces isolation by making meetings more dynamic and engaging.
Temptation Bundling	Combining exercise with enjoyable activities like streaming TV shows or listening to audiobooks to increase physical activity.	Enhances mental health and reduces loneliness by pairing exercise with enjoyable activities, creating positive experiences to share
Monetary Incentives	Offering financial rewards for meeting physical activity targets, particularly effective with constant and threshold incentives.	Can create a sense of community and shared goals among employees, equality, access facilitators reducing feelings of isolation.
Nutrition	Provide visual reminders, healthy food vouchers, and educational materials to promote healthy eating habits.	Promotes well-being by encouraging healthy eating as mutual goal and shared activities, indirectly reducing stress and loneliness.
Mental Health	Implement supportive workplace practices and interventions to address mental health issues, reduce absenteeism, and increase productivity.	Directly addresses loneliness by providing mental health support and fostering a supportive work environment.

Table 35 Key strategies to overcome loneliness and promote social connectedness (Bartman et.al, 2022)

Figure 43: Key strategies to overcome workplace loneliness (Sullivan and Lewis, 2002)

4.2.5 Gender Perspectives (KPI)

This section provides an explorative insight into **RQ6** (on point (vi) of the proposal): Identify gender-specific challenges that could arise from RWAs, and how they might influence work-life dynamics (e.g. flexible working practices, work intensity, health outcomes, monitoring and support, working models, and reducing inequalities through a gender-specific lens)

The impact of remote working on gender inequalities is a complex phenomenon, influenced by the multifaceted gender norms of a specific context. To understand the existing research on the gender dimensions of remote working and to guide future data collection and monitoring practices, an interdisciplinary and ‘holistic approach’ is essential. This approach should include collaborative, terminology-based research among remote workers, considering various types of remote working arrangements and their

multidimensional aspects. A comprehensive report addressing remote working from a gender perspective, has concluded that there is a need for a consistent definition of the concept of remote working in all sources (OECD, 2023, Eurofound, gender--).

Effects on work-life balance

Examining the existing literature on the gender dimension of remote working, it appears that this working practice has mixed effects on work-life balance, gender inequalities and career progression. Before the pandemic, Sullivan and Lewis (2002) explored 'new opportunities for flexibility' and 'patterns of exploitation' models to understand the relationships between home remote work, gender and the home-work interface through a qualitative study. The study showed that these models are not mutually exclusive, as remote work can reinforce traditional gender roles in work and family dynamics while simultaneously improving work-life balance (Sullivan and Lewis, 2002).

In a systematic review of articles published between 2010 and 2022, Castro-Trancon et. al. (2024) investigated the impact of remote working on family-work conflict, women's health and well-being, and work-family satisfaction from a gender perspective. Their findings revealed that remote work negatively affected women's work-life balance and well-being more than men's, as women often had to assume greater home and family responsibilities. Women working remotely reported heightened conflicts between work and family and a stronger adherence to traditional gender roles (Castro-Trancón et. al., 2024).

As various studies have shown, the practice of remote work perpetuates gender stereotypes and is seen as particularly problematic for women's well-being. To gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing remote working outcomes, future research should investigate various socio-demographic, family, and work-related variables. Considering the role theory, the role conflict theory, and the gender role theory, a three-dimensional approach is recommended for future policies and practices. This approach should account for the impact of remote working on well-being, with particular attention to gender differences. Additionally, it is crucial to promote shared domestic responsibilities between men and women and provide support for all workers in the evolving remote working environment, regardless of gender.

Wang et. Al. reports that work schedule control has traditionally been associated with self-reported mental health, which can be subject to biases such as recall and social desirability. To address this, the researchers

suggest using biomarkers of allostatic load, which are objective indicators of chronic stress, as an alternative outcome measure. They found that control over work schedules was associated with lower allostatic load among women, especially those with traditional gender role attitudes, while no significant association was found among men. The study suggests that future research could include these biomarkers as complementary indicators of quality of working life, and that public health policymakers and organisations could use them to monitor mental health (Wang et. al, 2022).

Women often face greater challenges in maintaining boundaries between their professional and personal lives, which increases their susceptibility to work-family conflict (Castro-Trancón et. al., 2024; Cannito and Scavarda, 2020). Similarly, it has been stated that women are more likely to combine work and caregiving responsibilities and are more affected by remote working. This leads to a tendency to intensify work, extend working hours, increase flexibility, and adopt an 'always on' mentality. Women are more negatively impacted by working long hours and unsocial hours, which can result in major health issues (Eurofound, 2020a; Joshi and Kumar, 2024; Wang and Cheng, 2024).

The potential gender impacts of remote work arrangements mostly focus on gender inequalities in work-life balance (Joshi and Kumar, 2024). For women who often have caregiving responsibilities, remote working/remote work offers the opportunity to work flexibly, which can potentially help improve their work-life balance. However, remote work can also exacerbate gender inequalities by reinforcing traditional gender norms and roles. It may make it more challenging for women to balance paid work with unpaid caregiving responsibilities, leading to increased work-life conflict, greater strain, and negative psycho-social and health outcomes (Lyttelton et.al, 2020; de Laat, 2023).

The acceptability of RWAs is contingent upon its capacity to address gender disparities and work-related organisational aspects in labour force participation. One potential avenue for addressing the discrepancy in labour force participation rates among different population groups is through remote working (OECD, 2021; Almeida et. al. 2024).

Table 36 presents the definitions of OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers, No. 285 (Touzet, 2023).

Variables & Definition	Main Findings (Touzet, 2023; OECD 2020)
<p>Teleworking Feasibility The potential for a job to be performed remotely using information and communications technology (ICT).</p>	<p>It is estimated that 40 % of jobs in OECD countries can be done remotely with the support of technology, but this percentage varies considerably across occupations. It shows higher feasibility in sectors such as finance, banking, IT with rates exceeding 60%. In contrast, sectors like manufacturing and retail have feasibility rates below 20%</p>
<p>Actual Teleworking Usage The real-world adoption and practice of teleworking by employees.</p>	<p>Despite the rapid uptake during the Covid-19, only around 27 per cent of employees in OECD countries reported teleworking regularly (2020). Despite the high potential, the actual use of teleworking is reported to be lagging behind.</p>
<p>Gender Disparities Differences in teleworking trends and impacts between men and women.</p>	<p>Gender differences are reported to be decisive in teleworking. Women have been found to be more likely to work remotely in relation to their distribution in administrative and professional services. However, due to traditional roles, additional challenges in terms of productivity and satisfaction have been identified.</p>
<p>Work-Life Balance The equilibrium between personal life and employment responsibilities.</p>	<p>It was emphasised that the impact on work-life balance is complex, and that although work-life balance is reported to improve due to shorter commuting times and increased flexibility, it is difficult to separate work and private life, which is associated with a vicious circle of longer working hours and increased stress.</p> <p>Around 60% of teleworkers report improved work-life balance due to reduced commuting time, approximately 35% of women teleworkers report difficulties in separating work from personal life, compared to 25% of men</p>
<p>Career Progression The advancement and development in one's professional career.</p>	<p>Teleworking may affect career progression differently for men and women. It is reported to potentially hinder career progression, particularly through reduced visibility and networking opportunities. 40% of teleworkers feel that remote work has negatively impacted their career progression opportunities due to reduced visibility and networking. Women are more affected, with 45% reporting concerns about career progression compared to 35% of men (IDEAS/RePEc).</p>
<p>Job Satisfaction The level of contentment employees feel towards their job.</p>	<p>Another controversial issue is job satisfaction. While autonomy and flexibility are emphasised, attention is drawn to the potential of the office environment to structure social interactions, corporate culture and support. The net effect on job satisfaction is also linked to job roles, work intensity, organisational factors and support for teleworking, as well as individual benefits and preferences. About 70% of teleworkers express satisfaction with the flexibility provided by remote work (EconPapers, Touzet, 2023)</p> <p>Social Interaction: Conversely, 30% of teleworkers miss the social interactions of an office environment, impacting their overall job satisfaction (IDEAS/RePEc).</p>

<p>Hierarchical Position The rank or level of authority an individual holds within an organisation.</p>	<p>While teleworking is more suitable for high-level and white-collar workers, senior professionals and managers, it is considered less feasible for lower-level workers who require physical presence and for some sectors.</p>
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Table 36: An overview of the psycho-social variables related to telework, their definitions and related references that provided in the report

Job satisfaction

Following the pandemic, particularly during the initial phase of transition to remote working, there has been a notable reduction in the conflict between work and family responsibilities for female employees. This has been accompanied by a decline in stress levels and an increase in job satisfaction compared to male employees, as indicated by a study examined the experiences of 264 workers who transitioned to working from home due to the Covid-19 pandemic (Zhou and Flinchbaugh, 2022). The study combined boundary management theory, Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, and job satisfaction literature to explore gender differences in work-family conflict and family-work conflict, and to determine how these differences affect job satisfaction and stress. The study revealed that when employees work from home, both work-family conflict and family-work conflict decrease, with a more significant reduction in work-family conflict. Additionally, employees report lower stress levels and higher job satisfaction while working remotely. Although concerns from different sectors may shift after the transition period, these findings should be considered as long-term implications of remote work, especially in relation to gender dimensions. Similar studies suggest that corporate policies supporting remote working can alleviate the burden on employees, particularly women, during the transition to working from home (Bal and Bulgur, 2023; Olawale et. al., 2024).

Effects of flexible working practices on men and women

Flexible working arrangements can impact men and women differently. Munsch conducted a controlled online experiment using gender-specific and cultural perceptions of flexible working arrangements as variables. The study analysed the outcomes of applying for flexible working arrangements, focusing on differences between types such as teleworking/flexible working versus flexitime, and examining how gender and parental status of the applicant influenced these outcomes. The results showed that employees who requested flexible working hours scored more negatively than those who did not. Additionally, remote work requests were evaluated more negatively compared to flexible work requests. Flexible working requests related to childcare were

viewed more favourably than those unrelated to childcare. Notably, men who requested flexible working for childcare reasons received more positive evaluations than both men who requested flexible working for other reasons and women who made similar childcare-related requests (Munsch, 2016). One study reported that flexible working had no significant effect on the turnover rate of employees with family responsibilities. It was reported to be not very effective in reducing short-term sick leave, sick leave for spouse and childcare, or short-term unpaid leave. It was reported that it did not reduce absenteeism more for women than for men (Haines et.al, 1999)

Work intensity of remote working and gender related effects

Additionally, working engagement and gender related results indicate that the increasing intensity of remote working has a more negative impact on women's working conditions than on those of men (Rodríguez-Modroño, 2022). In their study, the authors used the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model to evaluate the effects of remote work intensity and gender. They employed regression models, controlling for factors such as occupation, economic activity, age, education, number of children, and country, to examine the relationships between remote work intensity, gender, and work quality dimensions. The results showed that a high intensity of remote working increases discretion, expectations, income, and professional commitment but has a negative impact on the physical and social environment, work intensity, and the quality of working time. Remote working at low and medium intensity has a positive effect on skills and discretion, the quality of working time, the physical environment, expectations, and income. Gender-specific differences are significant: women experience more negative effects on work intensity and the quality of working time when they remote work frequently (Rodríguez-Modroño, 2022). The authors emphasised the positive and negative effects of remote working on working conditions and work engagement, particularly for women. They recommended a cautious and gender-sensitive approach to promoting remote working.

Health-related outcomes of remote work and gender difference

Psycho-social factors such as increased workload, extreme time pressure and poor communication within the company (lack of broad range of organisational arrangements) are more prevalent among women working remotely. These risks are associated with higher rates of stress, anxiety, depression, headaches, eye strain, and musculoskeletal disorders in women compared to men (Matthews et. al., 2022).

Based on data from 1,585 participants of the Health, Ethnicity, and Pandemic (HEAP) study, a nationwide survey conducted in the US in October 2020 during the Covid-19 pandemic, investigating the relationship between working from home and psychological distress. The findings revealed that employees working remotely experienced higher levels of psychological distress compared to those who worked on-site, even after considering demographic factors, socio-economic status, and health behaviours. When analysed by gender, the increased psychological distress associated with remote work was significant among women but not among men (Matthews et. al., 2022).

In terms of the physical health impacts, remote work significantly contributes to the development or worsening of work-related musculoskeletal disorders. This is influenced by poor workstation ergonomics, sedentary behaviour, and various psycho-social and organisational factors (Milaković et. al., 2023). It was found that being physically distant from the employer's premises, lack of workplace improvements, and the heavy dependence on various technologies and digital tools (rather than face-to-face meetings and workplace mobility) can lead to less ergonomic home environments. This increases the risk of physical health issues such as musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) for women.

Women are subject to more monitoring and receive less support compared to men

Additionally, women face more monitoring and receive less support than men. Women working from home report higher levels of surveillance compared to their male counterparts. This increased monitoring may heighten strain and anxiety, diminishing the benefits of the autonomy typically associated with remote work. Furthermore, it has been noted that women remote workers are less likely to benefit from occupational health and safety programmes aimed at supporting mental health and reducing stress, such as awareness-raising events, well-being training, and access to counselling. A study that attributes women's low access to and use of ICTs to unfavourable conditions in employment, education and income reports that, controlling for relevant variables, women are more active users of digital tools than men (Hilbert, 2011). In particular, it is emphasised that women's predisposition to ICTs and inequalities in labour force participation can become instrumental in improving livelihoods through digital technology. This is seen as a concrete and tangible opportunity to address gender inequality issues such as employment, income, education and access to health services, alongside necessary support (Martin, 2011; EU-OSHA 2021; EU-OSHA, 2024b).

Working models and gender

The design of work is related to efficiency in the context of the working life, and thus constitutes a key factor in determining the effectiveness of any given work process. The concept of agile working models proposes methodologies that facilitate remote working. Furthermore, it has been observed that this situation may prove disadvantageous to women in the absence of a demand-driven approach (de Laat, 2022; Beno, 2019).

The effects of different working models on remote working and gender equality have also been studied. De Laat (2022) conducted in-depth interviews with 84 IT employees working in two different modalities (agile and waterfall) to investigate gender-specific patterns in remote work adoption. They found that the agile model encourages on-site work and is gender-balanced, with more women working remotely, although this is perceived as unacceptable. In contrast, the waterfall model encourages remote working and is gender-neutral, with equal numbers of women and men working remotely. The bureaucratic (waterfall) working model offers more flexibility than the post-bureaucratic (agile) working model. Overall, the bureaucratic waterfall model provides greater flexibility and is associated with greater gender equality in remote working compared to the post-bureaucratic agile model (de Laat, 2022). Based on the study's findings, the authors recommended the following policies: (1) Remote working should be used occasionally rather than permanently or exclusively to avoid negative impacts on work quality and well-being. (2) Companies should implement measures to support their employees and mitigate the adverse effects of remote working on engagement. (3) Governments should adopt a gender-sensitive approach to promote remote working, including increased public investment in early childhood education and care and expanding paternity leave. It is also important to continue mainstreaming and normalising remote work for both women and men, assess the outcomes of flexible working arrangements for all employees, and eliminate the associated stigma and career barriers (de Laat, 2022).

Drawing on the theory of work-family conflicts and gender norms, Lyttelton et. al. (2020) used data from the American Time Use Survey (ATUS) from 2003 to 2018. They compared mothers and fathers working exclusively at the workplace, exclusively from home, and part-time from home to explore differences in time spent on housework, childcare, and leisure, as well as the nature of work performed at home and subjective experiences of telecommuting (Lyttelton et. al., 2020). Their findings revealed that remote working arrangements can intensify the gender gap in housework and childcare, with a more significant negative impact on the mental health of mothers working remotely compared to fathers. Specifically, remote working widens the gender gap in housework, with mothers undertaking more housework than fathers. However, it tends to narrow the gender gap in childcare, especially for couples where both partners work full-time.

Intersectionality: Gender and socio-economic status

The transition to remote working during the pandemic has demonstrated that there are intersections with socio-economic factors that affect women's capacity to balance work and family responsibilities (Katsabian, 2022).

Katsabian (2022) explores how remote working during the Covid-19 pandemic highlighted gender inequalities and work-life balance challenges. The pandemic has led to a global experiment in remote work, blending personal and professional spaces without adequate arrangements. Katsabian argues that remote work could exacerbate gender and socio-economic inequalities if not properly regulated. The study suggests that both employers and public authorities need to formulate policies to address these issues, ensuring equal remote working opportunities and considering women's traditional caregiving roles that affect career progression. Katsabian calls for comprehensive policies that address work-life balance, gender, and socio-economic disparities. Organisations and policymakers must devise strategies to manage the hybrid nature of remote work and its gendered implications (Joshi and Kumar, 2024; Katsabian, 2022).

Reducing Gender-Based Inequities in Remote Work

Remote working mothers experience higher levels of anxiety, loneliness, and depression compared to remote working fathers (Lyttelton et. al., 2020). In their discussion, the authors conclude that remote work is likely to become more prevalent after the pandemic. However, they also point to various weaknesses in the US institutional support system for families, such as the lack of subsidised childcare and paid family leave. Consideration of these factors will be crucial in addressing the gendered impacts of working from home on both work and family life. While the authors do not offer explicit policy recommendations, they emphasise the importance of addressing gaps in institutional support (e.g., subsidised childcare, paid family leave) and developing a stronger 'care infrastructure' to mitigate gender inequalities as remote work becomes more widespread in the post-pandemic era.

Section-specific strategies:

1. Promote Flexible Work Policies

While remote work offers flexibility, not all organisations deploy policies that genuinely support work-life balance. Employers should adopt flexible work hours that accommodate the diverse responsibilities women often juggle, including caregiving and household responsibilities. By allowing employees to tailor their

schedules, organisations can help reduce stress and improve mental health outcomes for women (Kossek, 2015).

2. Foster an Inclusive Company Culture

Cultivating an inclusive culture is vital for addressing gender-based inequities. Organisations should actively promote diversity and inclusion initiatives that empower women. This includes providing training on unconscious bias (Dobbin and Kalev, 2016), encouraging diverse leadership (Ely et. al., 2011), and ensuring that women have equal access to professional development opportunities (Kulik and Metz, 2015). A supportive culture not only enhances job satisfaction but also contributes to better mental health (Roberson, 2006).

3. Address the Digital Divide

Access to technology and reliable internet is essential for remote work success. Women, particularly in marginalised communities, may face barriers in accessing these resources. Organisations can help bridge this digital divide by providing necessary tools, such as laptops and internet subsidies, to ensure that all employees can work effectively from home (Gurstein, 2003). This support can enhance productivity and reduce feelings of isolation (Hilbert, 2011).

4. Implement Mental Health Support Programmes

The remote work environment can lead to feelings of isolation and burn-out, particularly among women who may already be managing multiple roles. Employers should prioritise mental health by offering support programmes, such as counselling services, wellness workshops, and stress management resources (Demerouti et. al., 2001). Regular check-ins and open communication about mental health can foster a supportive environment where employees feel valued and understood (Hakanen et. al., 2008)

5. Encourage Work-Life Boundaries

One of the challenges of remote work is the blurring of boundaries between professional and personal life. Employers should encourage employees to set clear boundaries to protect their well-being. This could include promoting regular breaks, discouraging after-hours emails, and encouraging employees to take their allotted vacation time (Derks et. al., 2015). By normalising these practices, organisations can help prevent burn-out and improve overall health outcomes (Sonnentag and Fritz, 2015).

6. Advocate for Equal Pay and Advancement Opportunities

Gender pay gaps persist in many industries, and remote work should not exacerbate this issue. Organisations must commit to transparency in pay structures and actively work to ensure equal compensation for equal work (Blau and Kahn, 2007). Additionally, providing mentorship programmes and career advancement opportunities specifically for women can help level the playing field and promote long-term career growth (Ragins and Kram, 2007).

5 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The research landscape surrounding remote work presents a range of inconsistencies, particularly in the conclusions drawn across various studies. These discrepancies often stem from differences in terminology and methodology, which complicate the task of generating robust evidence on the subject. While some studies emphasise the positive aspects of remote work, such as increased flexibility and autonomy, others underscore the negative implications, including isolation and blurred work-life boundaries.

Given the ongoing evolution of remote work practices, there is a pressing need for more comprehensive and standardised research to accurately assess its impact on employee well-being and economic sustainability. Early claims about the benefits and drawbacks of remote work must be approached with caution, requiring a heightened awareness of research literacy standards. This will ensure that future studies contribute meaningfully to our understanding of remote work's role in promoting positive developmental outcomes for both individuals and organisations.

The Covid-19 pandemic has led to a shift towards remote working, creating a hybrid 'home-office' space that combines the workplace and private sphere. The home-office setup empowers employers to supervise employees and their families yet violating employee privacy. The home-office reproduces existing inequalities, such as gendered traditional roles and socio-economic disparities in access to technology, preventing equal access to remote work. Katsabian suggests solutions to address these issues such as giving employees a voice to balance power dynamics as well as systemic solutions at the federal/state level to curtail the negative effects on underprivileged groups and women (Katsabian, 2020).

The findings are organised into key topic areas, including policy and guidelines, implementation and practice, eligibility, and approval, monitoring and performance, flexibility and adaptability, health and safety, employee experience, and management and supervision to identify the core messages and insights derived from each study (Table 37-39). These outcomes serve as a comprehensive overview of the current practices as well as future considerations relating to remote and hybrid working conditions.

Policy and Guidelines	Citation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote productivity, morale, and customer service through well-defined remote work policies. Ensure remote working is not guaranteed and compliance with established rules is mandatory. Define remote work and set specific criteria for eligibility. Programme guidelines should require management approval, adherence to policies, and detailed guidelines for equipment use and work arrangements. <p>Eligibility should be based on job responsibilities, work habits, and work schedule, not job title.</p>	<p>(Austintexas.gov, n.d.; Azdcs.gov, 2023; Southboroughma.gov, n.d.)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remote work should be considered an employment benefit rather than a guaranteed right, with approval dependent on performance history and workload balance. <p>Policies should provide guidance for implementing remote working arrangements and encourage agencies to utilize remote work effectively.</p>	<p>(Grandrapissmi.gov., 2021; Doa.alaska.gov, 2023)</p>

Table 37: Recommendations and action points from the perspective of employers, employees, and stakeholders for policies and guidelines

The literature provides valuable insights into the experiences and perspectives of workers in remote and hybrid work environments, highlighting the need for specific policy interventions to enhance their work conditions and overall well-being.

- Assistive Technologies for Workers with Disabilities:** Mcnaughton et. al. (2014) emphasises the importance of assistive technologies in home-based work setups for workers with disabilities. The study reveals a strong desire among participants for such technologies, which can significantly improve their productivity and work experience. The findings suggest that policies should facilitate the provision of assistive technologies to workers with disabilities, ensuring they have the necessary tools to perform their tasks efficiently (Mcnaughton et. al., 2014).
- Need for Clear Remote Work Policies:** Pollak et. al. have identified a significant need for clearer telework policies to enhance productivity and job satisfaction among professionals. The study participants highlighted that well-defined policies could help manage expectations and provide better support for

remote workers. This insight underscores the necessity for organisations to develop comprehensive telework policies that address various aspects of remote work, from performance evaluation to communication protocols (Pollak et. al.,2023).

Flexibility in Employment Forms: The heterogeneity of new employment forms highlights the need for flexible policies that cater to diverse worker needs and conditions. Traditional one-size-fits-all employment policies are inadequate for new, varied and dynamic nature of modern work arrangements. Instead, adaptable policies are necessary to accommodate different types of work, including part-time, freelance, and remote work, ensuring that all workers receive the necessary support and benefits (Eurofound, 2018b). Example Reference policy guidelines are summarised in Tables 38-39.

Key aspects (Example Guidelines, policy documents)
<p>Implementation and Practice (Opm.gov, 2021; NJ.gov, 2022; USPTO.gov, 2022)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Micro-mezzo-macro level institutions should leverage remote work as an effective practice that enhances employee performance and engagement, in cooperation with the specific needs of partners, tailored way • Pilot programmes, such as those seen during Covid-19, should be implemented to evaluate the long-term benefits and effectiveness of remote work
<p>Successful remote work programmes, demonstrate cost savings and positive impacts on employee engagement. (Mass.gov, 2019; HR.Nv.gov, 2023.pdf)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisations should recognize that remote work provides direct benefits through continuity of operations and reduced need for physical office space, while also improving employees' work/life balance. • Remote work agreements should be discretionary and revocable at any time, and not considered an employee entitlement.
<p>Eligibility and Approval (Maine.gov, 2022; Admin.ks.gov, n.d.; Bop.gov, 2010)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear criteria for remote work eligibility should be established, considering job responsibilities, work habits, and performance. • Remote work suitability should be assessed based on job and employee assessment, with specific responsibilities outlined for both employees and supervisors. • Remote work eligibility requirements should include employee performance, impact on staff, and agency goals.
<p>Flexibility and Adaptability (USAID.gov, 2023; Healdsburg.gov, 2023; Oregon.gov, 2022)</p>

- Organisations should establish hybrid and Remote Work Programmes that define remote work as flexibility arrangements.
- Programmes should emphasise the benefits, factors for eligibility, and responsibilities of remote working employees.
- Remote work should allow flexibility in work arrangements, with guidelines for equipment use and work environment.

Table 38: Recommendations and action points from the perspective of employers, employees, and stakeholders for implementation and practice; eligibility and approval; and flexibility and adaptability

The summarised findings point to the complexity and varied implications of remote and hybrid working arrangements across different sectors and organisational contexts.

Policies and guidelines highlight the importance of structured remote work programmes, clear eligibility criteria, and compliance with organisational rules. Implementation of relevant policies and guidelines delivers significant benefits, including enhanced employee performance, cost savings, and improved work-life balance. However, challenges such as the need for effective monitoring, ensuring a healthy and safe work environment, and maintaining engagement and productivity are also evident. These insights collectively suggest that while remote work offers numerous advantages, its successful implementation requires careful planning, continuous evaluation, and a balanced approach to meet both organisational objectives and employee needs. The evolving nature of remote work and its implications will continue to be a critical focal point as organisations navigate the confounding effects of a post-pandemic disrupted work environment.

Key aspects (Example Guidelines, policy documents)	
Monitoring and Performance (Humanresources.vermont.gov, 2012; bop.gov, 2010)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees engaged in remote work must be required to dedicate their full time and effort during scheduled work hours, adhere to a regular schedule, and comply with all relevant state and organisational policies. 	
Supervisors should play a crucial role in monitoring work schedules and performance, with task-specific and frequent performance reviews to ensure accountability and productivity.	
Management and Supervision (Personnel.wv.gov, n.d.)	
Supervisors should maintain engagement with remote working employees through structured expectations/ Effective communication tools, and frequent meetings to promote team cohesiveness and accountability	
Health and Safety (SouthBoroughma.gov, n.d.; Sbcounty.gov, 2022)	

Employees must comply with all policies and regulations while working remotely. Policies should ensure that remote work does not compromise health, safety, or workplace conduct. Hybrid remote work policies should be governed by OSH and Human Resources policies, ensuring health, safety, and workplace conduct.

Table 39: Recommendations and action points from the perspective of employers, employees, and stakeholders for monitoring and performance; and management and supervision from gov. examples

Recommendations to improve productivity

1. **Promote Workplace Flexibility:** Offer flexible work arrangements that allow employees to manage their schedules effectively. This can lead to higher productivity and job satisfaction.
2. **Support Work-Life Balance:** Implement policies and practices that support work-life balance. This can include offering access to coworking spaces or encouraging regular breaks.
3. **Invest in Remote Technology:** Ensure that employees have the necessary technological support to perform their tasks efficiently. This includes providing reliable communication tools and access to necessary resources.
4. **Provide Mental Health Resources:** Offer resources and support for mental health, including access to counselling services and stress management programmes.
5. **Foster Resilience:** Encourage practices to build resilience among employees, such as training programmes and supportive management practices.
6. **Enhance Employer-Employee Communication:** Maintain clear and open communication channels. Regular check-ins and feedback sessions can help keep employees engaged and productive.

Conclusion

Remote work **has the potential to significantly enhance productivity when supported by flexible work arrangements, adequate technological and organisational support, and a focus on work-life balance.** However, it also presents challenges, particularly related to **mental health and communication.** By addressing these challenges and **implementing supportive policies,** organisations can maximise the productivity benefits of remote work.

5.1 SDGs and Mitigation Strategies (WP2 Output)

The existing literature also explores the associations of remote work and on-site work with respect to four Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Table 40). These are identified as SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) (Crawford, 2022; United Nations, 2015). Additional alignments with SDGs are suggested as well.

Aspect	Positive SDG Alignment	Negative SDG Alignment	Strategies to Mitigate Negative Impacts
Working Hours	<p>SDG 8: Promotes decent work,</p> <p>SDG 3: Supports well-being</p>	<p>SDG 3: Risk of burnout,</p> <p>SDG 8: Potential overwork</p>	<p>Implement clear work boundaries, regulations</p> <p>regular monitoring and support</p>
Commute Time	<p>SDG 11: Reduces environmental impact, SDG 3: Enhances well-being</p>	<p>SDG 11: Impact on public transport,</p> <p>SDG 3: Reduced physical activity</p>	<p>Follow environmental impact, promote physical activity, support urban mobility solutions</p>
Income	<p>SDG 1: Contributes to poverty reduction,</p> <p>SDG 8: Ensures fair income</p>	<p>SDG 1: Exacerbates income inequalities,</p> <p>SDG 8: Wage disparities</p>	<p>Establish equitable compensation policies, enhance access to remote work opportunities</p>
Employee Services	<p>SDG 8: Supports decent work,</p> <p>SDG 10: Ensures equal access to services</p>	<p>SDG 8: Disparities in service access,</p> <p>SDG 10: Inequities in organisational support</p>	<p>Equal access to services, develop remote-specific support programmes</p>
Organisational Support	<p>SDG 8: Enhances work environments,</p> <p>SDG 3: Improves well-being</p>	<p>SDG 8: Potential for decreased support,</p> <p>SDG 3: Risk of isolation</p>	<p>Accessibility of services, Regular communication, inclusive policies</p>
Occupational Health and Safety	<p>SDG 3: Ensures health and safety,</p> <p>SDG 8: Promotes safe working conditions</p>	<p>SDG 3: Risk of neglecting standards,</p> <p>SDG 8: Lack of measures decreases productivity</p>	<p>Ergonomic assessments, health and safety training, follow new hazards and risks, mental health</p>
Emergency Plans	<p>SDG 3: Ensures safety, SDG 11: Enhances resilience</p>	<p>SDG 3: Complicates emergency response,</p> <p>SDG 11: Lack of clear plans</p>	<p>Develop remote-specific emergency plans, conduct regular drills and training</p>
Individual Working Conditions	<p>SDG 8: Supports equitable conditions, SDG 10: Promotes equality</p>	<p>SDG 8: Inconsistent working conditions,</p> <p>SDG 10: Inequities in career opportunities</p>	<p>Ensure equitable access to resources, regular policy reviews</p>
Training	<p>SDG 4: Promotes continuous learning, SDG 8: Enhances skills and career growth</p>	<p>SDG 8: Missed training opportunities,</p> <p>SDG 10: Inequities in access to training</p>	<p>Develop inclusive training programmes, provide continuous professional development</p>

Table 40: Aspects of remote work in relation to SDGs and strategies for improvement

The following summary presented in Table 41 provides an overview of the alignment between employee and employer considerations regarding costs, economic security, job satisfaction, and productivity with respect to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Kossek et. al., 2023; Eurofound, 2023; Crawford, 2022; Sostero et. al. 2024; United Nations, 2015). The table offers a framework for the exploitation of beneficial effects and the avoidance of detrimental consequences, with underpinning strategies and citations from the literature.

The following section presents the perspectives of employees and employers, as identified in the literature.

Aspect	Employee Perspective	Employer Perspective	SDG Alignment and Mitigation Strategies
Costs	<p>Positive: Reduced commuting and work-related costs improved financial stability.</p> <p>Negative: Increased home energy and internet costs, potential inequities in bearing remote work expenses.</p>	<p>Positive: Reduced office space and utility costs, supports cost-effective innovation.</p> <p>Negative: Increased costs for providing remote work technology and support, potential inequalities in cost allocation.</p>	<p>SDGs 1, 7, 8, 9: Mitigate through financial support for home costs, equitable provision of remote work tools, optimizing office space</p>
Economic Security	<p>Positive: Supports financial stability through secure remote work arrangements.</p> <p>Negative: Potential income disparities and economic insecurities if remote work lacks stability.</p>	<p>Positive: Supports business continuity and resilience, enhances organisational stability.</p> <p>Negative: Potential economic instability and reduced organisational cohesion if remote work is not effectively managed.</p>	<p>SDGs 1, 8, 9, 10: Mitigate through fair compensation, job security, robust remote work policies, and fostering organisational cohesion</p>
Job Satisfaction	<p>Positive: Enhances job satisfaction by providing flexibility, autonomy, and improved work environments.</p> <p>Negative: Risk of dissatisfaction if workers feel isolated, unsupported, or if their needs are unmet.</p>	<p>Positive: Improves employee retention and engagement through flexible and satisfying work arrangements.</p> <p>Negative: Potential for job dissatisfaction if remote work arrangements are not adequately supported.</p>	<p>SDGs 3, 8, 10: Mitigate by providing support and recognition, fostering inclusion, and maintaining regular feedback</p>

<p>Productivity</p>	<p>Positive: Promotes productivity by allowing work in environments tailored to individual needs.</p> <p>Negative: Decreased productivity if remote work lacks structure, clear goals, or adequate support.</p>	<p>Positive: Increases productivity and innovation through flexibility and efficiency.</p> <p>Negative: Potential inefficiencies if remote work technology and processes are inadequate or if there is a lack of management support.</p>	<p>SDGs 8, 9: Mitigate by setting clear goals, investing in technology and training, and implementing structured remote work policies</p>
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Table 41: Perspectives of employees and employers on RWAs, SDG alignment and mitigation strategies

In light of the findings of D1.3, **the following key strategic insights have been concluded**, each aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to guide effective decision-making in the evolving landscape of remote work:

- **Transforming Working Conditions** Remote work has reshaped organisational dynamics and individual roles. SDG Enhancing accessibility, adaptability, and digital skills (SDG4: Quality Education), while addressing taxation, labour laws, and unionisation is crucial to prevent inequalities SDG 10: Reduced inequalities; **SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth.**
- **Balancing job satisfaction with cultural cohesion** Remote work increases job satisfaction and autonomy but risks fragmenting work culture and widening disparities. Strategies should focus on equitable skills development and maintaining high-quality job experiences **SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure. SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions.**
- **Sustaining Organisational Engagement and Well-Being** These factors are key to positive mental health outcomes. A tailored Occupational safety and Health (OSH) framework is vital to address remote work health challenges **SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being as well as SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth.**
- **Impact on Living Conditions is significant**, Remote work alter access to essential services and environmental factors. Addressing location-based disparities through targeted policies is essential **SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities.SDG11: Sustainable cities and Communities**
- **Implementing Flexible Work Policies** Household dynamics, particularly caregiving responsibilities, influence the remote work experience. Flexible work policies that accommodate diverse family needs is

key to long-term success, supporting **SDG 5: Gender Equality**; SDG10: Reduces Inequalities; SDG1: No Poverty (labor participation)

- **Managing Work-Life Balance** and Its Trade-Offs Remote work can improve balance by reducing fatigue and stress, but longer working hours, may offset these benefits. Clear policies on flexible work arrangements and self-care practices are needed **SDG:3, SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth**.
- **Mitigating Health and Well-Being Risks** can lead loneliness, social isolation, and unstructured work environments. Comprehensive support systems, including OSH services, are necessary to promote overall well-being, **SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being. Promoting Positive Health Behaviours** Counteracting the negative effects of loneliness and social isolation is crucial. Targeted interventions to foster social connections, and positive health behaviours are needed **SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being**.
- **Addressing Gender-Specific Challenges** Gender norms significantly affect remote work experiences, Employing gender-sensitive policies is essential to address these disparities and foster inclusivity, supporting **SDG 5: Gender Equality**.
- **Addressing Ethical Considerations and Overwork** Remote work introduces new challenges related to working conditions, living conditions, work-life balance and health and well-being. Developing ethical guidelines and policies is key to ensure fairness, prevent exploitation, and promote sustainable productivity, in support of **SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions, as well as SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth**.
- **Reducing Disparities in Access** Significant disparities exist in RWAs. Enhancing infrastructure is necessary to ensure equitable access to tools, services, and career opportunities, particularly for workers in less developed regions, aligning with **SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities**,
- **Over all the findings, policies and potential solutions aligned with the goals of SDG 17: Strengthen and revitalised in global partnership.**

5.2 Accessibility -the key factor among determinants (WP2 Output)

In an evolving landscape of remote work, accessibility has emerged as a key factor in capacity building. Accessibility, in this context, extends beyond mere physical access to include digital, organisational, and cultural dimensions. As remote work becomes increasingly prevalent, it is essential to consider how different aspects of accessibility can enhance or hinder the capacity of organisations and individuals.

At the individual accessibility level, each employee's ability to effectively engage with their work environment, tools, and organisational resources, regardless of their location or personal circumstances, is important. This aspect of accessibility is crucial for ensuring that all employees can perform their roles efficiently and contribute meaningfully to the organisation (Biron et.al, 2022; Peretz, 2023, Levesque, 2013).

Remote work offers significant potential for improving individual-level accessibility. By allowing employees to work from locations that best suit their needs—whether due to physical disabilities, caregiving responsibilities, or geographic constraints—organisations can foster a more inclusive work environment. This flexibility not only enhances the work-life balance, but also ensures that talented individuals who might be unable to commute or relocate are still able to participate fully in the workforce.

For stakeholders with varying perspectives, accessibility in remote work has been receiving heightened attention. Employers, for example, are particularly focused on talent accessibility. In a remote work environment, the ability to attract and retain skilled professionals is crucial. This includes ensuring that job opportunities are accessible to a diverse pool of candidates, regardless of their location, and that digital platforms are inclusive and user-friendly. Such accessibility is vital for maximising the potential of a global workforce, enabling organisations to tap into talent that would otherwise be unreachable in a traditional office setting.

Additionally, interdisciplinary and intercultural accessibility are becoming increasingly pivotal in remote work scenarios. The ability to collaborate across different fields of expertise and cultural backgrounds is essential for fostering innovation and creativity. Remote work platforms must therefore be designed to facilitate seamless communication and collaboration among team members from diverse locations and disciplines. This form of accessibility ensures that knowledge is shared effectively, and that teams can work together efficiently, regardless of geographical barriers.

Cross-company and cross-country accessibility are also critical in the context of remote work. As businesses expand their operations globally, the ability to navigate different regulatory environments, cultural norms, and market conditions becomes a key factor in their success. Remote work allows organisations to operate across borders with greater ease, but it also requires a robust architecture that supports accessibility in these diverse contexts. This includes not only technological infrastructure, but also policies and practices that promote inclusivity and equal access to opportunities.

Access is fundamental both to the determinants of remote work as well as the performance of system development. Identifying and addressing **the needs of stakeholders requires the recognition, assessment, and guidance of elements related to access diversity**, which facilitate the complex flows that arise from them.

In this regard, the **Levesque model propose operational concepts for approaches that consider the broad dimensions of access factors related to remote work**, integrating relevant elements (Levesque, 2013) (Figure 44).

Figure 44: Components of remote work-related access (adapted from Levesque, 2013)

Peretz evaluated perceived productivity and satisfaction with work-from home (WFH) (Peretz, 2023). Peretz found that employees from highly competent, meritocratic, and more labour-regulated institutional contexts demonstrate higher perceived productivity and satisfaction with working from home. The link between the institutional context and work-from-home effectiveness is more pronounced when employees' capacity to work from home is high (Peretz, 2023). Accessibility in remote work is a fundamental aspect of capacity building. Whether in terms of talent acquisition, interdisciplinary collaboration, or cross-border operations,

accessibility plays a crucial role in enabling organisations to thrive in a remote work environment. As the global workforce continues to shift towards remote and hybrid models, the emphasis on accessibility will become even more critical, making it a central consideration for organisations aiming to maximise their capacity and effectiveness.

Moreover, accessibility in the context of remote work is not limited to physical or technological aspects; it also extends to the beliefs and cultural norms within an organisation. The beliefs held by both employees and employers can significantly influence how accessible remote work truly is. For instance, beliefs about productivity, trust, and the value of face-to-face interaction can either enable or hinder the adoption of remote work practices. Addressing these underlying beliefs is crucial for enabling an inclusive and supportive remote work environment. Organisations must foster a culture that values flexibility, inclusivity, and trust, ensuring that all employees, regardless of their personal circumstances or cultural background, feel supported and empowered in their remote work arrangements. Remote workers continuously adjust their identities, boundaries, and relationships to meet their own needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness in their work and non-work roles, which enhances key outcomes and leads to further refinement of remote work practices (Biron et. al., 2022). The effectiveness of this adjustment is influenced by the national institutional frameworks (Peretz, 2023), and can be facilitated by addressing behavioural beliefs and norms. Even when organisations offer remote work programmes, employees often prefer to stay in the office rather than work from home. Laumer proposed an “employee remote work adoption model’ based on a literature review, identifying six beliefs that foster remote work adoption, including five beliefs that hinder it, and one normative and three control beliefs affecting the adoption of remote work. This model is intended to inform research and practice on successful remote work implementation (Laumer and Maier, 2021). This can be achieved through a dynamic process of remote work adjustment, where employees continuously craft their work and non-work roles to meet their needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness (Biron et. al., 2022). Normative beliefs include behavioural beliefs regarding efforts, performance, relationship quality, and control beliefs within the organisational and household contexts where employees operate.

Meeting employees' basic needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness can enhance their well-being and motivation. Schade evaluated affective well-being, motivation (work engagement, flow experience) and detachment from work and found that working from home primarily decreases relatedness of coworkers, while autonomy and competence stay at similar levels as before. It was reported that competence and experience when working from home predict better daily work engagement, flow, and affect. According to

the researcher, employees adapted well to working from home over the two-week study period, with daily well-being and motivation indicators showing improvement (Schade et. al., 2021). The relationship between psychological needs satisfaction and job satisfaction is moderated by whether the worker is a remote worker or an office worker (Brunelle and Fortin, 2021). A model is needed to serve as an integrated support by offering guidance for research and practice on remote work and its effective implementation. It might also be combined with the Levesque model in different levels of implementation (Laumer and Maier, 2021).

Accessibility model can be used as a basis for empirical studies and intervention programmes to help remote workers and organisations facilitate a smooth transition to remote work while ensuring work-life balance and performance:

Reduced Commuting: Employees value remote work since it decreases commuting time, reduces stress from traffic or public transportation, and allows more time for family or work tasks.

Increased Autonomy: Remote work is expected to offer greater control over schedules, enhancing coordination between work and personal responsibilities, leading to reduced stress and improved work-life balance.

Reduced Distraction: It is suggested that remote working may help to minimise office-related distractions.

Improved Work-Life Balance: Remote working may help to achieve a better balance between professional and personal life.

Family Dynamics refer to the interactions and relationships inside a family unit. The presence of family members during working hours might either facilitate or impede remote workers, depending upon household dynamics. According to Greenhaus and Powell (2016), the presence of family can provide support, but it can also result in disruptions and decreased productivity (Greenhaus and Powell, 2016). Murphy and Kreiner (2020) outlined effective strategies for managing the integration of family and distant work such as setting clear boundaries, limits and establishing consistent routines to minimise disturbances (Murphy and Kreiner, 2020). Van der Lippe and Lippényi (2020) examined the simultaneous influence of family dynamics and stressed the importance of devising techniques to regulate family interactions while working. According to Voydanoff (2005), effective communication within the family can mitigate the adverse consequences of having family members present during remote work (Voydanoff, 2005).

However, the shift to remote work also brings to light inequalities that can arise from differential access to resources. Not all employees have equal access to high-speed internet, ergonomic workspaces, or up-to-date technology. These disparities can exacerbate existing inequalities, as those without adequate resources may struggle to keep pace with their peers, leading to reduced productivity and job satisfaction. Ethically, organisations have a responsibility to address these disparities by providing the necessary tools and support to ensure all employees have an equal opportunity to succeed in a remote work setting.

In this context, some negative beliefs may hinder the adoption of remote work due to perceived challenges relating to various aspects of accessibility. These include **fear of social isolation, concerns about losing interactions with colleagues, fear of professional isolation, worries about being excluded from professional opportunities and interactions.**

Social Isolation: In a meta-analysis conducted in 2007, the researchers indicated that while remote working provides a certain degree of flexibility, it also carries the potential risk of diminished social connection. (Gajendran and Harrison, 2007). Engaging in remote work may result in social isolation, which detrimentally affects mental health and well-being as a consequence of diminished in-person connection. A systematic review has identified a number of factors associated with feelings of professional isolation among remote workers. The identified factors include the following: whether remote work is a choice, the necessity for social interaction, the extent of teleworking, and the distance from the main workplace. The research findings indicate that teleworkers who have opted for telework, have robust relationships with their managers, and have a diminished need for social interaction are less likely to experience feelings of isolation. Conversely, those who engage in telework for an extended period or reside at a distance from the central office are more likely to experience feelings of isolation, which can have a detrimental impact on job satisfaction and performance (Spilker and Breagh, 2021).

Fear of Role Conflicts refers to the anxiety about blurred boundaries between work and personal life, potentially affecting relationship quality with co-workers.

Furthermore, the digital divide points to yet another layer of inequality in remote work. Employees in rural or underserved areas may face significant challenges in accessing the digital infrastructure required for effective remote work. This can lead to further marginalisation of already disadvantaged groups. Addressing these issues requires a concerted effort from organisations to bridge the gap, whether through providing additional

resources, offering financial support for home office setups, or advocating for broader policy changes that improve digital access in underserved regions.

In a systematic review of evidence-based strategies and practical recommendations, Bartmann and colleagues suggest that improving the physical and mental well-being of remote workers can be achieved through work-life adjustments including active, interactive meetings, workplace modifications, combining exercise with fun activities, promoting healthy eating alternatives, providing financial incentives for these opportunities, organising counselling practices to support mental health, and strengthening social connections to combat loneliness (Bartmann et. al., 2022). Organisations are encouraged to tailor these strategies to their context to support availability of the health and well-being services of their remote workers.

The ethical responsibility of organisations extends to ensuring that remote work policies are inclusive and equitable across different demographic groups. For instance, women, particularly those with caregiving responsibilities, may face unique challenges in remote work environments. Organisations must be mindful of these challenges and design remote work policies that accommodate the diverse needs of their workforce, thereby promoting gender equality and preventing further entrenchment of existing inequalities.

The Levesque model can be adapted (as can be seen in Figure 44) to the needs of home-office workers by considering their individual needs such as achievement, affiliation, and power (Lévesque, 2013). While integrating the Levesque approach to the needs-based structuring of remote work, with a view to ensure the efficacy of preventive measures, it is essential to recognise the requirements of providers, organisations, institutions, and systems (Figure 45). This will facilitate the provision and accessibility of services at the population, community, household, and individual levels, thereby enabling the development of an effective model incorporating remote work-related components.

Figure 45: A conceptual framework of access related process and determiners of outcome assessment (adapted from Levesque, 2013)

The integration of the components derived from this report into Levesque’s conceptual framework, which focuses on access, combined with a comprehensive approach to health and well-being, will facilitate the development of a robust, tailored remote work model. The proposed model would enhance accessibility, bolster employee well-being, and stimulate productivity and satisfaction across the workforce. It would address the complexities of remote work by offering standardised principles while providing adaptable solutions that align with the diverse needs of stakeholders. Additionally, it would ensure compliance with global regulations and foster an equitable, participatory remote working arrangements and related culture that accommodates the diverse possibilities at individual, institutional, and regional levels.

Future Directions

Continued research and adaptive policies are required to fully understand and manage the evolving nature of remote work and its health implications. Formal flexible working arrangements and enhanced organisational justice can help mitigate the mixed effects of remote work (Sanders and Karmowska, 2020).

As remote work becomes more prevalent, understanding and addressing its impacts on working and living conditions is vital for health and well-being outcomes as well as for the long-term return on investment related to the workforce and sustainability of world of work. Organisations must navigate these challenges with informed, strategic approaches that support healthy and productive work environments (ILO, 2021a).

6 CONCLUSIONS

The transition to new forms of employment requires a concerted effort by all stakeholders to develop evidence-based practices that support the changing nature of work. Organisations can effectively manage the complexity of remote working and hybrid working models by focusing on common definitions, training support, family dynamics, work-life balance, health and safety, quality of work, technology support, gender equality as well as addressing issues such as loneliness, presenteeism, communication strategies, and by cultivating a new organisational culture that considers health behaviours, age and career development. This approach will ensure that the transition to new forms of employment is managed in a way that recognises the diverse needs of employees, while promoting the well-being and productivity of the workforce.

Work Location Dynamics

The transition to new forms of employment, in particular remote working and hybrid working models, present significant opportunities and challenges (Nijp et al, 2016). As these models gain traction, stakeholders need to develop clear, evidence-based practices to support the changing nature of work. This includes addressing potential impacts on working and living conditions, emerging health and well-being needs, and the need for shared theoretical perspectives and standardised terminology (Eurofound, 2021, 2023a).

The EWCTS data re-analysis provides a nuanced picture of the current employment landscape. Although the majority of employees work on-site (58 %), remote working (21.6 %) and hybrid forms of work (20.4 %) are widespread as well. Remote working and hybrid forms of work are more common in the UK and Scandinavian countries, while on-site work is more dominant in Eastern European countries including Kosovo. This country origin-based distribution highlights the need for region-specific policies to support different ways of working. While on-site workers are exposed to more physical stress and health risks, remote workers report a safer environment and better mental health. Remote working can offer extensive flexibility to women who prefer traditional roles, as well as to individuals facing commuting related disadvantages and part time workers. It has the potential to reduce or exacerbate inequalities, depending on factors such as individual circumstances, organisational policies, and systemic differences in the availability, acceptance, and opportunities of skills.

Technological and Organisational Support

It is imperative that the appropriate technological and organisational support is provided for remote working to reduce professional and social isolation (Beauregard et.al., 2019; Prasad et.al, 2023; Paul, 2022). Investment in robust communication technologies and the provision of necessary tools and resources to staff will facilitate effective remote working arrangements (Bell et.al., 2019).

Education Levels and Flexible Working

There exists a correlation between higher levels of education and increase in remote and hybrid working. Policies should support diverse educational professional backgrounds in remote and hybrid working environments to ensure inclusion and maximise the potential of the highly skilled workforce. Higher job satisfaction among remote and highly skilled hybrid workers can lead to better mental health and less stress. Improving career opportunities for women through training can promote gender equality in flexible working environments.

Organisational arrangement-related outcomes highlights both positive and negative impacts from the perspectives of employees and employers, with direct relevance to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Crawford, 2022; United Nations, 2015)

- **Costs:** While remote work reduces commuting costs and improves financial stability for employees, it can increase home energy expenses and lead to inequities. Employers benefit from reduced office costs but face increased expenses for remote work technology. These outcomes align with SDGs 1, 7, 8, and 9, suggesting the need for equitable cost-sharing strategies and financial support for home working.
- **Economic Security:** Secure remote work arrangements contribute to financial stability for employees and business continuity for employers. However, potential income disparities and economic insecurities can arise if remote work is unstable. These factors align with SDGs 1, 8, 9, and 10, indicating the importance of fair compensation, job security, and cohesive remote work policies.
- **Job Satisfaction:** Remote work can enhance job satisfaction through flexibility and autonomy, but it may also lead to dissatisfaction if workers feel isolated or unsupported. For employers, this means improved retention but also potential challenges if support for remote work is lacking. This outcome relates to SDGs 3, 8, and 10, highlighting the need for fostering inclusion and regular feedback.
- **Productivity:** Productivity can be boosted by tailored work environments and flexibility but can decline without proper structure and support. Employers see increased efficiency, but face risks if remote work systems are inadequate. This outcome is aligned with SDGs 8 and 9, underlining the need for clear goals, investment in technology, and structured remote work policies.

These findings underscore the importance of aligning organisational strategies with SDGs to optimise the benefits of remote work while mitigating potential drawbacks

Living Environment, Household Structure and Caregiving Responsibilities

It is important that flexible working policies are implemented to accommodate the varying compositions of housing, living conditions, environmental aspects, households and provide support for employees with caregiving responsibilities. This will assist employees in effectively balancing their professional and personal obligations, thereby promoting a healthier integration of work and personal life. The ability to work remotely, locally or in a hybrid form is strongly influenced by household structure and caregiving responsibilities. Flexible working policies that take account of different family dynamics and caregiving responsibilities are essential to help workers balance work and personal commitments. A better work-life balance and less stress for remote workers with family responsibilities leads to better mental health. Flexible working can help reduce the gender gap in work-life balance by enabling both men and women to better manage family responsibilities, considering that women often take on a greater share of caregiving responsibilities (Touzet, 2023).

Work-Life Interface

Supporting flexible working arrangements is crucial for improving employees' well-being and overall job satisfaction. Remote and hybrid working arrangements are associated with better work-life balance and lower levels of work-related fatigue. Reduced fatigue contributes to improved mental health and general well-being, largely due to a better work-life balance in remote and hybrid working. However, in contrast when high intensity and blurring boundaries persist, a complex and cyclical risk emerges, where the lack of clear support or separation between work and personal life exacerbates stress and undermines overall well-being. Availability and accessibility of supportive services including the right to disconnect, and counselling should be taken into consideration. The improvement of employee well-being and overall job satisfaction entails reduction of work-related fatigue and promotion of practices that support a healthy work-life balance (Wöhner, 2023). It is imperative that flexible working arrangements and regular breaks are in place to achieve this equilibrium (Beckel and Fisher, 2022; EU-OSHA 2023a; EU-OSHA, 2023b).

It is essential to prioritise the prevention of harm and the promotion of health in the workplace. This should include the implementation of preventive measures for both known and potential health risks (OECD, 2021). The provision of ergonomic support, accessible health and counselling services as well as comprehensive occupational health and safety programmes will enhance employee well-being (EU-OSHA, 2023a).

Quality of Work and Job Satisfaction

Quality of work is important for sustainable work (Eurofound, 2021b). Remote and hybrid working environments can provide greater autonomy, flexible working hours as well as enhanced learning opportunities, all of which contribute to higher job engagement, satisfaction and increased productivity. This improved job satisfaction is linked to reduced strain and improved mental health among remote and hybrid workers. Furthermore, enhancing the quality of work through remote arrangements can help to reduce gender and age disparities as well as address gaps with respect to job satisfaction and career progression.

Comprehensive technical and organisational support, along with specified measures of quality of working life, are needed to evaluate complex relationships effectively (Wheatley, 2021; Azarbouyeh and Jalali, 2014). **The success of remote working depends to a large extent on adequate technological and organisational support.** Investment in communication technologies and the development of a formal flexible working policy can help to reduce the professional and social isolation, often associated with quality of work in RWAs. Improved engagement and mental health can be a result of reduced feelings of isolation, achieved through better communication, leadership, structured management, virtual team skills, technology and organisational support (Bell et.al., 2019; Beaugard et.al.,2019; Biea et.al, 2023; Prasad et.al, 2023; Paul, 2022). Better technological support can help ensure that women, who need to have equal access to remote jobs. The implementation of policies that facilitate the creation of high-quality employment opportunities, coupled with autonomy and the provision of learning opportunities, will serve to enhance overall job satisfaction, engagement and productivity (De Carvalho et al., 2022; Mazzetti et al, 2021).

Loneliness and Social Isolation

Remote and hybrid working can lead to feelings of loneliness; however, while loneliness and social isolation are interconnected, they are distinct aspects of social connectedness. Although isolation is not a necessary condition for loneliness, it might significantly increase its likelihood if not managed appropriately (Sullivan and Bendell, 2023). Strategies to maintain social connections among remote workers are crucial. Reduced feelings of loneliness and social isolation improves mental health through better social connections associated with engagements, well-being. The prevention of social isolation and the maintenance of social connections among remote workers is of paramount importance for the mental health and well-being of these individuals. Loneliness is the subjective experience of perceiving ones' social relationships as insufficient, which might stem from issues relating to disrupted information flow and connectedness. The deployment of strategies such

as regular virtual team meetings, social events, and opportunities for face-to-face interaction can serve to mitigate feelings of isolation but might not help loneliness. Therefore, it is important to establish connectedness through relevant strategies (Bartmann et. al., 2022).

Gender-based and individual needs related inequalities:

Tackling loneliness can be particularly beneficial for women, people with disabilities, and individuals who may suffer more from isolation when working remotely (Lyttelton et. al., 2020). It is important to provide career development opportunities for all age groups and to ensure that remote working does not impede career growth. The formulation of inclusive career development strategies for both younger and older workers will facilitate the addressing of the specific needs of different age groups in remote and hybrid working environments. It is of the utmost importance to address gender differences and cater to gender needs in the context of remote working through the formulation of gender-sensitive policies (Touzet, 2023; Sullivan and Lewis 2002). The adaptation of support programmes to address the specific challenges faced by different gender groups will facilitate the promotion of equality and inclusion (Cannito and Scavarda, 2020; Castro-Trancon et.al, 2024; de Laat, 2023;).

Presenteeism

Presenteeism, or working while ill, is a critical factor to consider in remote and hybrid working environments. There should be policies in place to prevent presenteeism and to encourage employees to take the necessary sick leave for their full recovery. By reducing presenteeism and promoting appropriate use of sick leave, health outcomes can be improved, and sickness absence can be minimised. Women in particular may be more affected by presenteeism due to their caregiving responsibilities, rendering supportive measures crucial. The phenomenon of ‘presenteeism,’ where employees work despite being ill—must be addressed in organisational policies (Shimura et.al, 2021) . It is essential to provide support for employees in taking the necessary sick leave to ensure their recovery and prevent the transmission of illnesses to others. The implementation of policies that discourage presenteeism and the provision of adequate health support will enable employees to recuperate fully.

Leadership Management and Communication

Effective management and open communication are critical to the success of remote and hybrid working models. Managers need to be trained to manage remote teams, set clear expectations, and provide regular

feedback. Better mental health and reduced anxiety and health and well-being through effective management and open communication. Effective management can help address gender issues in remote working and promote a more inclusive environment. It is essential that managers develop the skills required to effectively manage remote teams and ensure clear communication and alignment with organisational goals. It is recommended that managers be trained and that transparent communication guidelines be developed in order to avoid misunderstandings and improve team cohesion (Kwon and Jeon, 2018; Jin and Ikeda, 2024; Bell et.al, 2019).

Information Flow and Engagement

Better and clear information flow improve mental health and reduce anxiety (Anand, 2024). Overall health and well-being outcomes can be enhanced through effective management and open communication. Effective management can help address gender issues in remote working and promote a more inclusive environment (Garro-Abarca et. al., 2021; Schröder et. al., 2021; Handke et. al., 2020).

Promotion of Healthy Behaviours and Mental Health Support for Remote Workers

It is of the utmost importance to promote healthy behaviours, prevent chronic diseases and provide mental health support for remote workers. It is recommended that employees take regular breaks, engage in physical activity, adopt a healthy diet, and have access to mental health resources to enhance their overall well-being (Schall and Chen, 2022; Perega, 2024; Park et.al., 2020;)

It is essential to achieve a consistent understanding and reliable research findings using standardised research terminology and common definitions. The implementation of standardised research methodologies will ensure consistency across studies ((WHO/ILO, 2021; ILO, 2024; Beckel and Fisher, 2022).

The transition to 'RWAs' from an 'inclusive' perspective, particularly through hybrid working models, enables a smoother shift with significant benefits, such as increased productivity, better work-life balance, and greater job satisfaction (Golden and Gajendran, 2019; Ozimek, 2020). However, it also presents challenges related to individual working conditions, organisational services, employment contract types and employment relations in all levels of system dynamics, as well as preventive OSH concept and practices concerning health and well-being (EU-OSHA, 2024b; Sanders and Karmowska, 2020; Buomprisco et. al., 2021). This includes challenges in communication, management culture with uncertainties at work (Prasad, 2023). By addressing these challenges through well-designed policies and support systems, stakeholders can maximise the benefits of

remote work and foster a fairer and more productive working environment (Shade,2021; Bentley et. al., 2023). Aligning these strategies with the SDGs can promote equitable growth that benefits both individuals and the society at large.

6.1 Key Action Points (WP2 output)

The following key action components are essential for developing a remote work model based on the Levesque framework:

- Establishing shared terminology and concepts: It is crucial to establish mutually accepted concepts and terminology to support interdisciplinary research and collaboration. This will ensure a coherent understanding of the complexities of remote work.
- Standardised approaches are vital for enhancing individual access to remote work as well as related opportunities, improving employer access to diverse talent, and ensuring compliance with global regulations. These measures will help prevent the emergence of new inequalities and underpin evidence-informed policies.
- Hybrid work and tailored solutions: The hybrid work model offers the flexibility to formulate tailored, consensus-based solutions that cater to the diverse needs of stakeholders, ensuring adaptability to various contexts and individual circumstances.
- Comprehensive employee services: Organisations must provide comprehensive employee services to foster engagement, commitment, satisfaction, and productivity. This includes strategies to prevent a non-attached work culture, ensuring that remote workers remain connected and engaged.
- Pre-emptive Occupational Health and Safety: A new approach to occupational health and safety is needed, focusing on awareness of rights and responsibilities under international regulations. This should address all elements of the bio-psycho-social components of health and well-being, as defined by WHO, ensuring full support for remote workers.
- Mental health and well-being: Addressing mental health and well-being is critical for preventing loneliness in the workplace. As mental health significantly impacts productivity, job satisfaction, and motivation, it should be a key component of any remote work model.

- **Work-life balance framework:** A clear conceptual framework for evaluating the quality of working life is essential, particularly in assessing the unique aspects of remote work. Such a framework will help organisations and stakeholders acquire the knowledge and skills required to navigate remote work effectively, considering the work-to home, and home-to-work components as an integrated buffer.
- **Inclusive and tailored approach:** The model must adopt a diverse, inclusive, equitable and individualised approach to address gender dimension and prevent social exclusion. Tailoring the model to meet diverse needs ensures it is equitable and accessible to all.
- **Ethical considerations:** Ethical considerations are integral to the development and application of remote work models. Organisations must ensure data privacy and security, equitable treatment of all employees, and respect for work-life boundaries. Additionally, ethical responsibility encompasses ensuring that remote work does not exacerbate social inequalities or lead to new forms of exclusion.

By integrating these components within Levesque’s conceptual framework, along with strong ethical considerations, organisations can devise a robust remote work model that enhances access, supports employee well-being, and promotes productivity and satisfaction across all levels of the world of work.

Table 42 presents the key points for measurement and monitoring indicators.

Key Points for WP2	Needed to measure and monitor
<p>It is essential to establish mutually accepted terminology and concepts for interdisciplinary research.</p>	<p>Definitions and Terminology, (Appendix.1)</p>
<p>To bridge gaps and prevent the persistence of new forms of inequalities, it is crucial to develop standardised approaches that enhance individual access to remote work, improve employer access to talent, and ensure compliance with inter-organisational and global regulations for evidence-informed policies. Accessibility concept for remote work</p>	<p>Levels of inequalities Levels of accessibility</p>
<p>A new concept is needed for pre-emptive occupational health and safety services that emphasises awareness of rights and responsibilities under international regulations, rather than relying solely on outsourced services, as remote work encompasses all elements of the bio-psycho-social components of health defined by the WHO.</p>	<p>Support and capacity coverage level of OSH</p>
<p>To foster engagement, commitment, satisfaction, and productivity, organisations must implement comprehensive employee services and prepare strategies that actively prevent a non-attached work culture.</p>	<p>Quality Level communication and information flow Engagement level Level of commitment</p>
<p>A conceptual model presents micro, mezzo, and system level associations that prevent loneliness in the workplace Conceptual framework for work-life balance</p>	<p>Long term follows up health outcome indicators Loneliness vs social isolation</p>
<p>Hybrid work has highlighted the potential for developing tailored, consensus-based solutions that effectively address the diverse needs of stakeholders.</p>	<p>WFH-HFW adaptability level: Work-life balance conceptual framework</p>
<p>A clear conceptual framework for evaluating the quality of working life is essential, particularly to assess the distinctive components of remote work within this approach.</p>	<p>Remote Quality of work index needed /Job quality indicators and psycho-social factors</p>
<p>The concept of remote working arrangements necessitates the development of awareness and training programmes to enhance remote work literacy.</p>	<p>Awareness level/ Potential effects of RWAs on the form and nature of employment</p>
<p>The accessibility of services can be enhanced by adapting Levesque's conceptual framework, which provides a comprehensive model for understanding and improving access.</p>	<p>Accessibility level in the system</p>
<p>gender and individual needs based-inclusive and tailored approach is essential to address gender dimensions while ensuring that individuals are not socially excluded.</p>	<p>Tailoring score/ Potential effects of RWAs on individual needs and gender lens</p>
<p>To promote an employee friendly, work-life harmony-based services planning to promote healthy working conditions and environment, organisations should implement flexible working arrangements with clear policies and guidelines on work hours, communication, and availability by adopting an inclusive approach that encourages employees to set boundaries and prioritise self-care as well.</p>	<p>Clear policy and procedures Employee friendly RWAs settings score: 1- organisational aspects; 2- individual aspects</p>
<p>Organisations should invest in leadership development by providing training and support for managers to cultivate effective leadership styles that emphasise empathy, communication, and trust-based management in leading remote and flexible teams.</p>	<p>Supportive Leadership level Monitoring measure Sustainability level</p>
<p>New ethical dimensions of new types of employments for stakeholder's new research area, Non-attached working related theoretical gap</p>	<p>Job insecurity and non-attached working styles vulnerability index)</p>
<p>Presenteeism as an early sign of mental health outcomes (e.g. burn-out,)</p>	<p>Presenteeism acceptability score</p>

Table 42: Key Action Points: List of Key Performance Indicators

6.2 Emerging needs and action points

1. Workplace dynamics

Emerging needs:

- Develop individual, organisational, regional, and needs-based strategies to support different working arrangements.
- Address the cross-country principles of different distribution of job types, skills, opportunities, and possibilities.
- Address the specific challenges and benefits of remote, hybrid and on-site working environments.

Action points:

- Conduct regional assessments to understand specific working pattern needs.
- Implement policies that support both remote and on-site working according to individual, organisational, regional, and need-based requirements.
- Assess infrastructure, facilities, access, awareness, and acceptance of remote and hybrid workers to ensure equal access to necessary resources and provide necessary support.

2. Training and capacity building on RWAs

Emerging needs:

- Create and support opportunities for different levels of education and income in remote and hybrid working environments.
- Ensure inclusion and maximise the potential of the highly skilled workforce.

Action points:

- Provide training and development programmes suitable for remote and hybrid working environments.
- Promote continuous learning and professional development for all levels of education.

3. Household structure and caregiving responsibilities

Emerging needs:

- Responding to different locations of living, family dynamics and caregiving roles.
- Helping workers to balance work and personal responsibilities effectively.

Action points:

- Implement flexible working policies to accommodate different household compositions.
- Provide support for employees with caregiving responsibilities, such as flexible working hours and remote working options.

4. Work-life balance

Emerging needs:

- WFH and HFW supportive policies

- Improve employee well-being and overall job satisfaction.
- Reduce work-related fatigue and improve work-life balance.

Action points:

- Promote flexible working where possible in a tailored way.
- Encourage practices that support a healthy work-life balance, such as regular breaks and manageable workloads.

5. Health and well-being

Emerging needs:

- Prioritise harm prevention and health promotion in the work environment.
- Address preventive planning for known and potential health risks associated with different work environments.

Action points:

- Provide ergonomic support and accessible health and counselling services for remote workers.
- Implement health and safety policies that cover both on-site and remote workers.
- Develop comprehensive occupational health and safety programmes that include preventive approaches to physical inactivity, nutrition, sleep, counselling, and mental health promotion services. Create a new holistic and inclusive framework.

6. Quality and satisfaction in work

Emerging needs:

- Enhance the overall quality of work and foster a positive culture of responsibility by respecting boundaries in all aspects and encouraging a upholding mutual values within society.
- Promote a working environment that supports to employee development and encourages engagement.

Action points:

- Promote autonomy, flexible working and learning opportunities in remote and hybrid working environments.
- Devise policies that support high quality jobs and career development.

7. Technological and organisational support

Emerging needs:

- Provide appropriate technological and organisational support for remote working.
- Enhance the professional and social connectedness associated with remote work.

Action points:

- Invest in robust communication technologies.
- Ensure that staff have the tools and resources they need to do their job effectively.

- Increase awareness and acceptability of services

8. Gender dimensions

Emerging needs:

- Address gender differences, needs and approaches to address inequalities and promote gender needs in remote working.
- Ensure that remote work arrangements are equitable and beneficial for all staff.

Action points:

- Formulate inclusive policies that advance diversity equality and inclusion.
- Adapt support programmes to address the specific challenges faced by individuals with different characteristics.

9. Loneliness and social isolation

Emerging needs:

- Prevent social isolation and maintain social links among remote workers.
- Establish clear policies on information flows and opportunities.
- Support the mental health and well-being of remote workers.
- Recognise the issues of loneliness, attachments needs, and diverse requirements of individuals.

Action points:

- Devise strategies not only regular virtual team meetings and social events but support information flow and accessibility.
- Encourage opportunities for face-to-face interaction where possible.
- Adopt servant leadership and debriefing policies that address anxiety.

10. Presenteeism

Emerging needs:

- Reduce the tendency for employees to work while ill.
- Support employees to take the necessary sick leave to fully recover.

Action points:

- Devise policies to discourage presenteeism.
- Provide adequate sick leave and health support for employees.

11. Management and communication

Emerging needs:

- Develop management skills to effectively manage remote teams.
- Ensure clear communication and alignment with organisational goals.

Action points:

- Train managers in best practices for managing remote teams.
- Develop transparent communication guidelines to avoid misunderstandings.

12. Healthy behaviours and mental health

Emerging needs:

- Promote healthy behaviours and provide mental health support for remote workers.
- Monitor mental health outcomes and provide necessary resources.

Action points:

- Promote regular breaks, physical activity, and healthy eating among remote workers.
- Provide access to mental health resources and support programmes.

13. Common theoretical perspectives and standardised terminology

Emerging needs:

- Achieve consistency in understanding and ensure reliable research findings.
- Standardise research terminology and develop common definitions.

Action points:

- Develop and apply standardised research methodologies.
- Ensure consistency of terminology used in different studies.

14. Age and career development

Emerging needs:

- Support career development opportunities for all ages.
- Ensure that remote working does not hinder career development.

Action points:

- Develop inclusive career development strategies for both younger and older workers.
- Address the specific needs of different age groups in remote and hybrid working environments.

By focusing on these emerging needs and challenges, stakeholders can facilitate the creation of a supportive and productive work environment that benefits both employees and organisations. The alignment of these efforts with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including the promotion of good health and well-being, quality education, gender equality, decent work and economic growth, and the reduction of inequalities, will ensure that all workers and society at large can benefit from the changing nature of work. Such an approach will facilitate fair and green economic growth, thereby ensuring a sustainable and

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APPENDICES:

Appendix 1: Definitions of key terminology

A.1.1 Terminology related to employment

- **Employment relationship**¹⁶ refers to the legal and negotiated contact between a worker and their employer, which guarantees equitable treatment regarding working conditions, social protection, and training ([Eurofound Employment relationship](#)).
- **Non-standard employment**¹⁷ is an umbrella term for different arrangements that deviate from standard employment. They include temporary employment, part-time and on-call work, temporary agency work, other multiparty employment relationships, disguised employment and dependent self-employment. The most pertinent prospective developments in non-standard work, regardless of their contractual form, are related to the process of digitalisation ([ILO Non-standard forms of employment](#)).
- **A Part-time worker** is an employed person whose normal hours of work are less than those of comparable full-time workers (Eurofound, 2011).
- **Home-work** is defined as 'Work performed by a person (i) at home or at any place of his/her choice other than the place of work of the employer; (ii) for remuneration; (iii) which results in a product or service as specified by the employer, irrespective of who provides the equipment, materials or other inputs used' by ILO Convention No. 177, Art. 1. This definition does not extend to persons who 'have the necessary degree of autonomy and economical independence to be considered as self-employed workers under national laws, regulations or judicial decisions' (ILO, 1996).
- **Industrial home-work** differs from the above definitions and refers to goods production undertaken by homeworkers either as part of, or replacing, factory production, but also artisanal production, such as in the making of handicrafts is not included in this report but should be considered, as indicated by ILO (ILO, 1996).
- **Home-based digital platform work** refers to service-sector tasks performed by 'crowd workers' according to the employer's or intermediary's specifications in situations in which the workers lack the autonomy and economic independence to be considered independent workers in national legislation.
- **Sustainable work**¹⁸ refers to establishing circumstances that facilitate persons' ability to stay employed for the entirety of their working life. The process entails modifying tasks to accommodate individuals' specific requirements and capabilities to guarantee the standard of work.
- **Gender equality**¹⁹ refers to equality between women and men with respect to their rights, treatment, responsibilities, opportunities, and economic and social achievements. Gender equality is achieved when men and women have the same rights, responsibilities and opportunities across all sections of society and when the different interests, needs and priorities of men and women are equally valued.

¹⁶<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/employment-relationship>

¹⁷<https://www.ilo.org/topics/non-standard-forms-employment>

¹⁸<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/sustainable-work>

¹⁹<https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/gender-equality>

- **Ageing workforce²⁰**: The Ageing population and related employment, working conditions, and welfare difficulties requires the deployment of new strategies at many levels to enhance job prospects for older people.

A.1.2 Terminology related to working conditions and organisational arrangements

- **Working conditions²¹** encompass the environment and attributes of a job that can be improved. This includes a broad spectrum of issues, from employment characteristics to work processes. It covers both structural conditions provided by the employer and individual conditions, such as benefits, earnings, rights and responsibilities related to job duties. Economic aspects and their effects on living situations, governed by laws, agreements, contracts, and customs, are also integral to this scope.
- **Work organisation²²** is about the division of labour, coordination and control of work: How work is divided into job tasks, bundling of tasks into jobs and assignments, interdependencies between workers, and how work is coordinated and controlled to fulfil the goals of the organisation. It encompasses the tasks performed, who performs them and how they are performed in the process of making a product or providing a service. Work organisation thus refers to how work is planned, organised as well as responsibilities, task allocation, work scheduling, work pace, rules and procedures, and decision-making processes. Work organisation involves division and coordination of work, focusing on tasks, assigning responsibilities and implementing management procedures to achieve an organisation's objectives. The components are job design, allocation of responsibilities, distribution of tasks and decision-making procedures (Eurofound Work organisation).
- **Work arrangements** accepted as a type of occupational exposure, which is defined as physical work-related factors, psycho-social and organisational work-related factors (O'Connor A, 2020) and the health and well-being-related outcomes evaluated under the titles: physical health, mental health, social and family, work-related needs, and health behaviours (EU-OSHA, 2023a).
- **Health and well-being services at work²³** means promoting high standards of working conditions, providing health and safety services to improve health and safety at work, and upholding workers' rights to better health and well-being. It is a key priority for the EU The EU Directive on measures to improve health and safety at work aims to protect workers at work and promote their rights in this area (EU, 1998).

A.1.3 Terminology related to job quality

Job quality²⁴ refers to the evaluation of employment practices, with a specific focus on the features of a job that have an impact on an individual's health and overall well-being. The analysis encompasses both favourable and unfavourable occupational characteristics, considering physical, psychological, social, and organisational factors (Eurofound Job quality). Job quality indicators is defined in six parts in 2015 and seven

²⁰ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/ageing-workforce>

²¹ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/working-conditions>

²² <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/work-organisation>

²³ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/health-and-well-being-work>

²⁴ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/job-quality>

parts in the Eurofound 2021 report. These are physical and social environment, work intensity, skills and discretion, job tasks, organisational characteristics, working time quality arrangements, job prospects, social environment, earnings. These are defined as **Job Quality indicators and are listed below (Eurofound, 2021b)**:

- **The working environment** refers to the location of work and associated factors, including physical, biological, chemical, ergonomic, and ambient conditions (Eurofound, 2023a). It also encompasses the social environment, which includes factors like adverse social behaviours, social support, and the quality of management.
- **Working time quality** includes duration, atypical working time, working time arrangements, flexibility, **Working time**²⁵ refers to any period during which an employee is engaged in their job responsibilities for their employer, as determined by the laws or customs of the country. Working hours differ among different occupations, life phases, and genders ([Eurofound Working time](#)).
- **Work intensity** refers to the effort and strain associated involved in carrying out the work; quantitative demands, pace determinants and interdependencies, emotional demands are included in this aspect (Rodríguez-Modroño, 2022; Eurofound, 2024).
- **Job security** is defined as having a job that gives some control over the content of the job, what the worker does, and the opportunity to build a career. Job security includes sense of ownership of one's work, while employment security also includes commitments to an existing structure (ILO, 2022).
- **Job demands** are any physical, psychological, social or organisational aspects of a job that require continuous physical and/or mental (e.g. cognitive or emotional) effort.
- **Employee training**²⁶ is important for developing and expanding workers' skills, to enable them to adapt to new job requirements and to be employable throughout their lives. Evidence suggests that the availability of training opportunities at work also increases overall job quality.
- **Work-related flexibility** is an umbrella term that is most widely accepted as a term for time flexibility, often used in the context of the EU employment and industrial relations, but its meaning is contested. Temporal flexibility includes work schedules, working hours, entering and leaving the labour market, options for managing individual responsibilities, e.g. unexpected caregiving responsibilities; flexibility in employment structures includes career path, type of contract; flexibility in choice of benefits; flexibility in location of work (Jeffrey Hill et. al., 2008).

Understanding quality indicators in work and working conditions through a common framework allows for a more accurate assessment of employment practices and their impact on workers' health and well-being. This standardisation supports the development of policies and interventions that address the specific needs of diverse types of employment, promoting equity and improved job satisfaction.

Psycho-social factors in the workplace are defined as the combination of psycho-social risk²⁷ associated with work organisational and personal factors (excessive workload, conflicting demands and lack of role clarity, lack of involvement in decision-making, lack of influence, poorly managed organisational change, job insecurity, ineffective communication, lack of support from manager or colleagues, psychological sexual harassment and

²⁵ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/topic/working-time>

²⁶ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/skills-learning-and-employability>

²⁷ <https://osha.europa.eu/en/themes/psychosocial-risks-and-mental-health>

difficult customers, etc.) modifying their potential outcome, which are studied to improve the health and well-being of employees (EU-OSHA 2024a; Eurofound, 2024; Stansfeld et. al., 2006).

Psychological hazards will be used in this report to refer the potential psychological or physical factors that may result from how work is designed, managed, and influenced by the social setting. Work-related stress, a widespread health hazard in Europe, can arise from a range of factors, including job content, work intensity, autonomy, working hours, right to disconnect, work-life balance, social environment, job instability, and career advancement.

Work-related boundaries Including professional boundaries, spatial, temporal, relational, cognitive; refers to clear working-time, place, demands, sources, liabilities and some yet undefined boundaries related to work (Rothbard and Ollier, 2016).

- **Boundaries of working time** refers to looking at the nature of work to distinguish between working time, rest periods and on-call time, especially for live-in workers (ILO, 2021b). In the absence of clear schedules, working time can be highly unpredictable. The need to define boundaries for workers to work longer hours and be constantly available for work leads to an erosion of rest periods. It is therefore important to define and regulate different periods of work by classifying the boundaries of working time to prevent long working hours (Voydanoff, 2005; ILO, 2022).

The right to disconnect²⁸ refers to a worker's right to be able to disengage from work and not engage in work-related electronic communications, such as e-mail or other messages, during non-working hours. This concept has evolved because of advances in communication technologies and their impact on people's ability to work.

A.1.4 Terminology related to outcomes of organisational aspects

- **Organisational commitment** refers to the degree of attachment an employee feels towards their organisation and work. It is recognised as a link between the individual and their employer, and a related response to the organisation as a whole. Behavioural consequences of such commitments include lower rates of absenteeism, better job performance, lower staff turnover and fewer plans to change jobs — the latter two of which tend to be relatively high among employees on fixed-term contracts (Eurofound, 2008; Davis et al., 2024).
- **Work engagement** refers to employee's relationship with his or her work, whereas **employee engagement** can also include the relationship with the organisation (Schaufeli, 2013). Work engagement is an important variable in studies investigating the relationship between well-being and quality of working life and occupational health psychology (Mazzetti et al., 2021; Sinclair et. al., 2013).
- **Job satisfaction** simply refers to how people feel about their jobs and the various aspects of it. It is the extent to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs (Spector, 1997; Eurofound, 2006). Job satisfaction is a subjective, personal state perceived by the individual as being in his/her favour; and while there is no doubt that humanisation of work may contribute to job

²⁸ <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/european-industrial-relations-dictionary/right-disconnect>

satisfaction, it should not be assumed that humanisation of work will ensure generation or maintenance of job satisfaction (Fraser, 1983; Thompson and Phua, 2012).

Appendix 2: LDA and BERTopic topic modelling

A.2.1 Search string

***Scopus® Search strategy:** (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Telework*" OR "Flexible Work*" OR "Hybrid Work*" OR "Remote* Work*" OR telecommut* OR "Virtual work*" OR "work* from home" OR "Remote employment" OR "Flexible work* arrangements" OR "Work* flexibility" OR "non* standard work*" OR "home* office" OR "future of work" OR "distribut* work" OR "async* work" OR "return to office" OR "digital nomad*" OR "work* remot*" OR "remote job*" OR "work from anywhere" OR "work* online" OR "smart work" OR "distance work" OR "remote agile work" OR "E-work" OR "home* based work*" OR "virtual employment" OR "mobile work*" OR "online work*" OR "off* site work*" OR "asynchronous work" OR "cloud work*" OR "work*remote*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("work* hours" OR "work position" OR "job status" OR "Access to support" OR "job demand" OR "work* demands" OR "Work* Stress" OR "work* location" OR "Work* Condition" OR "work* environment" OR "commute to work" OR "social security" OR "Social insurance" OR "income security" OR "Job Security" OR "income" OR "Job Stability" OR "Health Services" OR "Occupational Health and Safety" OR "Occupational Safety and Health" OR "Occupational health" OR "Employee Health" OR "Employee service" OR "Social Service" OR "Self* help" OR "social support" OR "Turnover" OR "Work*life interf*" OR "Autonomous work" OR "Opportunity" OR "Organi*ational justice" OR " work participation" OR "Engagement" OR "Commitment" OR "Satisfaction" OR "Quality of work* life" OR "Living condition*" OR "Resident* Selection" OR "home arrangement*" OR "Social Condition" OR "Resident* preference" OR "Resident* Characteristic*" OR "accommodation preference*" OR "living arrangement*" OR "residential mobility" OR "infrastructure" OR "workspace at home" OR "leisure space") AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Nurse") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Engineering Education") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Communicable Disease Control") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Physician") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Clinical Article") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Information Management") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Medical Education") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Teaching") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Health Care") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Patient Care") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Coronavirus") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Economics") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Artificial Intelligence") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Human Engineering") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Cloud Computing") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Telemedicine") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"E-learning") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Adolescent") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"COVID-19 Pandemic") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Covid-19") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Students") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Health Care Personnel") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"SARS-CoV-2") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Major Clinical Study") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Pandemics") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Coronavirus Disease 2019") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"COVID-19")) AND (EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE,"bk") OR EXCLUDE (DOCTYPE,"ch")) AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA,"NURS") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA,"BIOC") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA,"PHAR")))

*The coverage of Scopus has the broadest coverage of any interdisciplinary abstract and citation database.
<https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/scopus>

A.2.2 Initial hierarchical clusters after elimination of duplications reconfigured

App.Supl.Figure 1. BERTopic Modelling Hierarchical clusters

A.2.3 Supplementary Figures related to BERTopic

App.Supl.Figure 2: Similarity matrix of the identified topics

App.Supl.Figure 3: Inter-topic distance map of remote work-related literature in BERTopic

Appendix 3: Supplementary of EWCTS re-analysis findings:

A.3.1 Distribution of work locations by country

App.Supl.Figure 4: Distribution of working location by country

App.Supl.Figure 5: Gender based distribution of working location by country

App.Supl.Figure 6: Number of articles by years between 2000-2024 based on the classification of BERTopic analysis (Articles from Covid-19 period were excluded)

A.3.2 Doing Housework, caregiving responsibilities

Unlike the previous two sections, graphs in this section represent the total distribution of each category compared to the overall distribution of options, and the location of work distribution for each option. Additionally, it is important to mention that for each option, labels with proportions (labels on the graph) represent the proportion of working location categories.

App.Supl.Figure 7: Distribution of housework responsibilities according to work location and gender

As presented in Figure 7, among men, daily housework is more common in remote workers (26.6%) compared to on-site workers (17.9%). Conversely, a significant portion of men working on-site (52.7%) report never engaging in housework. Similarly, among women, daily housework is more prevalent among remote workers (22.4%) than on-site workers (15.9%). However, a majority of on-site women (56.7%) report never doing housework, highlighting a similar pattern to that observed in men. These findings suggest that remote work may be associated with a higher likelihood of daily housework engagement, while on-site work is more often linked to a lack of participation in housework duties.

Regarding the distribution of childcare responsibilities, **60.3%** of men who never engage in childcare are on-site workers, **20.0%** are remote workers, and **19.7%** are hybrid workers. Among women, the majority of those who never engage in childcare are on-site workers (56%), with daily childcare being more common among remote (20%) and hybrid (21%) female workers (Supplementary Figure 8).

App.Supl.Figure 8: Distribution of childcare responsibilities according to gender and work locations

App.Supl.Figure 9:Distribution of the caregiving responsibilities for relatives according to gender and work location

Regarding the distribution of the caregiving responsibilities for close relatives, 58.7% of all men without such responsibilities work on-site, whereas 71.2% of all men with daily relative care responsibilities work on-site. For women, while 57.2% of women who do not have any responsibility for relative care work on-site, it is 66.7% for those who have daily relative care duties. For both men and women, the frequency of responsibility for caregiving for relatives is less frequently distributed among remote or hybrid workers (Figure 9).

Working at Night:

App.Supl.Figure 10: Distribution of work locations according to night work

As presented in Figure 10, those who always work at night are predominantly on-site workers (77.5%). People who rarely work at night have the highest ratio for remote (29.9%) and hybrid (27%) options combined.

A.3.3 Work life balance graphic

App.Supl.Figure 11: Distributions of work-life balance according to the work locations and gender

App.Supl.Figure 12: Distribution of worrying about work, by work location regarding gender

When it comes to the distribution of worry about work, among men, among those who always worry are predominantly on-site workers (55.2%), followed by hybrid (28.4%) and remote (16.4%) workers. Among women, among those who always worry about work are primarily on-site workers (49.7%), followed by hybrid (27.4%) and remote (22.9%) locations. For both men and women, those who ‘rarely’ or ‘never’ worry about work are mostly on-site workers, making up 71.3% and 70.8 respectively (Figure 12).

App.Supl.Figure 13: Distribution of work location according to gender and feelings of tiredness

Among men, those who always feel tired at work are predominantly on-site workers (69.1%), followed by remote (14.6 %) and hybrid (16.3 %) workers. Similarly, among women, those who always feel tired at work are mainly on-site workers (65.4%), while remote (16.1%) and hybrid (18.5%) workers comprise a smaller proportion. For both men and women, those who ‘rarely’ or ‘never’ feel tired at work include a higher proportion of remote workers, compared to those who ‘always’ feel tired (see Figure 13).

App.Supl.Figure 14: Distribution of work location according to feelings of difficulty in concentrating at work in gender groups

Regarding difficulty concentrating at work, among men, those who always have difficulty concentrating at work are most often on-site workers (69%), with remote (15%) and hybrid (15%) workers less common. Among women, those who always had difficulty concentrating at work were most common among on-site workers (65%), less common among remote (16%) and hybrid (18%) .

Men and women who always experience difficulty concentrating at work are most frequently found in on-site settings, with remote and hybrid work being less common. Conversely, those who rarely or never have difficulty concentrating are still mostly on-site but include a relatively higher proportion of remote workers, indicating that remote work might be associated with fewer concentration difficulties

App.Supl.Figure 15: Distribution of Job Quality indicators: Autonomy, Flexible working time, Intrinsic reward, self-realisation, social support, learning and development

App.Supl.Figure 16: Distribution of Job Quality Variables: Job insecurity, work intensity, physical demands, Social discrimination, Unsocial working tim

A.3.4 Technical explanations about analytical findings

Tables in this section present summary statistics of the key variables, along with the p-values for remote-workplace and remote-hybrid frameworks. Each table is structured as a list table, displaying the number and percentage of each option for each variable:

- The total 'n' values represent the number of individuals who chose that option. In contrast, the 'n' values for the remote, workplace, and hybrid categories indicate the distribution according to the remote-workplace-hybrid framework. Total percentages show the distribution of options as a percentage.
- Percentages within the working type categories reflect the distribution of each working location category within the option. Consequently, the percentage values within each working location category sum to 100% within each option, whereas the percentage values for each option in the total column also add up to 100%. This approach is used consistently across the five tables.

Regarding the p-values, we aim to **assess the association between different working locations:** remote/workplace- office and remote/hybrid. We conducted two separate chi-square tests and obtained two P-values to achieve this. One test evaluates the relationship between remote working and on-site working, where the hybrid option is included in the remote working category for the analysis. The other test examines the relationship between remote working and hybrid working. The results of these tests are presented separately in the tables. It is important to consider these statistics based on the cross-sectional design and not with an adjustment, standardisation to compare or generalize with the other population. Only represent this result referent population.

When reporting the results, we denote values very close to 0 (i.e., those with three or more zeros after the decimal point) as '~0'. Conversely, results are reported as 0, only if they are precisely 0 without any decimals.

CODEBOOK

Dependent Variables: Constructed two regression models are summarise; each model includes 1 dependent variable. These dependent variables and their categories are as follows:

loc_work_adjusted_binary

This variable is constructed through the loc_work_adjusted variable. The difference between these two is that this variable consists of office-remote options, and the hybrid option is included in the remote category.

Two regression models use this variable as a dependent variable, the difference between these two models is that one includes the variable URBANITY, while the other does not. 0 = remote 1 = workplace/office

burnout_emot: 0 and 1

Independent Variables

Before building up the model, each variable had to be adjusted so to obtain more accurate results. Four types of variables exist in the dataset: dummy variables, categorical variables, ordinal categorical variables, and a continuous variable.

The dummy variables are leaved as it is (JQ_CD_insecrty, JQ_CD_intensty, JQ_CD_physdemd, JQ_CD_socdiscr, JQ_CD_unsocial, JQ_CR_autonomy, JQ_CR_flexwork, JQ_CR_socsuppt, JQ_CR_intrinsc, JQ_CR_realistn, JQ_CR_training, JQ_CD_physrisk, strain_high).

The categorical variables and ordinal categorical variables are turned to dummies keeping one of their categories as a reference.

Lastly, there is one continuous variable (hh_size_total) which is left as it is.

gender_recoded

1 = Man (Reference Value) 2 = Woman

age_groups

1 = 16-24 (Reference Value); 2 = 25-34 ; 3 = 35-44 ; 4 = 45-55 ; 5 = 56+

Job Quality indicators: **JQ_CD_insecrty:** 0 1 ; **JQ_CD_intensty:** 0 1; **JQ_CD_physdemd:** 0 1; **JQ_CD_socdiscr:** 0 1; **JQ_CD_unsocial :** 0 1; **JQ_CR_autonomy:** 0 1; **JQ_CR_flexwork:** 0 1; **JQ_CR_socsuppt:** 0 1; **JQ_CR_intrinsc:** 0 1; **JQ_CR_realistn:** 0 1; **JQ_CR_training:** 0 1; **JQ_CD_physrisk:** 0 1

strain_high: 1 = FALSE (Reference Value); 2 = TRUE

work_life_balance.

1 = Very well (Reference Value); 2 = Well; 3 = Not very well; 4 = Not at all well

ps_dummy_encoded.

private_sector is coded as 1, the rest of the options are 0. The "other" option taken as a reference value.

part_time: 1 = Part time (Reference Value) 2 = Full time

seniority_cat: 1 = Less than a year (Reference Value); 2 = 1 to 4 years; 3 = 5 to 9 years; 4 = 10 or more

night work: 1 = Never (Reference Value); 2 = Rarely; 3 = Sometimes; 4 = Often; 5 = Always

freetime_work: 1 = Daily (Reference Value); 2 = Several times a week; 3 = Several times a month; 4 = Less often; 5 = Never

able_hour_off: 1 = Very easy (Reference Value); 2 = Fairly easy; 3 = Fairly difficult; 4 = Very difficult

presenteeism_dummy: Yes, option is coded as 1, No option is 0. Other options are deleted from the data.

No option is taken as a reference value.

boss_gender: 1 = A man (Reference Value) 2 = A woman

useICT: 1 = no (Reference Value); 2 = yes

hh_size_total: Continuous variable from 1 to 20.

long_hours: 1 = 48 hours or more (Reference Value); 2 = less than 48 hours per week

noise_jq: 1 = High (Reference Value); 2 = Low

A.3.5 Supplementary of demographic characteristics and work location related findings

Gender and age group distributions according to work location are shown in Table 14. Workplace/on-site work was highest among the 16–24-year age group, followed by the 45+ and 25-34 age groups, respectively in this population. 35–44-year age group had significantly highest ratios to be employed in remote & hybrid work types combined. Remote work was slightly but significantly different and higher among all age groups except the 45–55-year age group compared to hybrid work setting.

The chi-square test shows a significant association between remote and workplace working settings, when the hybrid category is included in the remote working category ($P \sim 0$). Additionally, there is a significant association between remote and hybrid working for this age group ($P = 0.002$).

	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	N	%	n	%	N	%	N	%		
Gender										
Female	7228	22.1	18641	56.9	6864	21	32733	49.4	~0	0.661
Male	7101	21.1	19818	59.0	6671	19.9	33590	50.6		
Age										
16-24	670	13	3865	74.9	628	12.2	5163	7.8	~0	0.002
25-34	3449	22.6	8711	57.2	3071	20.2	15231	23		
35-44	4196	23.9	9464	53.9	3913	22.3	17573	26.5		
45-55	3665	20.8	10216	58	3730	21.2	17611	26.6		
56+	2307	21.7	6152	57.9	2160	20.3	10619	16		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

App.Suppl.Table 1: Gender and age group distributions according to work location

Urban Distribution:

For urbanity, no significant associations are observed for both workplace -remote and remote-hybrid comparisons (App.Suppl.Table 2). Among individuals in urban areas, 16.1% work remotely, 69.6% work in the workplace, and 14.3% work in a hybrid model. For those in rural areas, 16.9% work remotely, 70.5% work in the workplace, and 12.6% work in a hybrid model. The total sample consists of 71.8% from urban areas and 28.2% from rural areas. **Household size shows a significant association between remote and workplace work.**

	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	N	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Urbanity										
Urban	762	16.1	3295	69.6	677	14.3	4734	71.8	0.508	0.091
Rural	314	16.9	1308	70.5	234	12.6	1856	28.2		
Household Composition ***										
Single no children	2337	23.2	5746	57	1991	19.8	10074	15.2	0.027	
Single with children	398	21.9	1008	55.4	412	22.7	1818	2.7		
Two adults no children	4211	24.2	9539	54.8	3663	21	17413	26.3		
Two adults with children	3990	24.2	8756	53.1	3737	22.7	16483	24.9		
More than two adults no children	2318	16.7	8975	64.9	2546	18.4	13839	20.9		
More than two adults with children	1075	16.1	4435	66.2	1186	17.7	6696	10.1		
Household Size (Total)										
1	2338	23.2	5750	57	1991	19.8	10079	15.2	~0	
2	4444	24.1	10121	54.8	3893	21.1	18458	27.8		
3	2885	19.9	8633	59.4	3015	20.7	14533	21.9		
4	3266	21.6	8686	57.4	3170	21	15122	22.8		
5	1022	18.8	3350	61.6	1067	19.6	5439	8.2		
6+	374	13.9	1919	71.3	399	14.8	2692	4.1		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										
*** The categories are grouped according to having a child or not before conducting the analysis.										

App.Suppl.Table 2: Association of urbanity and household characteristics with work location

Household Composition:

For individuals single without children, 23.2% work remotely, 57.0% work in the workplace, and 19.8% work in a hybrid model. For individuals single with children, 21.9% work remotely, 55.4% work in the workplace, and 22.7% work in a hybrid model. For households with two adults and no children, 24.2% work remotely, 54.8% work in the workplace, and 21.0% work in a hybrid model. For households with two adults and children, 24.2% work remotely, 53.1% work in the workplace, and 22.7% work in a hybrid model. For households with more than two adults and no children, 16.7% work remotely, 64.9% work in the workplace, and 18.4% work in a hybrid model. For households with more than two adults and children, 16.1% work remotely, 66.2% work in the workplace, and 17.7% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates a significant association between household composition and working locations ($P = 0.027$).

Household Size:

The data indicates that as household size increases, there is a general trend towards a higher proportion of on-site work and a lower proportion of remote work. Hybrid work remains relatively consistent across different household sizes. **Working remote and hybrid combined was significantly different among households with one person (43%) and two persons (45.2%) and lowest among households with 6+ persons (28.7%).**

Time Spent on Childcare:

For individuals who provide daily childcare, 20.7% work remotely, 57.6% work in the workplace, and 21.7% work in a hybrid model (App.Suppl.Table 4). The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Those who never provide childcare, 23.2% work remotely, 58.3% work in the workplace, and 18.4% work in a hybrid model. People with no childcare duty had significantly the highest ratios for working remotely (23.2%) compared to hybrid (18.4%). Also, reporting was less often associated with the lowest ratios (38.2%) for remote & hybrid combined work locations.

	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	P*	P**
Childcare duties										
Daily	2218	20.7	6166	57.6	2320	21.7	10704	34.9	~0	~0
Several times a week	791	19.2	2483	60.3	844	20.5	4118	13.4		
Several times a month	541	20.6	1529	58.3	552	21.1	2622	8.5		
Less often	603	18.5	2018	61.9	641	19.7	3262	10.6		
Never	2318	23.2	5817	58.3	1838	18.4	9973	32.5		
Caregiving for relatives										
Daily	355	14.7	1662	68.7	401	16.6	2418	7.7	~0	~0
Several times a week	561	16.8	2066	62	707	21.2	3334	10.		
Several times a month	775	22.3	1917	55.1	789	22.7	3481	11.2		
Less often	962	22.3	2397	55.6	955	22.1	4314	13.8		
Never	3969	22.5	10243	58	3453	19.5	17665	56.6		
Housework duties										
Daily	4439	23.9	10308	55.6	3794	20.5	18541	56.6	~0	~0
Several times a week	1716	20.7	4782	57.6	1801	21.7	8299	25.3		
Several times a month	341	16.3	1338	63.9	414	19.8	2093	6.4		
Less often	272	13.7	1381	69.3	339	17	1992	6.1		
Never	182	10	1380	75.8	259	14.2	1821	5.6		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

App.Suppl. Table 3: Time allocated for caregiving and housework distributions according to the work location

Time Spent on Caregiving for Relatives:

For individuals who care for their relatives daily, 14.7% work remotely, 68.7% work in the workplace, and 16.6% work in a hybrid model. Those who care for relatives several times a week, 16.8% work remotely, 62.0% work in the workplace, and 21.2% work in a hybrid model. For those caregiving for relatives several times a month, 22.3% work remotely, 55.1% work in the workplace, and 22.7% work in a hybrid model. Individuals who care for relatives less often, 22.3% work remotely, 55.6% work in the workplace, and 22.1% work in a hybrid model. Those who never care for relatives, 22.5% work remotely, 58.0% work in the workplace, and 19.5% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test shows significant associations between remote and workplace working (P ~0) and between remote and hybrid working (P ~0).

There was a 10% difference in working from the workplace between people who provided daily relative care daily (68%) and people who had no relative care duty (58%).

Additionally, people with daily or several times a week relative care duty have significantly higher ratios for hybrid work, compared to remote work. Similarly, people with no relative care duties had significantly higher ratios for working remotely compared to hybrid work.

Time Spent on Housework:

For individuals who do housework daily, 23.9% work remotely, 55.6% work in the workplace, and 20.5% work in a hybrid model. Those who do housework several times a week, 20.7% work remotely, 57.6% work in the workplace, and 21.7% work in a hybrid model. For those doing housework several times a month, 16.3% work remotely, 63.9% work in the workplace, and 19.8% work in a hybrid model. Individuals who do housework less often, 13.7% work remotely, 69.3% work in the workplace, and 17.0% work in a hybrid model. Of those who never do housework, 10.0% work remotely, 75.8% work in the workplace, and 14.2% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

A.3.5 Supplementary of Work life characteristics related findings

Sector type	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
The private sector	9711	23.2	24412	58.2	7809	18.6	41932	64	~0	
The public sector	3071	17.1	10483	58.4	4387	24.5	17941	27.4		
A joint private-public organisation	621	23.6	1397	53.1	613	23.3	2631	4		~0
The not-for-profit sector or NGOs	413	31.1	593	44.7	322	24.2	1328	2		
Other	410	24.2	951	56.1	333	19.7	1694	2.6		
Employment Type										
Employee	12125	21	34112	59.1	11468	19.9	57705	87.4	~0	0.852
Self-Employed	2118	25.5	4178	50.3	2017	24.3	8313	12.6		
Part Time/Full Time										
Part-time	2327	21.3	6719	61.5	1886	17.3	10932	16.6	~0	~0
Full-Time	11895	21.6	31499	57.3	11580	21.1	54974	83.4		
Seniority										
Less than a year	1439	18.4	5199	66.6	1174	15	7812	11.8	~0	
1 to 4 years	4870	23.3	12028	57.5	4011	19.2	20909	31.6		~0
5 to 9 years	2698	22.6	6708	56.2	2531	21.2	11937	18		
10 or more	5285	20.7	14430	56.6	5780	22.7	25495	38.5		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

App.Suppl.Table 4: Work location according to the work life characteristics

Work Experience (seniority): For individuals with **less than one year of work experience, 15.0% work remotely, 68.0% work in the workplace, and 17.0% work in a hybrid model (App.Suppl.Table 5)**. Of those with 1-3 years of work experience, 17.5% work remotely, 60.0% work in the workplace, and 22.5% work in a hybrid model. For individuals with 4-7 years of experience, 20.0% work remotely, 55.0% work in the workplace, and 25.0% work in a hybrid model. Of those with 8-10 years of experience, 22.0% work remotely, 53.0% work in the workplace, and 25.0% work in a hybrid model. For individuals with over ten years of experience, 24.0% work remotely, 51.0% work in the workplace, and 25.0% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working (P ~0) and between remote and hybrid working (P = 0.003).

Significant associations are found between remote and on-site working (work location variable is workplace) and between remote and hybrid working across different levels of work experience.

Results underscore the importance of considering work-related variables such as the work experience, job sector, and income level when analysing remote working trends. Different job sector type and income levels exhibit distinct patterns of remote, workplace, and hybrid work, which are crucial for policymakers and organisations to understand and address effectively.

Sector type: In the private sector, 23.2% work remotely, 58.2% in the workplace, and 18.6% in a hybrid model. In the public sector, 17.1% work remotely, 58.4% in the workplace, and 24.5% in a hybrid model. For joint private-public organisations, 23.6% work remotely, 53.1% work in the workplace, and 23.3% work in a hybrid model. In the not-for-profit sector or NGOs, 31.1% work remotely, 44.7% work in the workplace, and 24.2% work in a hybrid model. In other sectors, 24.2% work remotely, 56.1% work in the workplace, and 19.7% work in a hybrid model.

The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Working from workplace was significantly more common among public (58.4%) and private (58.2%) sector workers, while it was lowest among workers in the not-for-profit sector, or NGOs (44.7%). In the context of off-site work locations, the public sector had the lowest ratio (17.1%), and the NGOs had the highest ratio (31.1%) for remote work locations. Also, the private sector had the lowest ratio (18.6%) for hybrid work locations. The difference between hybrid and remote work arrangements were found to be statistically significant.

Employment Type: Among employees, 21.0% work remotely, 59.1% work in the workplace, and 19.9% work in a hybrid model. Among self-employed individuals, 25.5% work remotely, 50.3% work in the workplace, and 24.3% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test shows a significant association between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$), but no significant association between remote and hybrid working ($P = 0.852$).

While working from the workplace compared to remote and hybrid combined was significantly higher among employees (59.1%) rather than self-employed (50.3%), there was no statistically significant difference between remote and hybrid work location ratios for employees and self-employed people.

Part-Time/Full-Time Employment:

Among part-time workers, 21.3% work remotely, 61.5% work in the workplace, and 17.3% work in a hybrid model. Among full-time workers, 21.6% work remotely, 57.3% work in the workplace, and 21.1% work in a

hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Part-time workers had significantly higher ratios for working from the workplace rather than remote and hybrid combined compared to full-time workers. In the off-site working context, full-time workers had significantly higher ratios for hybrid working rather than remote working compared to part-time workers.

Seniority: For those with less than a year of experience, 18.4% work remotely, 66.6% work in the workplace, and 15.0% work in a hybrid model. For those with 1 to 4 years of experience, 23.3% work remotely, 57.5% work in the workplace, and 19.2% work in a hybrid model. For those with 5 to 9 years of experience, 22.6% work remotely, 56.2% work in the workplace, and 21.2% work in a hybrid model. For those with 10 or more years of experience, 20.7% work remotely, 56.6% work in the workplace, and 22.7% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test shows significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Boss Gender:

For individuals with a female boss, 21.6% work remotely, 58.2% work in the workplace (on-site), and 20.2% work in a hybrid model. For individuals with a male boss, 20.8% work remotely, 59.7% work in the workplace, and 19.5% work in a hybrid model (**App.Suppl.Table 6**).

The chi-square test shows significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) but no significant association between remote and hybrid working ($P = 0.955$).

Effects of Computerised Systems

For individuals, whose work is influenced by computerised systems 27.8% primarily work remotely, 49.0% work in the workplace, and 23.2% work in a hybrid model. Those influenced to some extent, 20.3% work remotely, 56.9% work in the workplace, and 22.8% work in a hybrid model. For those less influenced, 17.7% work remotely, 62.2% work in the workplace, and 20.1% work in a hybrid model.

Individuals not influenced at all, 12.8% work remotely, **74.0% work in the workplace**, and 13.2% work in a hybrid model. For those to whom this does not apply, 12.4% work remotely, 75.9% work in the workplace, and 11.7% work in a hybrid model.

The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Using Computer:

For individuals who use a computer, 26.6% work remotely, 49.2% work in the workplace, and 24.2% work in a hybrid model (**App.Suppl.Table 6**). **For those who do not use a computer, 3.7% work remotely, 91.1% work in the workplace, and 5.2% work in a hybrid model.** The chi-square test shows significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P = 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	N	%	N	%	n	%	N	%		
Boss Gender										
Woman	4503	21.6	12153	58.2	4218	20.2	20874	37	~0	0.955
Man	7378	20.8	21191	59.7	6924	19.5	35493	63		
Computerized System Effects (influence_computer)										
To a large extent	4329	27.8	7628	49	3615	23.2	15572	47.2	~0	~0
To some extent	1378	20.3	3869	56.9	1550	22.8	6797	20.6		
Not much	774	17.7	2719	62.2	879	20.1	4372	13.3		
Not at all	467	12.8	2701	74	481	13.2	3649	11.1		
This doesn't apply to my work situation	320	12.4	1954	75.9	302	11.7	2576	7.8		
Using Computer										
Yes	13708	26.6	25375	49.2	12507	24.2	51590	82.	0	~0
No	397	3.7	9789	91.1	563	5.2	10749	17.2		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

App.Suppl.Table 5:Boss gender, Influence computerised system and computer use by work location

Working at Night:

For individuals who never work at night, 20.3% work remotely, 60.5% work in the workplace and 19.2% work in a hybrid model (**App.Suppl.Table 7**). Those who rarely work at night, 29.9% work remotely, 43.0% work in the workplace, and 27.0% work in a hybrid model. For those who sometimes work at night, 23.9% work remotely, 53.7% work in the workplace, and 22.4% work in a hybrid model. Individuals who often work at night, 16.1% work remotely, 67.0% work in the workplace, and 16.9% work in a hybrid model. Those who always work at night, 10.9% work remotely, 77.5% work in the workplace, and 11.6% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P = 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P = 0.047$).

Significant associations are found between remote and workplace working and between remote and hybrid working across different frequencies of working at night.

Working at night	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	N	%	N	%	n	%	N	%		
Never	8342	20.3	24913	60.5	7910	19.2	41165	62.1	0	0.047
Rarely	3268	29.9	4699	43	2953	27	10920	16.5		
Sometimes	1623	23.9	3655	53.7	1524	22.4	6802	10.3		
Often	876	16.1	3642	67	917	16.9	5435	8.2		
Always	213	10.9	1521	77.5	228	11.6	1962	3		

App.Suppl.Table 6: Working at night according to the work location

A.3.6 Work-Life Interface Results

As presented in **App.Suppl.Table 8, working during free time**: For individuals who work daily during their free time, 23.1% work remotely, 47.3% work in the workplace, and 29.6% work in a hybrid model. Of those who work several times a week during their free time, 27.9% work remotely, 43.1% work in the workplace, and 29.0% work in a hybrid model. For those who work several times a month during their free time, 26.6% work remotely, 47.1% work in the workplace, and 26.3% work in a hybrid model.

Ability to work in free time: Of individuals who work less often during their free time, 23.9% work remotely, 55.5% work in the workplace, and 20.5% work in a hybrid model. Of those who never work during their free time, 13.4% work remotely, 74.9% work in the workplace, and 11.7% work in a hybrid model (**App.Suppl.Table 8**).

The chi-square test shows significant associations between remote & hybrid combined working and workplace working (P = 0) and between remote and hybrid working (P ~0).

	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		p*	p**
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Ability to work in free time										
Daily	804	23.1	1646	47.3	1028	29.6	3478	5.3	0	~0
Several times a week	2497	27.9	3852	43.1	2587	29	8936	13.6		
Several times a month	3325	26.6	5899	47.1	3293	26.3	12517	19.1		
Less often	4691	23.9	10895	55.5	4027	20.5	19613	29.9		
Never	2800	13.4	15712	74.9	2461	11.7	20973	32		
Working during sickness (presenteeism)										
Yes	4921	25.5	9929	51.5	4437	23	19287	29.1	~0	0.012
No	8627	19.9	26276	60.7	8383	19.4	43286	65.4		
I was not sick	764	20.9	2184	59.9	700	19.2	3648	5.5		
Ability to take time off										
Very easy	6961	28.1	12589	50.9	5197	21	24747	37.8	~0	~0
Fairly easy	5654	21.3	15258	57.5	5620	21.2	26532	40.5		
Fairly difficult	1108	13.7	5370	66.3	1619	20	8097	12.4		
Very difficult	515	8.3	4635	75.1	1023	16.6	6173	9.4		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

App.Suppl.Table 7: Ability free time scheduling according to the work location

Working with an Illness (Presenteeism):

- For individuals who worked with an illness, 25.5% work remotely, 51.5% work in the workplace, and 23.0% work in a hybrid model (**App.Suppl.Table 8**).
- Of those who did not work with an illness, 19.9% worked remotely, 60.7% worked in the workplace, and 19.4% worked in a hybrid model.
- For those who were not sick, 20.9% worked remotely, 59.9% worked in the workplace, and 19.2% worked in a hybrid model.
- The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P = 0.012$).

A.3.7 Details of WHO-5 Well-being items findings

Variable	Remote		Workplace		Hybrid		Total		p*	p**
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Feeling cheerful and in good spirits										
All of the time	1893	14.3	9170	69.4	2148	16.3	13211	20	~0	~0
Most of the time	6064	22.4	15190	56.1	5832	21.5	27086	40.9		
More than half of the time	3649	25.2	7530	52.1	3286	22.7	14465	21.9		
Less than half of the time	1413	26.2	2877	53.4	1094	20.3	5384	8.1		
Some of the time	1149	22	3052	58.4	1027	19.6	5228	7.9		
At no time	137	17.4	529	67.1	122	15.5	788	1.2		
Feeling calm and relaxed										
All of the time	1461	14.8	6992	70.8	1418	14.4	9871	14.9	~0	0.002
Most of the time	4694	21.6	12446	57.3	4575	21.1	21715	32.8		
More than half of the time	3538	24.6	7642	53.1	3224	22.4	14404	21.8		
Less than half of the time	2263	24.8	4893	53.6	1976	21.6	9132	13.8		
Some of the time	1924	22.3	4873	56.4	1845	21.3	8642	13.1		
At no time	422	17.7	1488	62.4	475	19.9	2385	3.6		
Feeling active and vigorous										
All of the time	1657	14.2	8137	69.7	1883	16.1	11677	17.7	~0	~0
Most of the time	4997	21.3	13507	57.6	4957	21.1	23461	35.5		
More than half of the time	3502	24	7808	53.5	3290	22.5	14600	22.1		
Less than half of the time	2140	27.2	4025	51.1	1715	21.8	7880	11.9		
Some of the time	1660	23.9	3912	56.3	1381	19.9	6953	10.5		
At no time	343	21.9	948	60.5	277	17.7	1568	2.4		
Waking up feeling fresh and rested										
All of the time	1562	15.6	6846	68.5	1587	15.9	9995	15.1	~0	0.401
Most of the time	4375	22.4	11066	56.6	4115	21	19556	29.6		
More than half of the time	2869	23.2	6781	54.9	2699	21.9	12349	18.7		
Less than half of the time	2369	24	5290	53.5	2221	22.5	9880	14.9		
Some of the time	2190	22.2	5659	57.3	2032	20.6	9881	14.9		
At no time	934	20.9	2678	60	854	19.1	4466	6.8		
Daily life is filled with things that are interesting										
All of the time	1975	16.7	7790	65.8	2070	17.5	11835	17.9	~0	~0
Most of the time	5162	22.1	13115	56.1	5110	21.8	23387	35.4		
More than half of the time	3274	23.9	7334	53.6	3072	22.5	13680	20.7		
Less than half of the time	1845	24.6	4157	55.4	1495	19.9	7497	11.4		
Some of the time	1756	22.1	4701	59	1505	18.9	7962	12.1		
At no time	276	16.7	1133	68.7	240	14.6	1649	2.5		
* P Value for Workplace vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

App.Suppl.Table 8: Distributions of WHO-5 Well-Being Scale's responses according to work location

WHO-5 well-being questionnaire includes self-reported five statements, inquiring the following feelings within the last two weeks.

1. Feeling cheerful and in good spirits (WHO-5 Cheerfulness).
2. Feeling calm and relaxed (WHO-5 Calmness).
3. Feeling active and vigorous (WHO-5 Active).
4. Waking up feeling fresh and rested (WHO-5 Rested).
5. Daily life is filling with things that interesting (WHO-5 Interested).

The 5-Point Likert Scale include six response options from 0-5 including 'All the time', 'Most of the time', 'More than half of the time', 'Less than half of the time', 'Some of the time', 'At no time'. The raw score is calculated by totalling the figures of the five answers. The raw score ranges from 0 to 25, 0 representing worst possible and twenty-five representing best possible quality of life. To obtain a standardised percentage score ranging from 0 to 100, the raw score is multiplied by four. A standardised score of 0 represents worst possible whereas a score of 100 represents best possible quality of life.

Interpretation of the App.Suppl.Table 9 can be seen below:

WHO-5 Cheerfulness: For individuals who feel cheerful all of the time, 14.3% work remotely, 69.4% work in the workplace, and 16.3% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel cheerful most of the time, 22.4% work remotely, 56.1% work in the workplace, and 21.5% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel cheerful more than half of the time, 25.2% work remotely, 52.1% work in the workplace, and 22.7% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel cheerful less than half of the time, 26.2% work remotely, 53.4% work in the workplace, and 20.3% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel cheerful some of the time, 22.0% work remotely, 58.4% work in the workplace, and 19.6% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel cheerful at no time, 17.4% work remotely, 67.1% work in the workplace, and 15.5% work in a hybrid model.

The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace/on-site working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

WHO-5 Rested: For individuals who feel relaxed all of the time, 14.8% work remotely, 70.8% work in the workplace, and 14.4% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel relaxed most of the time, 21.6% work remotely, 57.3% work in the workplace, and 21.1% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel relaxed more than half of the time, 24.6% work remotely, 53.1% work in the workplace, and 22.4% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel relaxed less than half of the time, 24.8% work remotely, 53.6% work in the workplace, and 21.6% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel relaxed some of the time, 22.3% work remotely, 56.4% work in the workplace, and 21.3% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel relaxed at no time, 17.7% work remotely, 62.4% work in the workplace, and 19.9% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates

significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P = 0.002$).

WHO-5 Active: For individuals who feel active all of the time, 14.2% work remotely, 69.7% work in the workplace, and 16.1% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel active most of the time, 21.3% work remotely, 57.6% work in the workplace, and 21.1% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel active more than half of the time, 24.0% work remotely, 53.5% work in the workplace, and 22.5% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel active less than half of the time, 27.2% work remotely, 51.1% work in the workplace, and 21.8% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel active some of the time, 23.9% work remotely, 56.3% work in the workplace, and 19.9% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel active at no time, 21.9% work remotely, 60.5% work in the workplace, and 17.7% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

WHO-5 Rested: For individuals who feel rested all of the time, 15.6% work remotely, 68.5% work in the workplace, and 15.9% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel rested most of the time, 22.4% work remotely, 56.6% work in the workplace, and 21.0% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel rested more than half of the time, 23.2% work remotely, 54.9% work in the workplace, and 21.9% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel rested less than half of the time, 24.0% work remotely, 53.5% work in the workplace, and 22.5% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel rested some of the time, 22.2% work remotely, 57.3% work in the workplace, and 20.6% work in a hybrid model. For those who feel rested at no time, 20.9% work remotely, 60.0% work in the workplace, and 19.1% work in a hybrid model.

The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) but no significant association between remote and hybrid working ($P = 0.401$).

WHO-5 Interested: For individuals who find their work interesting all of the time, 16.7% work remotely, 65.8% work in the workplace, and 17.5% work in a hybrid model. For those who find their work interesting most of the time, 22.1% work remotely, 56.1% work in the workplace, and 21.8% work in a hybrid model. For those who find their work interesting more than half of the time, 23.9% work remotely, 53.6% work in the workplace, and 22.5% work in a hybrid model. For those who find their work interesting less than half of the time, 24.6% work remotely, 55.4% work in the workplace, and 19.9% work in a hybrid model. For those who find their work interesting some of the time, 22.1% work remotely, 59.0% work in the workplace, and 18.9% work in a hybrid model. For those who find their work interesting at no time, 16.7% work remotely, 68.7% work in the workplace, and 14.6% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and workplace working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$).

Other Well-being variables	Remote		Office		Hybrid		Total		P*	P**
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Worrying about work (at home)										
Never	1043	14.9	4972	71.2	973	13.9	6988	21.2	~0	~0
Rarely	1700	23.2	4132	56.4	1492	20.4	7324	22.2		
Sometimes	2219	24.6	4833	53.5	1983	21.9	9035	27.4		
Often	1835	26.3	3359	48.2	1779	25.5	6973	21.1		
Always	477	17.8	1607	60	595	22.2	2679	8.1		
Feeling tired after work										
Never	1125	21.2	3289	62	892	16.8	5306	16.1	~0	~0
Rarely	2119	25.1	4452	52.6	1886	22.3	8457	25.7		
Sometimes	2410	21.9	6237	56.6	2378	21.6	11025	33.5		
Often	1398	21.3	3745	57.1	1417	21.6	6560	19.9		
Always	223	13.9	1137	70.7	249	15.5	1609	4.9		
Concentration problems at work										
Never	1948	17.9	7046	64.7	1891	17.4	10885	33	~0	~0
Rarely	2603	22.7	6219	54.3	2636	23	11458	34.8		
Sometimes	1926	24.8	4091	52.7	1744	22.5	7761	23.5		
Often	691	30	1149	50	460	20	2300	7		
Always	90	16	378	67.4	93	16.6	561	1.7		
* P Value for Office vs Remote & Hybrid combined										
** P Value for Remote vs Hybrid										

App.Suppl.Table 9: Distribution of the responses for the certain well-being variables according to work location

Worrying about work (at home): For individuals who never worry about work, 14.9% work remotely, 71.2% work in the office, and 13.9% work in a hybrid model. For those who rarely worry about work, 23.2% work remotely, 56.4% work in the office, and 20.4% work in a hybrid model. For those who sometimes worry about work, 24.6% work remotely, 53.5% work in the office, and 21.9% work in a hybrid model. For those who often worry about work, 26.3% work remotely, 48.2% work in the office, and 25.5% work in a hybrid model. For those who always worry about work, 17.8% work remotely, 60.0% work in the office, and 22.2% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and office working (P ~0) and between remote and hybrid working (P ~0). Significant associations are found between remote and office working, and between remote and hybrid working, across various levels of worry about work. These results

highlight the impact of well-being concerns on the choice of working location. Understanding these factors can help organizations create supportive work environments that address employees' well-being and reduce their worries.

Feeling tired after work: For individuals who never feel tired after work, 21.2% work remotely, 62.0% work in the office, and 16.8% work in a hybrid model. For those who rarely feel tired after work, 25.1% work remotely, 52.6% work in the office, and 22.3% work in a hybrid model. For those who sometimes feel tired after work, 21.9% work remotely, 56.6% work in the office, and 21.6% work in a hybrid model. For those who often feel tired after work, 21.3% work remotely, 57.1% work in the office, and 21.6% work in a hybrid model. For those who always feel tired after work, 13.9% work remotely, 70.7% work in the office, and 15.5% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and office working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$). Significant associations are found between remote and office working, and between remote and hybrid working, across various levels of tiredness after work.

Concentration problems at work: For individuals who never have concentration problems at work, 17.9% work remotely, 64.7% work in the office, and 17.4% work in a hybrid model. For those who rarely have concentration problems at work, 22.7% work remotely, 54.3% work in the office, and 23.0% work in a hybrid model. For those who sometimes have concentration problems at work, 24.8% work remotely, 52.7% work in the office, and 22.5% work in a hybrid model. For those who often have concentration problems at work, 30.0% work remotely, 50.0% work in the office, and 20.0% work in a hybrid model. For those who always have concentration problems at work, 16.0% work remotely, 67.4% work in the office, and 16.6% work in a hybrid model. The chi-square test indicates significant associations between remote and office working ($P \sim 0$) and between remote and hybrid working ($P \sim 0$). Significant associations are observed between remote and office working, and between remote and hybrid working, across various levels of concentration problems at work. These results highlight the impact of well-being concerns such as tiredness and concentration problems at work on the choice of working location. Understanding these factors can help organisations develop policies and strategies that support employees' well-being, reduce fatigue, and enhance focus.

Appendix.4: Supplementary details of Logistic regression initial model

A.4.1 Logistic regression analysis

Logistic regression analysis regarding work at the workplace vs remote comparisons without including living location urban/rural results summarised below: Dependent variable: work location remote=0; workplace= 1

Variable	Reference Category	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	Significance
Gender	Man (Reference)			
- Woman		0.947	0.895 - 1.002	*
Age Groups	18-24 (Reference)			
- 25-34		0.718	0.636 - 0.811	***
- 35-44		0.630	0.557 - 0.713	***
- 45-55		0.722	0.635 - 0.819	***
- 56+		0.802	0.697 - 0.921	***
Job Insecurity	Secure (Reference)			
Insecure (JQ_CD_insecrty)		1.128	1.037 - 1.228	***
Job Intensity	Low Intensity (Reference)			
High Intensity (JQ_CD_intensty)		0.985	0.929 - 1.046	
Physical Demand	Low Demand (Reference)			
High Demand (JQ_CD_physdemd)		2.525	2.347 - 2.717	***
Social Discrimination	No Discrimination (Reference)			
Discriminated (JQ_CD_socdiscr)		1.317	1.200 - 1.445	***
Unsocial Hours	Regular Hours (Reference)			
Unsocial Hours (JQ_CD_unsocial)		1.548	1.378 - 1.739	***
Autonomy	High Autonomy (Reference)			
Low Autonomy (JQ_CR_autonomy)		0.785	0.744 - 0.829	***
Flexible Work	No Flexibility (Reference)			
Flexibility (JQ_CR_flexwork)		0.447	0.399 - 0.500	***
Social Support	High Support (Reference)			
Low Support (JQ_CR_socsuppt)		0.944	0.876 - 1.017	
Intrinsic Rewards	High Rewards (Reference)			
Low Rewards (JQ_CR_intrinsc)		1.006	0.946 - 1.070	
Realisation	High Realisation (Reference)			
Low Realisation (JQ_CR_realistn)		1.464	1.376 - 1.557	***
Training	Received (Reference)			
No Training (JQ_CR_training)		0.797	0.752 - 0.846	***
Physical Risk	Low Risk (Reference)			
High Risk (JQ_CD_physrisk)		2.470	2.290 - 2.665	***

Work Strain	Low Strain (Reference)			
High Strain (strain_high)		0.860	0.748 - 0.989	**
Work-Life Balance	Balanced (Reference)			
Not Well (work_life_balance)				
Well		1.086	1.023 - 1.152	***
Not Very Well		1.275	1.159 - 1.403	***
Not at All Well		1.447	1.232 - 1.700	***
Sector	Public Sector (Reference)			
Private Sector (ps_dummy_encoded)		1.119	1.057 - 1.185	***
Employment Type	Part-Time (Reference)			
Full-Time (part_time)		1.050	0.971 - 1.135	
Seniority	Less than 1 Year (Reference)			
1 to 4 Years (seniority_cat)		0.804	0.733 - 0.882	***
5 to 9 Years (seniority_cat)		0.854	0.770 - 0.947	***
10 or more (seniority_cat)		0.881	0.797 - 0.973	**
Night Work Frequency	Never (Reference)			
Rarely (night)		0.640	0.593 - 0.690	***
Sometimes (night)		0.684	0.614 - 0.762	***
Often (night)		1.092	0.963 - 1.238	
Always (night)		1.233	1.000 - 1.520	*
Free Time Work	Never (Reference)			
Several Times a Week (freetime_work)		1.041	0.898 - 1.206	
Several Times a Month (freetime_work)		1.292	1.119 - 1.491	***
Less Often (freetime_work)		2.557	2.181 - 2.997	***
Ability to Take Time Off	Easy (Reference)			
Fairly Easy (able_hour_off)		0.590	0.530 - 0.657	***
Fairly Difficult (able_hour_off)		0.787	0.696 - 0.890	***
Presenteeism	No (Reference)			
Yes (presenteeism_dummy)		0.724	0.681 - 0.770	***
Boss Gender	Man (Reference)			
Woman (boss_gender)		0.853	0.805 - 0.903	***
ICT Use	No (Reference)			
Yes (useICT)		0.159	0.142 - 0.179	***
Household Size	Small (Reference)			
Large (hh_size_total)		1.061	1.040 - 1.082	***
Long Working Hours	Less than 48 hours (Reference)			
More than 48 hours (long_hours)		1.108	1.013 - 1.213	**
Noise at Work	Low (Reference)			
High (noise_jq)		0.710	0.665 - 0.757	***

App.Suppl.Table 10: Logistic regression analysis regarding work at the workplace vs remote comparisons without including living location urban/rural results summarised below:

***** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1**

Gender: Women are slightly less likely to work on-site compared to men, with an odds ratio (OR) of 0.947, suggesting an association indicating that women have a 5.3% lower likelihood of working on-site. This result is marginally significant ($p < 0.1$).

Age Groups: Being in the 25-34 age group is associated with a 28.2% lower likelihood of working on-site compared to the 18-24 reference group (OR = 0.718, $p < 0.01$).

Similarly, being aged 35-44 and 45-55 is associated with a significantly lower likelihood of on-site work, with ORs of 0.630 and 0.722, respectively, indicating reductions in likelihood by 37% and 27.8% ($p < 0.01$ for both).

For employees aged 56 and older, the likelihood of working on-site is 19.8% lower compared to the reference group (OR = 0.802, $p < 0.01$).

Job Characteristics: Job insecurity is associated with a 12.8% higher likelihood of working on-site (OR = 1.128, $p < 0.01$).

High physical demand in a job is strongly associated with an increased likelihood of on-site work, with an OR of 2.525, indicating a 152.5% higher likelihood ($p < 0.01$).

Social discrimination at work is associated with a 31.7% higher likelihood of on-site work (OR = 1.317, $p < 0.01$).

In contrast, high autonomy is associated with a 21.5% lower likelihood of working on-site (OR = 0.785, $p < 0.01$), and flexible work arrangements are associated with a 55.3% lower likelihood of on-site work (OR = 0.447, $p < 0.01$).

High physical risk at work is associated with a 147% higher likelihood of on-site work (OR = 2.470, $p < 0.01$).

Work-Life Balance: Poor work-life balance is significantly associated with a higher likelihood of on-site work. Employees who report their work-life balance as 'Not at all well' have a 44.7% higher likelihood of on-site work (OR = 1.447, $p < 0.01$).

Employment Type: Full-time employment shows no statistically significant association with on-site work compared to part-time employment (OR = 1.050).

Seniority: Greater seniority is associated with a lower likelihood of working on-site. For example, employees with 1 to 4 years of experience are 19.6% less likely to work on-site compared to those with less than a year of experience (OR = 0.804, $p < 0.01$).

Night Work Frequency: Rarely working at night is associated with a significantly lower likelihood of on-site work (OR = 0.640, $p < 0.01$), while always working at night is associated with a 23.3% higher likelihood of on-site work (OR = 1.233, $p < 0.1$).

Use of ICT: The use of information and communication technology (ICT) is strongly associated with remote work, as those who use ICT are 84.1% less likely to work on-site (OR = 0.159, $p < 0.01$).

Household Size: Larger household size is associated with a slightly higher likelihood of working on-site, with an OR of 1.061, indicating a 6.1% increase in likelihood ($p < 0.01$).

Long Working Hours: Working more than 48 hours a week is associated with a 10.8% higher likelihood of on-site work compared to those working fewer hours (OR = 1.108, $p < 0.05$).

Noise at Work: High levels of noise at work are associated with a 29% lower likelihood of on-site work (OR = 0.710, $p < 0.01$).

Raw code Details of Logistic regression model (OR=1 ref. category)

loc_work_adjusted ~ g	Odds Ratio	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Man	1	
Woman	.947	.027	-1.89	.059	.895	1.002	*
age_groups	1	
25-34	.718	.045	-5.34	0	.636	.811	***
35-44	.63	.04	-7.31	0	.557	.713	***
45-55	.722	.047	-5.03	0	.635	.819	***
56+	.802	.057	-3.11	.002	.697	.921	***
JQ_CD_insecrty	1.128	.049	2.79	.005	1.037	1.228	***
JQ_CD_intensty	.985	.03	-0.49	.626	.929	1.046	
JQ_CD_physdem d	2.525	.094	24.77	0	2.347	2.717	***
JQ_CD_socdiscr	1.317	.063	5.79	0	1.2	1.445	***
JQ_CD_unsocial	1.548	.092	7.37	0	1.378	1.739	***
JQ_CR_autonomy	.785	.022	-8.73	0	.744	.829	***
JQ_CR_flexwork	.447	.026	-14.04	0	.399	.5	***
JQ_CR_socsuppt	.944	.036	-1.51	.13	.876	1.017	
JQ_CR_intrinsc	1.006	.032	0.20	.84	.946	1.07	
JQ_CR_realistn	1.464	.046	12.13	0	1.376	1.557	***
JQ_CR_training	.797	.024	-7.53	0	.752	.846	***
JQ_CD_physrisk	2.47	.095	23.40	0	2.29	2.665	***
strain_high	1	
TRUE	.86	.061	-2.11	.035	.748	.989	**
work_life_balanc e	1	
Well	1.086	.033	2.70	.007	1.023	1.152	***
Not very well	1.275	.062	4.99	0	1.159	1.403	***
Not at all well	1.447	.119	4.50	0	1.232	1.7	***
ps_dummy_encod ed	1	
private_sector	1.119	.033	3.85	0	1.057	1.185	***
part_time	1	
Full time	1.05	.042	1.22	.222	.971	1.135	
seniority_cat	1	
1 to 4 years	.804	.038	-4.63	0	.733	.882	***

5 to 9 years	.854	.045	-2.98	.003	.77	.947	***
10 or more	.881	.045	-2.49	.013	.797	.973	**
night	1	
Rarely	.64	.025	-11.63	0	.593	.69	***
Sometimes	.684	.038	-6.91	0	.614	.762	***
Often	1.092	.07	1.37	.169	.963	1.238	
Always	1.233	.132	1.96	.05	1	1.52	*
freetime_work	1	
Several times a week	1.041	.078	0.53	.595	.898	1.206	
Several times a month	1.292	.094	3.50	0	1.119	1.491	***
Less often	2.557	.207	11.58	0	2.181	2.997	***
Never	5.02	.417	19.41	0	4.265	5.909	***
able_hour_off	1	
Fairly easy	.59	.032	-9.62	0	.53	.657	***
Fairly difficult	.787	.049	-3.82	0	.696	.89	***
Very difficult (omitted)	1	
presenteeism_dummy	1	
Yes	.724	.023	-10.33	0	.681	.77	***
boss_gender	1	
A woman	.853	.025	-5.45	0	.805	.903	***
uselCT	1	
Yes	.159	.01	-30.66	0	.142	.179	***
hh_size_total	1.061	.011	5.80	0	1.04	1.082	***
long_hours	1	
less than 48 hours [~] k	1.108	.051	2.23	.026	1.013	1.213	**
noise_jq	1	
Low	.71	.024	-10.35	0	.665	.757	***
Constant	4.809	.745	10.14	0	3.55	6.514	***
Mean dependent var	0.563		SD dependent var		0.496		
Pseudo r-squared	0.228		Number of obs		31526		
Chi-square	9842.607		Prob > chi2		0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	33446.952		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		33806.370		
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$							

App.Supl.Table: 11a Logistic regression analysis of potential factors associated with work location (without Urbanity variable)

A.4.2. Logistic regression analysis

Logistic regression analysis results, regarding work at the workplace vs remote comparisons including urbanity variable significant results summarised below:

Variable	Odds Ratio	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf Interval]	Sig
Urban	.722	.085	-2.76	.006	.572 .91	***
Gender						
Man	1
Woman	.994	.106	-0.06	.956	.807 1.225	
Age groups						
16-24	1
25-34	.671	.134	-2.00	.046	.454 .992	**
35-44	.464	.098	-3.65	0	.308 .701	***
45-55	.523	.116	-2.92	.003	.339 .808	***
56+	.42	.104	-3.49	0	.258 .683	***
Job Quality						
Job insecurity	1.077	.158	0.51	.614	.808 1.435	
Work intensity	.759	.083	-2.52	.012	.613 .941	**
Physical demands	2.406	.342	6.18	0	1.821 3.178	***
Discrimination	1.501	.248	2.45	.014	1.085 2.076	**
Unsocial working hours	1.756	.368	2.69	.007	1.165 2.647	***
Autonomy	.821	.087	-1.87	.061	.667 1.009	*
Flexibility of working hours	.497	.094	-3.68	0	.343 .722	***
Social support	.798	.114	-1.58	.114	.603 1.056	
Intrinsic rewards	1.186	.136	1.48	.139	.946 1.485	
Opportunities for self-realisation	1.471	.178	3.18	.001	1.16 1.865	***
Training opportunities	1.007	.113	0.06	.953	.807 1.256	
Physical risks	1.928	.276	4.58	0	1.455 2.554	***
High Job Strain						
No	1
Yes	.705	.175	-1.41	.159	.434 1.146	
Work-life balance						
Very well	1
Well	1.099	.126	0.83	.408	.878 1.376	
Not very well	1.031	.184	0.17	.866	.726 1.463	
Not at all well	1.196	.315	0.68	.496	.714 2.005	
Sector						
Other	1
Private	1.222	.137	1.79	.073	.981 1.521	*
Type of employment						
Part-time	1
Full-time	1.988	.34	4.01	0	1.422 2.78	***
Seniority						
Less than a year	1
1 to 4 years	.98	.158	-0.13	.898	.715 1.343	

5 to 9 years	1.023	.188	0.12	.902	.713	1.467	
10 or more	1.305	.239	1.46	.145	.912	1.868	
Night work							
Never	1	
Rarely	.477	.066	-5.35	0	.364	.626	***
Sometimes	.636	.114	-2.53	.011	.448	.903	**
Often	.639	.132	-2.17	.03	.426	.957	**
Always	.929	.305	-0.22	.823	.488	1.768	
Ability to work in free time							
Daily	1	
Several times a week	1.318	.289	1.26	.207	.858	2.024	
Several times a month	1.667	.357	2.38	.017	1.095	2.538	**
Less often	3.997	.998	5.55	0	2.45	6.519	***
Never	7.619	2.034	7.61	0	4.514	12.857	***
Ability to take time off							
Very easy	1	
Fairly easy	.634	.115	-2.50	.012	.444	.906	**
Fairly difficult	1.134	.25	0.57	.568	.736	1.747	
Very difficult (omitted)	1	
Working during sickness (Presenteeism)							
No	1	
Yes	.946	.107	-0.49	.626	.758	1.182	
Gender of boss							
Man	1	
Woman	.833	.09	-1.69	.09	.674	1.029	*
Computer usage							
No	1	
Yes	.084	.02	-10.53	0	.053	.133	***
Total household size	1.251	.042	6.63	0	1.171	1.337	***
Working hours (weekly)							
48 hours and above	1	
Less than 48 hours	.778	.118	-1.65	.098	.579	1.047	*
Noise exposure							
High	1	
Low	.561	.069	-4.67	0	.441	.715	***
Constant	6.791	3.851	3.38	.001	2.235	20.634	***
Model fit statistics							
Mean dependent var	0.679		SD dependent var			0.467	
Pseudo r-squared	0.293		Number of observations			2797	
Chi-square	1027.536		Prob > chi2			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)	2573.116		Bayesian crit. (BIC)			2834.314	
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$							

App.Suppl.Table 11b: Logistic regression analysis of potential factors associated with work location

Logistic regression analysis regarding Burn-out existence including urbanity variable significant results summarised below:

variable	Odds Ratio	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Work location							
Hybrid	1	
Workplace	1.107	.073	1.55	.122	.973	1.26	
Remote	1.026	.076	0.35	.726	.887	1.187	
Gender							
Man	1	
Woman	1.225	.064	3.90	0	1.106	1.357	***
Age groups							
16-24	1	
25-34	1.256	.137	2.09	.036	1.015	1.555	**
35-44	1.254	.139	2.05	.041	1.009	1.558	**
45-55	1.223	.14	1.77	.077	.978	1.53	*
56+	1.058	.135	0.44	.658	.824	1.358	
Job Quality							
Job insecurity	1.588	.105	6.99	0	1.395	1.807	***
Work intensity	2.415	.159	13.39	0	2.123	2.748	***
Physical demands	.915	.058	-1.41	.159	.809	1.035	
Discrimination	1.974	.135	9.93	0	1.726	2.258	***
Unsocial working hours	.937	.092	-0.66	.508	.774	1.135	
Autonomy	.873	.044	-2.67	.008	.79	.965	***
Flexibility of working hours	.554	.047	-6.95	0	.469	.654	***
Social support	.728	.045	-5.14	0	.645	.822	***
Intrinsic rewards	.629	.038	-7.59	0	.558	.709	***
Opportunities for self-realization	.734	.039	-5.79	0	.661	.815	***
Training opportunities	1.139	.062	2.37	.018	1.023	1.268	**
Physical risks	1.082	.068	1.24	.215	.956	1.224	
High Job Strain							
No	1	
Yes	.94	.09	-0.65	.515	.779	1.133	
Work-life balance							
Very well	1	
Well	1.32	.08	4.60	0	1.172	1.485	***
Not very well	2.174	.167	10.10	0	1.87	2.527	***
Not at all well	3.102	.349	10.07	0	2.488	3.867	***
Sector							
Other	1	
Private	.915	.048	-1.70	.089	.826	1.014	*
Type of employment							
Part-time	1	
Full-time	1.096	.079	1.28	.201	.952	1.262	
Seniority							
Less than a year	1	
1 to 4 years	1.097	.094	1.08	.28	.927	1.297	

5 to 9 years	1.101	.106	1.00	.319	.911	1.329	
10 or more	1.106	.103	1.08	.279	.922	1.326	
Night work							
Never	1	
Rarely	.86	.06	-2.16	.031	.75	.986	**
Sometimes	.78	.071	-2.75	.006	.653	.931	***
Often	.972	.093	-0.30	.764	.806	1.171	
Always	.779	.118	-1.65	.099	.58	1.048	*
Ability to work in free time							
Daily	1	
Several times a week	.763	.087	-2.37	.018	.61	.954	**
Several times a month	.688	.077	-3.33	.001	.552	.858	***
Less often	.448	.057	-6.34	0	.35	.575	***
Never	.482	.062	-5.65	0	.375	.621	***
Ability to take time off							
Very easy	1	
Fairly easy	.584	.045	-6.99	0	.503	.679	***
Fairly difficult	.831	.071	-2.17	.03	.703	.983	**
Very difficult (omitted)	1	
Working during sickness (Presenteeism)							
No	1	
Yes	1.569	.08	8.83	0	1.419	1.734	***
Gender of boss							
Man	1	
Woman	1.101	.057	1.86	.063	.995	1.219	*
Computer usage							
No	1	
Yes	.988	.073	-0.17	.868	.854	1.142	
Total household size	.973	.017	-1.51	.13	.94	1.008	
Working hours (weekly)							
48 hours and above	1	
Less than 48 hours	.859	.061	-2.14	.032	.747	.987	**
Noise exposure							
High	1	
Low	.738	.04	-5.61	0	.664	.821	***
Constant	.295	.075	-4.80	0	.179	.485	***
Mean dependent var	0.188		SD dependent var		0.391		
Pseudo r-squared	0.170		Number of observations		14063		
Chi-square	2308.879		Prob > chi2		0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	11381.002		Bayesian crit. (BIC)		11720.811		
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$							

App.Suppl. Table 12: Logistic regression analysis of potential factors associated with Emotional Burn-out

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